

HEXA-X-II

A holistic flagship towards the 6G network platform and system, to inspire digital transformation, for the world to act together in meeting needs in society and ecosystems with novel 6G services

Deliverable D2.5 Final overall 6G system design

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Abstract

This document is the fifth deliverable of Hexa-X-II Work Package 2 (WP2)– “Final overall 6G system design”. It provides the final version of the overall 6G system design, completed with specific system views on fundamental aspects of the 6G: radio interfaces and protocols, 6G new services and their exposure, multistakeholder service realization and pervasive functionalities for the AI/ML and Security, Privacy and Resilience (SPR) aspects. A methodological analysis of enablers is proposed to select those which matches with reminded requirements, design principles and sustainability criteria from the work package 1, while focusing the analysis on a concrete collaborative robot use-case typically envisaged with 6G systems. Enablers encompass those from Hexa-X-II on radio interface and protocols, E2E intent-based management and SPR, but also some from other SNS-JU projects on complementary areas. This document then makes a status on Proof of Concepts realization which will be further developed in the last WP2 deliverable. Lastly, an assessment of the WP2 work with respect to the project objectives is provided.

Keywords

6G, system requirement, E2E system, architecture, radio interface, radio protocol, intent-based management, privacy, security, resilience, SNS-JU projects, overall design, Proof of Concept.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is the fifth deliverable of the Work Package 2 (WP2) of the Hexa-X-II project, titled “Final overall 6G system design”, which presents the revised design of a comprehensive end-to-end (E2E) 6G system architecture. The document summarizes the key findings to build future 6G systems relying on key technical differentiators and new services offered by the 6G, considering economic, environmental and social sustainability (including trustworthiness) as fundamental pillars of the system. While building on the previous WP2 deliverables, the document can be read by new readers without necessary prior knowledge on those deliverables, which are referenced for readers interested in reading about the additional details.

Future 6G systems will have to cope with stringent use cases comprising immersive experiences, collaborative robots (cobots), digital twins, etc. These use cases impose strong operational requirements in terms of modularity and scalability, resilience and security, overall sustainability goals and intent-based automation. Ten design principles are therefore elaborated for future 6G systems: 1. Support and exposure of 6G services and capabilities; 2. Full automation and optimization; 3. Flexibility to different network scenarios; 4. Network scalability; 5. Resilience and availability; 6. Persistent security and privacy; 7. Internal interfaces are cloud optimized; 8. Separation of concerns of network functions; 9. Network simplification in comparison to previous generations and 10. Minimizing environmental footprint and enabling sustainable networks.

To make the implementation of such a system possible, Hexa-X-II and other Smart Network and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS-JU) projects are developing enablers, i.e., any technical asset that makes it possible to introduce or enhance a 6G capability. The document consequently includes three dimensions to build the 6G system architecture:

- A description of those enablers, ranging from radio interfaces and protocols, intent-based service management, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML) embedded functionalities and robust security, privacy, and resilience (SPR) measures.
- A methodology to classify and filter the enablers with respect to key requirements, design principles, and the sustainability ambitions defined by the Hexa-X-II WP1. To provide a concrete example, the methodology has also been applied to a precise cobots use case, incorporating feedback from Proof of Concepts (PoCs) and complementary enablers from other SNS-JU projects.
- A high-level and overarching view of the 6G system architecture, which includes and organizes the selected enablers. However, WP2, in tight collaboration with partners from all Hexa-X-II work packages, also complemented this overall 6G system blueprint architecture with specific system views highlighting key differentiators of a 6G system, including:
 - Radio Interfaces and Protocols: Innovations on radio user plane protocols, mobility procedures, and application-network interactions are proposed, contributing to the overall efficiency and flexibility of the 6G system.
 - New 6G Services: The blueprint outlines the integration of new 6G service types such as Sensing, Compute, and AI as a Service, and their exposure across the ecosystem.
 - Multi-Stakeholder Dimension: The document addresses the multi-stakeholder dimension of E2E 6G services, highlighting the need for collaborative design and implementation.
 - Pervasive Functionalities: The blueprint incorporates pervasive functionalities to embed AI/ML mechanisms and SPR functionalities, ensuring a secure and resilient 6G system.

Additionally, the deliverable provides a status on the E2E System-Level validation phase design and the experimental-based assessment design to validate the architecture’s robustness and readiness for future real-world deployment. The primary outcomes highlight the successful implementation of advanced application features, demonstrating the system’s capacity to support complex use cases like cobots and immersive environments. The implementation incorporates new devices with energy harvesting capabilities, key enablers such as advanced management and orchestration enablers, the system’s integration fabric, an intent-based management framework, AI-powered closed-loop automation, as well as new Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) leveraging exposure of application enablement platform capabilities, such as Quality of

Demand (QoD) and device status/density. These results underscore the system's adaptability, scalability, and ability to deliver reliable and secure operations across diverse domains. Future work will focus on leveraging the proof-of-concepts towards a comprehensive assessment phase against the project's established Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVI)s, which will be reported in the WP2 final deliverable D2.6.

Thanks to this structured methodology, this deliverable contributes to the fulfilment of the Hexa-X-II objectives by:

- Presenting a comprehensive blueprint for a sustainable 6G platform, outlining its design principles and analysing key technical aspects with respect to their compliance with economic, environmental, and social sustainability goals.
- Innovating in 6G radio protocols, focusing on radio user plane protocols, mobility procedures, and application-network interactions. It extends existing 5G radio protocols and operations to minimize standardization work and utilize the existing ecosystem of devices and infrastructure, positioning 6G radio design as an evolution of 5G. It analyses the integration of other 6G capabilities, like Joint Communication And Sensing (JCAS), Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN), and AI-ML, into the radio protocol design. This integration requires extending existing procedures, updating reference signals, and adding new capabilities for communication between the UE and the network.
- Highlighting the development of an intent-based service management framework that contributes to efficient network Management and Orchestration design and implementation. This framework emphasizes scalability, flexibility, and automation, ensuring seamless E2E service provisioning and fulfilment in order to meet the 6G E2E system requirements.
- Identifying and mitigating specific threats and vulnerabilities unique to 6G (the 6G security delta), a comprehensive framework for security, privacy, and resilience has been developed across different layers of the network relying on the concept of SPR controls. These controls, including physical layer security, data-sensitive aspects of JCAS, generalized AI application, and a transparent notary service among other ones, are deeply integrated with other system-wide enablers, acting as mechanisms to detect and mitigate the impact of specific threats on system performance while prioritizing trustworthiness.

This deliverable provides a valuable foundation for future research and development activities, paving the way for a sustainable and trustworthy 6G future. Further research and standardization efforts are required to address remaining challenges, including:

- Further work is needed to fully achieve the desired radio design principles and link these innovations to the 6G Key Value Indicators (KVI)s.
- Assessing security vulnerabilities for intent generation and maintenance and developing policies for intent conflict resolution.
- Consolidating controls and enablers to address the 6G security delta, particularly those at early Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs).
- Extending and promoting the adoption of the proposed enabler selection methodology across future SNS-JU projects and various stakeholders.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Term	Description
2D	Two Dimensional
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Program
3P	Third-Party
4/5/6G	Fourth/Fifth/Sixth Generation
5GC	5G Core
5GSA	5G Standalone
AAA	Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting
ADC	Analog to Digital Converter
ADSR	Activate, Deactivate, Suspend, Resume

AEP	Application Enablement Platform
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIoT	Ambient Internet of Things
AIaaS(F)	AI-as-a-Service (Function)
AICP	AI-enabled Control Plane
AM	Acknowledged Mode
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
API	Application Programming Interface
ARQ	Automatic Repeat Request
ASP	Application Service Provider
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
BCS	Beyond Communication Services
BS	Base Station
CA	Carrier Aggregation
CaaS	Compute as a Service
CAPIF	Common API Framework
CCF	Confidential Consortium Framework
CCN	Compute Controlling Node
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CE	Control Element
CFR	Carrier Frequency Reference
CIA	Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability
CHO	Conditional Handover
CKKS	Cheon-Kim-Kim-Song (homomorphic encryption scheme)
CL	Closed Loop
CN	Core Network
CMF	Compute Management Function
Cobots	Collaborative robot
CompN	Computing Node
COP	Capability Operator
CP	Control Plane
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRS	Cell-specific Reference Signal
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete operations

CSI	Channel State Information
CSP	Communication Service Provider
CU/DU	Centralized Unit/Distributed Unit
DataF	Data Functions
DataOps	Data Operations
DC	Dual Connectivity
DCI	Downlink Control Information
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DevSecOps	Development, Security and Operations
DIR	Declarative Intent Reconciliation
DL	Downlink
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DMRS	Demodulation Reference Signal
DN	Data Network
DNN	Deep Neural Networks
DNS	Domain Name System
DoS	Denial of Service
DPoD	Digital Post Distortion
DRB	Data Radio Bearer
DSM	Digital Service Manager
DSM-IME	Digital Service Manager Intent Management Entity
DSC	Digital Service Consumer
DSP	Digital Service Provider
D-SSB	Dynamic or Dedicated SSB
DT	Digital Twin
DTMRG	Data Transfer within Measurements Radio Gap
DTX	Discontinuous Transmission
E2E	End-to-end
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FA	Functionality Allocation
FASIL	FrAmework for Secure and prIvacy-preserving federated Learning
FL	Federated Learning
FR1/2/3	Frequency Range 1, Range 2, Range 3
GBR	Guaranteed Bitrate

GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
gNB	Next generation node B
GPU	Graphics Processing Units
GS	Ground Station
GSM	GSM Association
HAPS	High Altitude Platforms
HARQ	Hybrid Automatic Repeat reQuest
HLS	Higher Layer Split
HO	Handover
IAB	Integrated Access and Backhaul
IBI	Intent-Based Interface
IBM	Intent-Based Management
IBN	Intent-Based Networking
IDM	Intrusion Detection Mechanism
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IF	Integration Fabric
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IME	Intent Management Entity
JCAS	Joint Communication And Sensing
KG	Knowledge Graph
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
KV	Key Value
L1/2/...	Layer 1, Layer 2, ...
LCID	Logical Channel Identifier
LDPC	Low-Density Parity-Check
LEO	Low-Earth Orbit
LiDAR	Laser imaging Detection And Ranging
LLS	Low Layer Split
LoRa	Long Range
LPP	LTE Positioning Protocol
LPWA	Low Power Wide Area
LOS	Line-Of-Sight

LoT	Level of Trust
LoTAF	LoT Assessment Function
LTM	L1/L2 Triggered Mobility
M&O	Management and Orchestration
MAC	Medium Access Control
MC	Multi-Connectivity
MCE	Management Capability Exposure
MD	Management Domain
MDP	Multi-domain Data Plane
MgtN	Management Node
(D-)MIMO	(Distributed) Multiple Input Multiple Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps(F)	Machine Learning Operations (Function)
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MRSS	Multi-Radio Spectrum Sharing
MSC	Message Sequence Chart
MTC	Machine Type Communication
NACK	Negative Acknowledgment
NAS	Non-Access Stratum
NBI	North-Bound Interface
NCRs	Network-Controlled Repeaters
NDT	Network Digital Twin
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NF	Network Function
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NLOS	Non-Line-Of-Sight
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NOP	Network Operators
NPU	Neural Processing Units
NR	New Radio
NRF	Network function Repository Function
NTN	Non-Terrestrial Networks
NW	Network

NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function
OAM	Operation, Administration, and Management
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
ON	Offloading Node
PCell	Primary Cell
PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
PDU	Protocol Data Unit
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
PHY	Physical (layer)
PLD	Physical Layer Deception
PLS	Physical Layer Security
PoC	Proof-of-Concept
ProSe	Proximity Services
QFI	QoS Flow Identifier
QoD	Quality of Demand
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
QUIC	Quick UDP Internet Connections
(P)RACH	(Physical) Random Access Channel
RAN	Radio Access Network
RBD	Reliability Block Diagram
RCA	Root Cause Analysis
RDI	Reflective QoS flow to DRB mapping Indication
REST	Representational State Transfer
RF	Radio Frequency
RFID	Radio-Frequency Identification
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
RLC	Radio Link Control
RLF	Radio Link Failure
RQI	Reflective QoS Indication
RRC	Radio Resource Control
RRM	Radio Resource Management
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
RU	Radio Units

Rx	Reception
SAD	Single Administrative Domains
SAN	Sandboxing Environment
SAREF	Smart Appliances REference ontology
SAT	Satellite
SBA	Service-Based Architecture
SCF	Sensing Control Function
SCITT	Supply Chain Integrity, Transparency and Trust
SCRAPI	SCITT Reference API
SCU	Sensing Control Unit
SDAP	Service Data Application Protocol
SDK	Software Development Kits
SDN	Software Defined Network
SDR	Software Defined Radio
SDU	Service Data Unit
SeaaS	Sensing as a Service
SecA	Security Agent
SeMF	Sensing Management Function
SKG	Secret Key Generation
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLO	Service Level Objective
SMF	Session Management Function
SN	Sequence Number
SNS-JU	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
SoC	System-on-Chip
SpCell	Special Cell
SPF	Sensing Processing Functions
SPR	Security, Privacy, and Resilience
SPU	Sensing Processing Unit
SRB	Signalling Radio Bearer
(D/E/I/M-)SSB	(Dedicated/ Extended periodicity/Idle mode/Mobile-) Synchronization Signal Block
SU	Sensing Unit
TB	Transport Block
TCI	Transmission Configuration Indication

TDD	Time Division Duplex
TechCo	Technology Company
TLA	Trust Level Agreements
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TM Forum	TeleManagement Forum
TN	Terrestrial Network
TNS	Transparent Notary Service
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TRP	Transmission Point
Tx	Transmission
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UCI	Uplink Control Information
UDM	Unified Data Management
UE	User Equipment
UI	User Interface
UL	Uplink
UM	Unacknowledged Mode
UP	User Plane
UPF	User Plane Function
USRP	Universal Software Radio Peripheral
VCS	Version Control System
VENENA	Visual ENcryption for Eavesdropping NegAtion
VR	Virtual Reality
VM	Virtual Machine
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network
WP	Work Package
WT	WLAN Terminal
XAI	eXplainable AI
XR	eXtended Reality
ZED	Zero-Energy Device
ZSM	Zero-touch network and Service Management

1 Introduction

Hexa-X-II is the 6G Flagship project under the European Union Horizon Europe research and innovation program Smart Network and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) [HEXA2]. This document is the fifth public deliverable of Work Package 2 (WP2), and it provides the final overall 6G system design, before the last Deliverable [HEX225-D26] of WP2 latter this year on the final end-to-end (E2E) system evaluation results of the overall 6G system design.

The document presents the conclusion of the WP2 efforts in designing a comprehensive and robust 6G E2E system. It builds upon previous deliverables, aiming to provide a self-contained and detailed overview of the 6G system architecture, summarizing and updating when necessary the requirements and design principles, as well as the enablers encompassing all aspects of the future 6G architecture from the low level radio protocol design to the E2E intent-based management (IBM) possibly across multiple involved stakeholders and associated pervasive functionalities such as the Security, Privacy and Resilience (SPR).

This final system architecture presents detailed updates of WP2 enablers introduced in the previous iteration of the 6G E2E system design [HEX224-D23], as well as a short description of enablers from other Smart Network and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS-JU) projects. The comprehensive enabler selection methodology of [HEX224-D23] is reviewed and extended to include the Key Value Indicators (KVI) from the WP1, which describe the environmental sustainability, digital inclusiveness, and trustworthiness, and their impact on the 6G E2E system.

The document aims at serving as a crucial reference point for understanding the evolution of the 6G E2E system, highlighting key innovations and advancements achieved within Work Package 2 and beyond. It is intended for a broad audience, including researchers, engineers, and stakeholders involved in the development and deployment of 6G technologies.

1.1 Objective of the document

The main objective of the document is to provide the final version of the E2E 6G system blueprint, relying on a structured methodology to develop, analyse and select critical enablers required for the realisation of a 6G E2E system, compliant with the system requirements and design principles defined in previous deliverables.

In Hexa-X-II, an enabler is defined as any technical asset that makes it possible to realize or enhance a 6G capability. It is recursive, e.g., 6G system enables new use cases, and 6G radio is an enabler of 6G system to achieve system requirements. A 6G enabler can be further classified into different types that are extensible, e.g., architecture, system component, process, algorithms, etc.

The objectives of the document can be organised around three different areas:

- A final update of various enablers, either directly studied within the WP2, or in close collaboration with other work packages (for enablers described in their respective final deliverables in particular [HEX225-D35], [HEX25-D45], [HEX225-D65]), or from other SNS-JU projects such as CENTRIC [SNS-CENT], ADROIT-6G [SNS-ADR6G], ETHER [SNS-ETHER], 6G-SHINE [SNS-6GSH], PREDICT-6G [SNS-PRED6G], TERA6G [SNS-TERA6G], RIGOUROUS [SNS-RIG], ACROSS [SNS-ACR], HORSE [SNS-HOR] and CONFIDENTIAL6G [SNS-CONF6G].
- The final E2E 6G system blueprint, updated based on the analysis of these enablers, but also further detailed by zooming into key specific views highlighting key differentiators of 6G systems. This sub-objective also explores the migration path from 5G to 6G, highlighting key considerations and challenges for the introduction of 6G.
- An assessment of the WP2 work along the project with respect to the initial project objectives.

1.2 Structure of the document

With the objective to provide a document which is self-contained for an external reader, the document is structured to provide a clear and logical flow of information. Therefore, Chapter 2 first provides a summary and the necessary updates on the system requirements and design principles for a 6G E2E system. It also provides an outline of the methodology for the enabler selection of [HEX224-D23], which is further applied

in the final 6G E2E system design latter on in the document. Then, Chapters 3, 4 and 5 respectively describe specific enablers tightly related to radio protocols and flexible topologies, IBM, and SPR pervasive functionalities.

Chapter 6 is the core part of this document as it provides the final Hexa-X-II E2E 6G system blueprint, as well as finer grain specific system views on key 6G functionalities such as radio protocols and flexible topologies, new 6G services and the related exposure framework, multistakeholder aspects in the design of an 6G E2E system, and pervasive functionalities, including the SPR capabilities and the global Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML) functionalities and architecture. To avoid delays in introducing key 6G services, Chapter 6 also discusses a smooth migration path from the existing 5G to 6G networks. At last, a new analysis of the enablers from Hexa-X-II and other SNS-JU projects is provided, with respect to the system requirements, the design principles, and the sustainability constraints developed in the WP1. To have a concrete analysis, this updated enabler selection is applied to the specific collaborative robots (cobots) use case. Then, Chapter 7 provides a tangible analysis of the validation aspects of such 6G E2E system, both summarizing key realizations on the first two Proof-of-Concepts (PoC) as well as remaining plans for the final delivery of the WP2 PoC.

Before concluding, Chapter 8 provides a comprehensive assessment of the WP2 outcomes focusing on the analysis of the fulfilment of the two objectives in relation with the WP2 agenda, objective 2 “Description of the blueprint and system validation of the environmentally, economically and socially sustainable 6G platform” and objective 5 “Service orchestration aspects for the 6G platform”.

Finally, Chapter 9 concludes the document summarizing its key findings and contributions, highlighting the future directions, and identifying potential areas for further research and development.

Two additional annexes are also provided to detail several results of the task on the radio interfaces and protocols, and to provide short descriptions of enablers from other work packages and of the technical scope of other SNS-JU projects mentioned previously.

2 Requirements, design principles and enablers selection methodology

In [HEX223-D22], the project specifies use case requirements and operational requirements. These requirements were further expanded in [HEX224-D23], wherein use case requirements were re-categorised as use case functional requirements. Additionally, technical requirements were discussed, which specifically considered the KPIs and sustainability aspects of 6G.

However, it is worth reiterating the most important requirements from the 6G system, in terms of:

- What the 6G system should do?
- How the 6G system should behave or the constraints under which it must operate?

Subsequently, for improved understanding, the aforesaid requirements are hereby classified as *functional* and *non-functional* requirements, respectively.

Therefore, and to provide a self-contained document, this section delves into system requirements, encompassing the functional and non-functional requirements, in section 2.1, summarized from [HEX223-D22] and [HEX223-D23]. Subsequently, a summary of the design principles is provided in section 2.2. Lastly, in section 2.3, an update to the enabler selection methodology, which was developed in [HEX224-D23], is presented. The updated methodology considers the difficulty in quantifying Key Value Indicators (KVI), i.e., quantifiable targets for KVI may not be readily defined, and presents a strategy to fine-tune the enabler selection given the relatively subjective/consultative nature of the KVI inputs.

2.1 Summary of system requirements

2.1.1 Functional requirements

The functional requirements are focusing on functionalities (what) for the use cases (user perspective). The proposed 6G use cases pose several different functional requirements on the 6G system, many of which are inherited from 5G, e.g., mobility support, reliability, or service continuity. However, 6G is also expected to introduce new functional requirements e.g., pervasive AI/ML, intent-based interfaces, or sensing, which require novel functionalities to be considered when designing 6G. Further details on the envisioned functional requirements can be found in [HEX223-D22], [HEX224-D23]. A few examples related to advanced communication and computation requirements are presented below:

- *Positioning and Sensing*: By leveraging on the radar properties of the radio propagation, 6G is poised to broaden the utility of mobile networks, to provide cost-efficient detailed positioning and sensing capabilities to end-users. Also, as more users experience and consume common digital services e.g., a joint immersive experience, it will be important to be able to ensure accurate time synchronization between them. If multiple users are to interact simultaneously with the same digital object, they need to be accurately time synchronized from an end-user point of view and might also require accurate positioning.
- *Pervasive AI/ML capabilities*: The network should support AI/ML capabilities for various applications, including immersive experiences, robot coordination, and real-time processing of sensor data. 6G system will ensure the use of AI-native network functions and data collection framework, wherever it delivers gains and at the same time ensure explainability and adherence to sustainability goals.
- *Compute capabilities*: The network should have the capability of reliable compute to handle the complex digital twin models and databases with the integrated advanced AI skills to simulate, steer, and predict. Compute offloading from the devices to the network of heavy processing tasks should also be supported.
- *Ubiquitous coverage*: As more and more mobile services become imperative to everyday life as well as indispensable for efficient industries, the expectation for connectivity wherever you are is continuing to rise. At least basic 6G services (e.g., video streaming, simpler low-tier XR services, etc.)

should be available everywhere, to facilitate truly global services, and to provide connectivity to unconnected or under-connected areas and regions, requiring the integration of terrestrial (TN) and non-terrestrial (NTN) networks, along with the seamless integration of multiple network types. Furthermore, with a large share of the data traffic consumed indoor, the 6G network should provide full-service coverage, both indoor and outdoor, despite challenges posed by signal penetration and propagation at higher frequencies.

- *Local Ad Hoc Connectivity:* The network should support local ad hoc connectivity for collaborative tasks involving machines like cobots. Direct communication between connected devices within a localized area enables the formation of task-specific subnetworks. These temporary, localized subnetworks, embedded within broader campus networks, optimize latency and reliability for collaborative operations.
- *High Privacy Protection:* Like previous generations, privacy will continue to be paramount to avoid any malicious disruption (tampering, interception, impersonation, abuse, etc.) of networks, devices, and services. The network should support the definition and verification of privacy requirements, incorporating them into service level requests and agreements.

2.1.2 Non-functional requirements

The non-functional requirements relate to how the 6G system behaves. They cover two aspects: system operations and performance of the services for the use cases. For the first aspect, non-functional requirements emphasize on automation, modularity, and resilience, ensuring scalable, efficient, and secure deployments. Key non-functional requirements, based on [HEX224-D23], [HEX223-D12], [HEX225-D14], include:

- *System Scalability:* Scalability is important, particularly as the volume of applications grows. The system should manage increasing demand to prevent network and compute congestion and maintain performance levels for high-demand scenarios. This requires an infrastructure that can be flexible to reconfigure the network topologies, along with effective orchestration to automate the dynamic scaling of services and resource, supports diverse applications and allows rapid adaptation. This also includes data-driven network management and a cloud-edge continuum for distributed computation. Additionally, integrating edge intelligence with rest of the infrastructure and data network ensures lower latency, offloads central infrastructure, and enables localized decision-making.
- *Resilience and Security:* Networks must withstand failures through redundancy, self-healing mechanisms, and rapid fault recovery. Additionally, security frameworks that protect data through cryptographic protocols and can detect anomalies should be provisioned by 6G system. Moreover, confidential computing ensures that even during processing, sensitive data remains protected. Lastly, AI-enabled automated responses to cyberattacks and vulnerabilities will be needed to enhance resilience.
- *Efficient Automation:* Management systems should interpret high-level user intents (e.g., “optimize latency”) and autonomously configure networks to meet these needs. This includes ML-based closed-loops at multiple levels, for feedback systems through continuous monitoring and for ensuring the intent fulfilling during the service lifetime. Next, coordination across multiple domains should be provisioned, including autonomous and third-party networks, for supporting complex applications. Effective automation should also provision real-time adaptation of services ensures optimal performance in dynamic environments. Additionally, 6G system will ensure the use of AI-native management services and the corresponding data framework to provision effective management and orchestration services.
- *Flexible radio protocols:* For the 6G system to achieve its potential, one of the methods is to introduce a flexible protocol stack in the radio access network (RAN). This should consider approaches such as radio resource control (RRC) simplification, improving/optimizing the data recovery and reordering mechanisms, making security features more optimized and in general ensuring as much flexibility as reasonably possible.
- *Mobility procedures:* For the mobility aspects, the 6G system should support a solution wherein the mobility procedures may be unified. Furthermore, it should be expected that the 6G system mobility

procedures are agnostic to network architecture/deployment options. Moreover, prevalent methods should be further optimized for 6G including support for frequency range 3 (FR3) centimetre-wave (7-15 GHz). Additionally, the inclusion of AI/ML and Joint Communications and Sensing (JCAS) towards improving mobility procedures should also be considered.

- *Environmental, Social and Economic Sustainability*: The power consumption optimizations through green network technologies and AI-driven energy management are critical for addressing concerns related to potential negative environmental impact, i.e., environmental sustainability footprint. Moreover, ubiquitous connectivity is key to bridge the digital divide. Inclusion will require well-designed APIs, to make the network and its AI-native capabilities accessible to third-party consumers. Risks due to privacy and data breaches should be mitigated. Furthermore, the system should also ensure a trustworthy AI framework. 6G systems should be designed for gradual deployment, tailored to specific needs and locations. Heavy computational services must provide benefits that justify their costs. Operating expenditures can be reduced with more automation and reliability and resilience in the system operations.
- *Performance requirements*: The use cases identified in Hexa-X-II reflect the diverse and complex performance requirements of 6G technologies [HEX223-D12], [HEX224-D23]. It's important to note that not all requirements will be met simultaneously, nor necessarily by the same network deployment.
 - Immersive experience: Use cases like seamless immersive reality and immersive gaming demand require:
 - *E2E latency* of <10 ms (split rendering), <50 ms (voice) and <150 ms (collaboration).
 - *User-experienced data rates* of <250 Mbps (both uplink and downlink), *area traffic capacity* of up to 250 Mbps/m² and *reliability* of up to 99.999%.
 - *Positioning accuracy* of < 10 cm, both horizontal and vertical.
 - Collaborative robots: Use cases such as cooperating mobile robots for warehouses will require:
 - *User-experienced data rates* of up to 10 Mbps and *positioning accuracy* up to 1 m.
 - *Bounded end-to-end latency* of up to 0.8 ms, *service-level reliability* of up to 99.99999% and support for *mobility* up to 20 km/h.
 - Physical awareness use cases: Use cases such as network-assisted mobility will require:
 - *User-experienced data rate* of up to 100 Mbps and *E2E latency* up to 20 ms
 - *Reliability and service availability* of up to 99.99% and *coverage* of 99.9%.
 - Support for device *connection density* of up to 10⁴ devices/km².
 - Digital Twins (DTs): Applications such as real-time DT of industrial processes or smart cities, will require:
 - *Reliability* of up to 99.99999%, *user-experienced data rates* of up to 100 Mbps and *coverage* of up to 99.99%.
 - *Location accuracy* of up to 10 cm and *E2E latency* on the order of a few ms.
 - Fully connected world: Use cases such as ubiquitous network will require:
 - *E2E latency* of up to 100 ms, *reliability* of up to 99.999% and *availability* of up to 98.5%
 - *User-experienced data rates* of up to 25 Mbps and *coverage* of up to 99.9%, including indoor coverage.
 - Trustworthy environments: Use cases such as human-centric services will require:
 - *E2E latency* of < 1 s, *reliability* of up to 99.999%
 - *Location accuracy* of up to 10m, *positioning accuracy* of up to 1 m and *relative positioning accuracy* of up to 0.1m.

2.2 Summary of design principles

The design principles for the 6G system were introduced in Hexa-X-II deliverable D2.1 [HEX223-D21] and have served as a guideline for the work in Hexa-X-II. Those principles aim at providing guidelines for the system blueprint design to address the functional and non-functional requirements, even if principles below are not described to target individually a specific requirement. During the work, a few additional aspects have been identified, and the design principles need to be clarified. The revised design principles are:

Principle 1 – Support and exposure of 6G services and capabilities: The 6G system should be able to provide comparable or superior user experience for all existing services, e.g., voice and Mobile Broadband while allowing gradual network deployment without disrupting legacy services. In addition, it should enable efficient incorporation of novel 6G digital services, such as sensing and computational offloading, and be able to expose new or existing capabilities to E2E applications.

Principle 2 – Full automation and optimization: The 6G system should be AI-native, i.e., integrate AI/ML agents and functionalities wherever beneficial to enhance performance and efficiency in network and service management automation, as well as to support new functionalities. This will include both observability as well as intent-based management. The system should also support continuous orchestration over multiple stakeholders and domains, in an E2E approach.

Principle 3 – Flexibility to different network scenarios: The 6G system should be flexible to address different types of scenarios and topologies, including local networks, wide area networks, non-terrestrial networks, public and private networks, and utilization of new spectrum in an efficient way.

Principle 4 – Network scalability: The 6G system should be scalable to different networks and deployments. For example, it should be able to support myriad deployments from small to large wide area networks (low-power with wide area coverage, fixed wireless access, energy neutral access or private networks).

Principle 5 – Resilience and availability: The architecture should allow network deployments with high resilience and availability tailored to the service needs/demands. This includes support of separation of Control Plane (CP) and User Plane (UP), resilient mobility solutions as well as subnetwork resilience.

Principle 6 – Persistent security and privacy: The 6G system should be able to address current as well as future threats in a resilient manner and incorporate security fundamentals in its design. Furthermore, the 6G system should inherently support the preservation of privacy and allow different levels of anonymity also for future services such as sensing, offloading, or AI as a service.

Principle 7 – Internal interfaces are cloud optimized: Network interfaces should be designed to be used in a cloud-native environment, utilizing state-of-the-art cloud technologies, design patterns, platforms and IT tools in a coherent and consistent manner, while at the same time considering the time requirements of the network tasks to be executed. Care should be taken to design proper service separation to maximize the potential for service reuse and allow for service innovation with minimal integration efforts (plug-and-play).

Principle 8 – Separation of concerns of network functions: The network functions should have bounded context (separation of concerns) with minimal dependency on other network functions. This allows network functions to be developed and replaced more independently from each other and also allows efficient scaling of network resources. The functionality of network functions should not be duplicated.

Principle 9 – Network simplification in comparison to previous generations: The network architecture should be streamlined to reduce the complexity of Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Network (CN) functions with fewer (well-motivated) parameters to configure and fewer external interfaces, to maximize innovation, and to reduce time to market. It will be important that the new 6G services do not introduce detrimental complexities for the legacy services.

Principle 10 – Minimizing environmental footprint and enabling sustainable networks: The design of 6G system should ensure that the environmental footprints can be justified, and any increased footprint should be clearly motivated with added value, cost efficiency, and societal benefits. The architecture design should make it possible to disable or deactivate functions that are not in use, either short-term or long-term, to ensure zero power at zero load. It should also facilitate circular practices through higher modularity of components to limit the replacement to only the degraded part or compatibility with software update to extend the lifetime.

While all ten design principles are crucial for the 6G system design, three stand out as top priorities:

- Principle 9: Network simplification in comparison to previous generations,
- Principle 10: Minimizing environmental footprint and enabling sustainable networks,
- Principle 6: Persistent security and privacy

It is important to note that the principle of simplification (principle 9) is central in achieving full automation and optimization (principle 2). Both principles go in synergy. Simplification aiming at a reduced complexity and improved efficiency, it inherently enhances the network ability toward achieving full automation. Full automation and optimization, leveraging AI/ML, can further reduce complexity and streamline the network operation.

2.3 Revision of enabler selection methodology

In this section we discuss the updates made to the enabler selection methodology, which aims to account for the rather subjective nature of the inputs.

2.3.1 Current state-of-the-art on the enabler selection process and outcomes

Firstly, the enabler selection methodology is briefly summarized based on the process followed in [HEX224-D23] for defining the most relevant components for the 6G system. Notably, a comprehensive methodology for designing the 6G E2E system has been demonstrated in [HEX2-KPJ+24]. The design process is defined as a two-way approach, consisting of i) a Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)- and KVIs-based design process and ii) a top-down versus bottom-up alignment process. Building on this broad framework and given the large number of enablers that are presented in Hexa-X-II and other SNS projects, and their corresponding dependencies and features, in [HEX224-D23] a mechanism that can consider these complex relationships was developed. This method aims to provide a suitable set of enablers for a given set of requirements. Furthermore, such an approach allows one to visualize and evaluate these multitudes of combinations, which can then be used to design/deploy the 6G system.

This approach, illustrated in Figure 2-1, is based on a knowledge graph (KG) to capture the dependencies between recommended enablers, enabler features, design principles and use case requirements. Concretely, the KG method ingests some meta data as inputs (e.g., use case, use case required (Req.) KPI/KVI, enablers, functionality provisioned, enabler provisioned (Prv.) KPI/KVI, enabler priority, network statistics that provide insights into enabler performance, etc.) and generates the KG. This is done by clearly determining:

- The nodes (enablers) and edges of the KG
- The node (enabler) features, which can include information about technical maturity, KPIs, KVIs, etc
- Edge features of the KG, wherein the edge features are weights accorded to the edge

For more details about the exact nature of the edge and node features used in the enabler selection, readers can refer to the initial work in [HEX224-D23] and results from the updated process in Section 6.2. Consequently, for the 6G E2E system design, an initial version of the graph which is a noisy knowledge graph was built. Note that a noisy KG is a KG that consists of all nodes and edges. Next, it considers the established constraints and objectives from the inputs as well as any other user defined constraints or objectives, and executes:

1. **Prioritization step:** This step prioritizes the enablers and their dependencies that are essential for the 6G E2E system design. Prioritization was obtained from inputs related to the recommendation meta data, see details in Section 7.2 in [HEX224-D23].
2. **Clustering:** Certain nodes might provide the same level of functionality, or they may achieve similar objectives. Hence, those nodes are clustered on the basis of functionality. For example, in the current 5G NR radio protocol stack both the MAC and RLC layer have retransmission mechanisms, which in essence provision same level of functionality. Thus, enablers provisioning similar functionalities can be grouped/clustered.
3. **Graph pruning:** This step involves eliminating the unessential nodes and edges from the KG to achieve the defined objective and adhering to the constraints. Specifically, this step involves using a

harmonization/combination function F and a quantitative threshold ψ to evaluate the essential nature of the nodes and their corresponding edges. The output of this stage is the set of selected enablers.

If new enablers become available, or the features of the existing enablers change, the method includes an optional step to reiterate to obtain a new or updated selection of enablers for the overall 6G E2E system design.

Note that the detailed level of enablers' impact on the functional and technical requirements discussed in Section 2 of [HEX224-D23] were not considered in this initial iteration of the analysis. With respect to the methodology described in Section 7.1 of [HEX224-D23], required and provisioned KPI and KVI and network statistics were not available. Consequently, the established selection did not provision any details on the compliance/impact of the 6G E2E system on the sustainability pillars as they require further evaluation with PoCs and simulations. With this background, the meta-data values for all the recommended enablers were collected. A detailed version of the meta-data collection is provided in [HEX2-JOK+24]. Subsequently, based on KG method as well as certain pragmatic considerations, enablers were selected, which have been listed in Table 7.1 in [HEX224-D23]. Detailed analysis and discussions for this selection can be found in [HEX224-D23] [HEX2-JOK+24].

Figure 2-1 Knowledge graph method-based enabler selection for 6G E2E system in [HEX224-D23].

2.3.2 Updated selection methodology

The main challenge towards an efficient pruning method is to be able to consider both the KPI and KVI requirements for the use cases and enablers. To this end, we update the enabler selection methodology to account for the heterogeneous nature of the enablers, their associated KPIs as well as the complexities associated with the use case key values (KVs) and key value indicators. Specifically:

- Step 1: The measured/analysed KPIs and KVI are collected from
 - The PoCs analysis [HEX224-D24]
 - Use case requirements and KPIs [HEX223-D12]
- Step 2: Collecting the relevant KVs and KVI (qualitative) from the use case analysis [HEX225-D14]

- Step 3: Collecting meta-data on the technological enablers (discussed in further detail in Section 6.2) consist of:
 - Maturity level (Technical Readiness Level)
 - Requirements for update to standards
 - Criticality towards migration from 5G to 6G
 - Requirements for new hardware entities
 - Dependencies on other enablers
 - Existence/presence of interfaces, protocols, etc., for communication/management/information exchange with the other dependent enablers
 - Design principles fulfilled
 - Qualitative impact of the enablers on the collected KPIs, i.e., positive, neutral or negative impact on the KPIs
- Step 4: Create the noisy/full KG by
 - Utilizing the collected enabler data
 - Use case KPI requirements
 - Other inferred network statistics, if network is already operational
- Step 5: Prune the noisy KG based on the impact on the KPIs, wherein the objective is to select all those enablers and their dependencies that maximize the positive impact on the KPIs
- Step 6: Evaluate the selected enablers for the E2E system based on the KVI determined for the specific use case, by
 - Deriving the requirements to satisfy/achieve the KVIs
 - Updating the E2E system if the KVI guidelines from WP1 are not met, via re-selection of enablers
 - Updating KVI requirements in case it is realized that the stated requirements are too stringent/loose
- Step 7: Repeat the above process for all use cases

Note that, only a qualitative analysis is performed with respect to the KPIs. This is because, to ensure a particular service level agreement (SLA), an enabler in the radio might have different requirements as compared to another enabler in the management and orchestration (M&O) domain, while both are necessary for ensuring the SLA. Hence, for a unified analysis and selection process, a qualitative assessment is performed, wherein the pruning process is finally executed via a simple maximum aggregate score function. With this background, we now illustrate the updated enabler selection process through Figure 2-2.

Figure 2-2 Updated Knowledge Graph based enabler selection method

As can be seen from Figure 2-2 and Figure 7.1 in [HEX224-D23], the updated enabler selection methodology (Figure 2-2), in comparison to the first iteration of the enabler selection methodology (Figure 7.1 in [HEX224-D23]) considers the KVI requirements after a KPI based enabler selection has been performed. This is because of the subjective nature of the KVs and KVIs, as well as the challenges related to analysing enablers from different domains with a specific KPI target. Concretely, since meta-data collected for each enabler and their impact on the KPIs is subjective, and the use case KV/KVI requirements are also subjective, the proposed sequential approach provides a less complex enabler selection process. It must be stated that, if the KV/KVI for the use case is not satisfied then it is checked if there is a requirement to update KPI and KVI targets for the use case. This can typically be avoided, if not enough combinations of the enablers have already been explored. In case many enabler combinations have been explored then a decision to update the KPI and KVI targets needs to be considered. Next, for the iteration of the graph pruning approach, the main objective is to determine another combination of enablers that satisfies the KPI and KVI requirements. This is different from the “New inputs” as the presence of a new enabler triggers the entire process again.

3 Radio interface and protocols

Innovations in the 6G radio interface and protocols are twofold. On the one hand, we leverage learnings from 5G deployments and implementations to propose enablers that take advantage of the once a decade opportunity of non-backwards compatibility offered by a new generation. On the other hand, the 6G needs to support new radio capabilities.

This chapter first describes enablers related to generic enhancements to 3GPP radio protocols in the areas of user plane, mobility procedures, and application network interactions in Section 3.1. Then, the integration of JCAS, Non-Terrestrial-Networks (NTN), and AI-ML in the radio protocols is discussed in Section 3.2. Finally, Section 3.3 concludes the radio interface and protocols innovations presented in this chapter.

3.1 Radio protocols

This section presents innovations for the design of 6G radio protocols. Three main research areas are discussed: radio user plane protocols, mobility procedures, and application-network interactions. The described enablers complement the previous work presented in the previous Hexa-X-II deliverable [HEX224-D23].

3.1.1 Radio user plane protocols

The following sections present user plane radio protocol enablers for 6G related to Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) enhancements based on new considerations in medium access control (MAC) retransmission and radio link control (RLC) operation, and device types' support considering a modular user plane design.

3.1.1.1 6G MAC retransmission technique

HARQ retransmissions may not always improve the decoding probability of the transport block (TB), e.g., in case of highly degraded channel conditions during the reception of the initial TB. Additionally, in 5G with incremental redundancy, after 4 retransmissions, the lowest coding rate possible for this transmission has been reached, and from the 5th retransmission onwards, only Signal Interference + Noise Ratio may be increased [38.212]. As a result, several problems are identified with HARQ retransmission in legacy cellular systems. The first is the unnecessary HARQ retransmissions, wasting resources and therefore increasing latency of other transmissions. Such unnecessary retransmissions can be anticipated for example from the channel condition observed by the user equipment (UE) during the initial transmissions. Secondly, packet loss in case of RLC unacknowledged mode (UM), due to failing HARQ combining, as RLC UM purely relies only on MAC layer for ensuring error-free reception of the RLC protocol data units (PDUs). Finally, packet latencies and jitter in case of RLC acknowledge mode (AM), due to failing HARQ combining, where RLC Status reporting and RLC ARQ retransmissions ensure the lossless transmission, but the latency and jitter per packet increases as a result. Figure 3-1 highlights the significance of failed HARQ combining on top of latency in RLC AM or packet loss in RLC UM.

Figure 3-1 New Radio (NR) Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) retransmissions and HARQ combining with Radio Link control (RLC).

As evident above, MAC shall determine the conditions for the specific cases, where HARQ retransmissions would not help the decoder, and reset the transmission of the TB instead of wasting resources. Therefore, the MAC layer can have a new function “*MAC segmentation for HARQ retransmissions*” to aid with such retransmissions. This function would be applicable in both downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) and is independent

of the MAC PDU's content (i.e., whether it includes full or partial RLC PDUs). Figure 3-2 (a) and (b) provide an example of how the MAC segmentation for HARQ retransmissions could look like. With MAC segmentation, the same time-frequency resources can be used in combination with a lower modulation and coding scheme to transmit the now fewer information bits of each MAC segment. In order to realize this, there shall be a way to ensure that the reception (Rx) side is aware of the ongoing segmentation happening in MAC. The need for Sequence Number (SN) and Segment Offset is however, not really needed as the segmentation would happen to a certain TB that is currently being transmitted and tied to a certain HARQ process. There are multiple ways to achieve this awareness at the Rx side (e.g., using Downlink Control Information (DCI) information). This would result in a more reliable transmission in comparison to current HARQ retransmissions scheme as it will involve segmentation but would require more slots to transmit all MAC segments. In comparison to legacy RLC, RLC re-segmentation can allocate each segment to a different HARQ process, however this comes at the cost of extra latency due to waiting for the RLC status report to be received. Additionally, with RLC segmentation there is no combining across RLC segments retransmissions, which would be possible with MAC segmentation. Note that the RLC reassembly timer (i.e., t-Reassembly in Figure 3-2 (a)) should cover all HARQ retransmissions of the original non-segmented MAC PDU. As an optional additional feature, if timer extension is needed, the "Dynamic RLC t-Reassembly" (i.e., highlighted in Figure 3-2 (a)) would cover the additional HARQ retransmissions of all segments of the segmented MAC PDU. Note that a potential drawback is the increased latency due to the segmentation of the original TB and retransmissions of such segments. However, such smaller segments would be sent with higher reliability, hence may require less retransmissions resulting in only a marginal increase in such latency.

Figure 3-2 MAC segmentation for HARQ retransmissions: (a) Example flow highlighting MAC segmentation and HARQ combining along with RLC timer, (b) Visualisation of MAC segmentation and soft bits generation.

3.1.1.2 Asymmetric radio link control

In [HEX224-D23], two main issues with HARQ in DL, namely the discontinuous transmission (DTX) interpreted as acknowledgment (ACK) (i.e., DTX-to-ACK) and negative acknowledgment (NACK) interpreted as ACK (i.e., NACK-to-ACK) by base station (BS) were identified. Both of those errors will cause the BS to stop the HARQ retransmissions, since the BS will believe that the UE has correctly received the transport block which will in turn increase the packet error rate. To combat this in legacy cellular systems (e.g., 5G), RLC AM [38.322] is used as a secondary retransmission mechanism on top of HARQ, where under bad radio conditions with high block error rate, the RLC AM uses retransmissions to recover lost packets. Those errors, however, do not exist in UL, as the BS that controls the HARQ procedure knows when a TB has been correctly or erroneously received, meaning that NACK-to-ACK or DTX-to-ACK conversion errors are not possible, and hence no need for the UE to implement RLC AM in the UL direction to take care of such errors. Therefore, a new scheme for RLC is proposed, where the UE would only require RLC UM functionality for both UL and DL with some RLC AM related functionality only for the DL path, namely Asymmetric RLC protocol (i.e., see Figure 3-3).

Figure 3-3 Asymmetric radio link control (RLC) protocol.

This new scheme for RLC would allow for a lower UE memory requirement, as well as a lower implementation complexity at both the UE and the BS, as there is no longer the need for RLC AM TX at the UE and hence, no need to store data in RLC, handling RLC status reports and performing retransmissions. Additionally, the UL shall rely on HARQ retransmissions only, where retransmissions happen much earlier compared to RLC AM ReTX, leading to reduced latency compared to legacy. For data which requires more reliability, more HARQ retransmissions shall be used, and hence after HARQ failure the packet error can propagate faster to the higher layers, leading to more responsiveness. Finally, with Asymmetric RLC, and potentially in combination with the MAC segmentation feature (i.e., see 3.1.1.1), the BS can dynamically choose whether to insist for a TB or parts of the TB to ensure it will be received (i.e., equivalent to RLC AM) versus giving up after some retransmissions (i.e., equivalent to RLC UM). It should be noted that Asymmetric RLC can also be applied in the UL direction, if seen needed.

3.1.1.3 Modular user plane design for different UE types

For 6G, as discussed in [HEX224-D23], modular user plane design can enable native support of various device types optimized for different purposes. The modular UP consists of the following two main components:

- Anchor module (referred as Anchor Protocol Stack in [HEX224-D23]): designed for low bitrate services with maximum coverage (e.g., bit-level optimizations) and high reliability (e.g., relying on RLC AM).
- Additional module (referred as Fast Protocol Stack in [HEX224-D23]): designed for high bitrate services, where the focus is on a processing-friendly and implementation-friendly design.

Different device types can then natively be supported with such a design, for example:

- For the lowest device type like Low Power Wide Area (LPWA) type devices [NOK24], only the anchor module can be used to support the necessary CP functions (e.g., Radio Resource Control, RRC) and UP functions (e.g., for small data transmission).
- For the mainstream device type such as broadband IoT devices or extended broadband devices, in addition to the anchor module, a few more modules can be included for supporting higher data rate.
- For high-end device types, even more additional modules can be included to further boost the supported maximum data rate.

In short, the proposed modular UP design can greatly simplify overall processing, support various UE types, allow for hardware-based parallelization of processes, all of which can help to reduce power consumption for high bit rate services without compromising low bit rate performance.

3.1.2 Mobility procedures

The following sections explore evolution of mobility procedures for 6G, complementing the work presented in [HEX224-D23] and [HEX23-D22]. Some of these sections provide more technical details to previous work while other sections introduce additional innovations for mobility in 6G, targeting different aspects ranging from mobility procedure operation and information to exchange, to mobility procedures enhancements.

3.1.2.1 Methods for cellular data transfer within connected measurements radio gaps

During cellular connected mode (e.g., RRC connected mode), the Cellular Network may assign radio gaps (e.g., measurement gaps in 4G/5G) to the UE during which the UE is able to switch radio frequency (RF) to other frequencies to search and measure neighbouring cells. Accordingly, during these gaps, the DL/UL data transfer between the UE and the cellular network is interrupted as shown in Figure 3-4 below.

The impact of this interruption is significant for use cases such as ultra-low latency, as the UE must wait until the measurement radio gaps are finished to resume data transfer. Additionally, for UEs with a single RF chain, the interruption is even more critical.

Figure 3-4 Illustration of data transfer interruption during measurement gaps

To overcome this problem, the cellular network may exchange data with the UE via one of the neighbour cells to be measured by the UE during a connected mode measurement radio gap. This neighbour cell via which data transfer can be exchanged with the UE during measurement radio gap is referred as Data Transfer Within Measurements Radio Gap (DTMRG) hosting cell. The high-level signalling of the concept is represented in Figure 3-5 below. The serving cell of the UE is aware of which neighbour cells are to be measured by the UE and find the DTMRG cell with good signal quality. Then, the serving cell forwards DL data of UE to the DTMRG hosting cell which sends it to the UE during measurement gaps. Note that, UE may still perform measurements of the DTMRG hosting cell using the remaining resources in the reference signals. Further details can be found in Annex A.2.

Figure 3-5 High-level signalling aspects of the data transfer within measurements radio gap (DTMRG)

3.1.2.1 Data driven mobility

The potential realization of the data-driven mobility is shown in [HX224-D23], where the UE and the network collaborate to enhance the connectivity control decisions during UE mobility by using not only the signal measurements as in legacy procedures but also leveraging information from the other sensors of the UE, utilizing the UE traffic pattern, and using the history of connectivity experiences of itself and other UEs. The usage of these additional information could be realized using contextual events e.g., radio/traffic events which was described briefly in [HX223-D22]. The following table provides information about potential user contextual events, their impact on user connectivity, mobility contextual event type, possible network mobility decisions, and 3GPP predictive event definitions.

Note that, UEs do not need to share any privacy sensitive data with the network (i.e., the first column of the following table “on-device understanding”). The network will only receive the event definitions (e.g., Z1, Z2 (third column)), when an event is satisfied. The definition of those events could be agreed with the network during capability exchange or connection establishment.

Table 3-1 Contextual mobility events

User contextual event (on-device understanding: from device sensors, user activity, application information, etc.)	Impact on user connectivity	Mobility contextual event type	Possible Network (NW) mobility decisions	3GPP predictive event definition (equivalent to A3, etc..)
Pedestrian user entering a thick building on a phone call in 3 seconds	User will continue its call inside the building	Radio environment event: high loss expected on this band (e.g., Frequency Range 2, FR2)	→Switch from FR2 to FR1 →Increase number of ReTx	Z1: Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) in Current band will drop for an extended period
User in a car entering a tunnel (passengers in the car are watching 4K video, downloading a large file, etc.), given the speed the tunnel will last 10 seconds	User will be on a phone call inside the tunnel	Radio environment event: high loss expected on this band	→ Change band →Increase Radio Link Failure (RLF timers) →Increase number of ReTx	Z2: RSRP in Current band will drop momentarily
User is going for a cross biking for at least 30 mins	User does not use the phone during this activity	Data traffic event: Low traffic expected	→Handover to offload the cell	Z3: traffic on this band from this user will decrease for an extended period
User will start its weekly hiking activity that lasts typically 2 hours	User does not use much traffic during hiking	Data traffic event: Low traffic expected from this user during this mobility time window	→Handover to offload the cell	Z4: traffic on this band from this user will decrease for an extended period

System level simulations are performed to compare the performance of contextual event Z2 described above with the legacy procedures. The UE is commuting every day from home to work by car and at some point, the car enters a tunnel and the channel degrades. Based on some historical crowd-sourced connectivity data over time, it is known that the serving cell of the UE before and after the tunnel is likely to be the same. In legacy procedures, the UE performs radio link monitoring, and due to the channel degradations inside the tunnel, it declares RLF and initiates reestablishment procedure. In reestablishment procedure the UE initiates cell selection [38.304] and starts to scan the available frequencies to find a suitable cell that satisfies the cell selection criteria. Once the cell is detected, the UE initiates random access procedure to the target next generation node B (gNB). After the uplink grant is received from the target gNB, the UE sends an RRC reestablishment request and completes the reestablishment procedure by following the steps described in [38.331]. The RRC reestablishment procedure is costly for the UE as it increases the service interruption time. In the given scenario above, the UE needs to perform the cell selection procedure, random access and RRC message exchange in order to connect to the network.

By using the contextual events, the interruption time after out-of-coverage (e.g., after UE leaves the tunnel) could be reduced by leveraging the historical data of the UEs. If a UE detects that it will enter a tunnel along its trajectory, and the serving cell does not change after it exits the tunnel, it can increase the T310 timer to avoid RLF and initiating the reestablishment procedure to reduce interruption time. So that, when UE exits the tunnel, it continues the normal operation with the serving cell. This can be achieved either by immediate

network interaction such that UE informs the network upon triggering a contextual event e.g., Z2 and the network sends a new configuration to extend T310 timer or indirect interaction with the network such that the network sends a configuration beforehand e.g., during RRC reconfiguration which is applied when a contextual event e.g., Z2 is satisfied to extend T310 timer.

The system level simulations showed that the interruption time after the tunnel can be avoided by leveraging historical UE data and trajectory prediction. Therefore, the average DL throughput is also much higher than the baseline approaches. The average DL throughput across different channel realizations is aggregated to compare the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the different procedures, as seen in Figure 3-6 below. Further details of simulation assumptions and results can be found in Annex A.2.3.

Figure 3-6 Comparison of Downlink (DL) cumulative distribution function (CDF) average throughput

3.1.2.2 Computation aware mobility

In [HX224-D23], it was stated that the legacy procedures in 5G rely on signal measurements to trigger serving cell change, which may not be sufficient for computation offloading use cases, if the target cell does not satisfy the computation requirements of the UE. The UE should evaluate its own computation requirements as well as the computation capabilities of the BS(s) before initiating mobility procedures.

In some cases, the source BS may continue to perform the computation task and send the output to the target, if the resulting latency is acceptable. In this case, the UE may indicate to the network that it wants to use source BS for computations, or it may be up to network to determine which cell to use for computation tasks. Further details of signalling aspects and deployment can be found in A.2.4.

3.1.2.3 Unprepared handover

In 5G baseline mobility procedures, the handover (HO) preparation and execution phases take time, require allocated resources, and involve multiple signalling exchanges. Especially, the time required for preparation phase can cause higher failure rate due to too late HO. To solve this issue, in 5G conditional handover (CHO) was introduced, achieving higher robustness due to earlier preparation and immediate execution by UE when HO condition is met for a candidate target cell. However, CHO requires allocated resources over longer time, due to earlier preparation, and potentially at more than one candidate target cell, hence, inefficient in terms of resource usage. Furthermore, since CHO is prepared earlier, the configuration may need to be updated before use as UE context may change between the time of HO request and the time HO execution happens.

To avoid the costly preparation in terms of time, signalling, and resources, 6G mobility procedure can skip the full preparation before HO command and configure the UE with cell common configuration while preparing the full configuration for a given UE in parallel, what can be called unprepared HO. In an unprepared HO, a (candidate) target node prepares a default (cell-specific) configuration for each of its cells and shares this default configuration and the associated criteria on when to use default configuration with its neighbouring nodes. When the source node has a UE which needs to be handed over to a new cell while satisfying the associated criteria corresponding to the default target configuration, HO command can be generated by source cell without the HO preparation phase using the available default configuration and transmitted to the UE. At

the same time the UE information is transmitted to the target to initiate preparation of the UE-specific configuration which will be delivered to the UE when it arrives.

This approach can provide the robustness level that CHO targeted, but since there is no need to wait for HO preparation before the source node can configure the UE with HO command, there is no need to allocate resources to any specific UE earlier than sending the HO command, and no/low risk that the early prepared configuration becomes invalid. A high-level example is shown in Figure 3-7.

Figure 3-7 Unprepared (conditional) handover.

3.1.2.4 Mobility configured and managed by lower layers

In 5G architecture, the RRC Layer controls the UE mobility and reconfigures RRC parameters at every change of cell. In 3GPP release 18, L1/L2 Triggered Mobility (LTM) was introduced, enabling support at MAC layer to trigger cell change while candidate cell configurations are provided from RRC layer.

LTM encompasses many benefits, one is the cell switch being more adaptive to lower layer measurement. Another benefit is the more frequent update of L1 measurement reports that enables prompt triggering of the potential cell change. However, since in LTM, RRC prepares the corresponding LTM configuration, MAC could reuse RRC sending the indication of mobility in addition to L1 measurement for cell switch, this creates a necessity of inter-working between RRC layer and MAC layer. Due to this interworking, the true benefit of lower layer mobility, which are mentioned above, is hindered by the slow processing of RRC layer. To overcome this issue, 6G mobility procedures can delegate more autonomy to lower layers (physical, PHY and MAC), enabling the MAC layer to control more over RRC layer operation for mobility management such as configuration and triggering for cell switch. With MAC, which is the resource scheduling entity, directly providing the lower layer configuration to UE and subsequently triggering the cell switch based on L1 measurement, achieving not only faster response, beam level-aware cell switch which are already offered by LTM, but also slim operation with minimum redundancy. A high-level diagram showing this MAC mobility management is illustrated in Figure 3-8.

Figure 3-8 Lower layer managed mobility concept.

3.1.2.5 Random Access Channel (RACH)-less baseline handover with early TA acquisition

Main motivation of RACH-less HO in 5G is to reduce the HO interruption time. The duration of the interruption time due to RAN procedure is ~60 ms, comprising 10 ms of Physical RACH (PRACH) occasion waiting time, followed by 10 ms of random access response waiting time, and considering the delay incurred by repetition of these procedures. For new applications like immersive experiences in 6G, the reduction of interruption time can be beneficial. In 5G, the LTM feature allows the UE to perform RACH-less handover to the target cell with new procedure called “early timing advance acquisition”, enabling the reduction in the interruption time. This involves sending the PRACH preamble to target cell while UE is still connected with serving cell and the timing advance (TA) of the target cell is provided by serving cell to the UE. Then, during the LTM execution the RACH procedure is completely skipped, and UE can send UL transmission (RRCReconfigurationComplete) directly to the target cell. However, this early TA acquisition procedure cannot be used in other handover procedures in 5G beyond LTM. Technically, early TA acquisition procedure could be used in other HO procedures as well to benefit from interruption time reduction. Therefore, 6G HO procedures could incorporate early TA part of the basic HO procedure. Figure 3-9 illustrates the high-level steps in 6G RACH-less baseline handover as compared to current RACH-based handover in 5G-A.

Figure 3-9 6G RACH-less handover as compared to 5G-A handover.

3.1.2.6 Related work on Terrestrial Networks (TN)/Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) handover

The investigation of TN/NTN handover mechanisms in [HEX224-D43] focuses on reducing handover signalling overhead and minimizing service interruption time. The proposed solutions are as follows:

- **Quality-of-Service (QoS) aware omission of HO common information:** This approach differentiates the handling of HO common information based on knowledge of the QoS or traffic patterns, addressing signalling overhead during the preparation phase. For sporadic data or delay-tolerant traffic, most or all HO common information in the HO message can be omitted. Similarly, if the UE can acquire the required parameters while in source cell, during source and target overlap time, this information may be omitted. For other cases, the HO common information could be included as in legacy.
- **Random time-based conditional HO:** This method reduces signalling during HO execution by modifying the time-based CHO procedure introduced in early 5G systems. According to this approach, when specific conditions are met, UEs can initiate HO within a defined overlapping period between source and target cells. However, in scenarios with a high density of UEs, this might lead to a surge of signalling messages. The random time-based CHO approach mitigates this issue by introducing randomness into the HO initiation time. Instead of all UEs trying to perform handover at once within the overlapping time window, each UE is assigned a random time within that period to perform its CHO.
- **Satellite switching with “physical cell indicator (PCI) change only”:** In this case, no HO procedure is involved. The cell configuration remains unchanged, and only the target cell identifier is updated via existing signalling mechanisms. This approach reduces HO-related interruption time, ensures backward compatibility, and resolves limitations of the “PCI unchanged” method in 3GPP Rel-18 [R2-2301269].

3.1.2.7 Mobility procedure harmonization

The unification of 6G mobility procedures builds upon enablers described in [HEX223-D21] and [HEX223-D22] about multiple level DL control and flat RRC structure. In 5G, multi-level DL control by RRC/MAC/DCI are utilized in various mobility procedures. For instance, the transmission configuration indication (TCI)-state configuration for beam management is done by RRC, the TCI-state activation is done by MAC, and the beam indication is done by DCI. For LTM, the candidate pre-configuration is done by RRC, while the pre-synchronization and LTM cell switch is done by MAC. for CHO, the candidate pre-configuration and event

triggered execution are both done by RRC. Overall, this is very complex and there is a need to unify these control commands.

In 6G, the principle is that persistent reconfiguration (e.g., mobility commands and configuration of mobility procedure) should be handled by RRC, since RRC provides a reliable delivery (e.g., feedback on RLC level). In addition, a RAN architecture without higher layer split allows UE control in a single network point and there is no impact on procedure time whether the command is from RRC or MAC. In this regard, special purpose RRC messages with limited content can help reduce interruption time, with tailored stricter processing time requirements depending on what is changed. This type of RRC message sometimes can be just a legacy MAC CE put into RRC format, but delivered similarly as other RRC messages, e.g., transmitted in a logical channel and subject to ciphering and integrity protection. The unified mobility procedure consists of three steps: pre-configuration, pre-synchronization, and execution, however, the legacy L3 HO procedure will also be supported as fall-back, in case any issues arise. Further details can be found in Annex A.2.1.

3.1.2.8 *Lean system mobility*

As discussed in [HEX224-D23], in 6G, multiple separate Synchronization Signal Blocks (SSBs) can be defined to decouple between IDLE and CONNECTED modes, and ultimately can have different properties in either time, spatial or frequency domain. In this section, we provide more details on how they can be used, and some follow up technical discussions.

A subset of nodes/carriers will provide coverage with always-on signals (i.e., I-SSB (idle mode-SSB) or E-SSB (extended periodicity SSB)) along with system information. Additionally, there will be nodes/carriers used for data transmission only that do not need to provide idle mode coverage. These nodes can be dynamically activated when needed to boost data rates and/or capacity. Those nodes do not transmit SSB always but only on-demand, e.g., M-SSB or D-SSB (dynamic or dedicated SSB). The ultimate purpose is to turn on nodes only when needed and so to reduce energy footprint.

The need to power on additional nodes can be due to two reasons:

1. There is a demanding UE, e.g., streaming extended reality (XR). In this case, the network simply activates the capacity node with an indication to the UE about its M-SSB/D-SSB.
2. The capacity boosting node is turned on during a high system load. This requires that UEs connected previously to the non-capacity node handed over to the capacity node.
 - a. In the case of other connected-mode UEs moving into this area, the UEs can be provided with candidate cell configuration including these capacity nodes and so that these nodes can be found, and signal qualities can be measured.
 - b. One complicated scenario is whether an RRC_IDLE mode UE can camp on the capacity node so that the UE can perform initial access on that capacity node and receive paging information from that node. Note that for UEs to camp on a SSB, that SSB must include system information. The ambition level should be that very few UEs in IDLE mode camp on the capacity node, but rather most UEs are in INACTIVE/CONNECTED mode. It may be sufficient to let RRC_IDLE UEs camp on the coverage node and to handover to the capacity node if needed. In case of a consistent system high load, a smart network implementation instead can start to broadcast I-SSB or E-SSB so that IDLE mode UEs can camp on those.
 - c. An even more complicated scenario is whether an RRC_INACTIVE mode UE can camp on the capacity node, and the transition from the RRC_INACTIVE state to the RRC_ACTIVE state when the UE was last served by the capacity node. Here, various options can be envisioned. One option is that the UE can resume on the coverage node and indicate good quality M-SSBs (which is not associated with any broadcasted system information) from the capacity node by associating it with a specific preamble or random access occasion. When doing so, the UE assumes the reference signals containing system information (i.e., I-SSB, E-SSB) are present and the system information has not been changed (e.g., contained in I-SSB/E-SSB for random access, paging), unless a validity timer configured to the UE has expired as can be seen in Figure 3-10.

Figure 3-10 Signalling diagram for resuming directly using Mobile Synchronization Signal Block (M-SSB)

3.1.3 Application-network interactions

The following sections introduce new application-network interactions for 6G service differentiation and QoS, complementing the work presented in [HEX224-D23] and [HEX23-D22]. These innovations leverage UE intelligence and application awareness for the base station to optimize service provisioning in 6G.

3.1.3.1 Ad-Hoc radio bearer and inline signalling

Figure 3-11 Example MAC CEs for inline signalling: (a) Data Radio Bearer (DRB) setup/reconfiguration /release, (b) DRB small delta (re-) configurations.

In [HX224-D23], a new mechanism, via inline MAC control element (CE) signalling, that would allow for the setup, reconfiguration, and release of radio bearers in a more dynamic fashion based on application or service requirements was introduced. The idea is to start with only the best effort bearer (i.e., as long as this serves the purpose of all current services). If buffers get filled due to heavy background traffic, or requirements change, adapt the settings of the best effort bearer or open up a new data radio bearer (DRB) quickly (i.e., via inline signalling) to overcome this situation (for more details please refer to section A.1.1). One way to realize the ad-hoc bearer setup/release/reconfiguration via inline signalling, is reusing the current MAC CEs in 5G. For example, the reserved IDs of 35-44 of logical channel identifiers (LCID) of the uplink shared channel in [38.321] can be utilized. Figure 3-11 gives two examples of possible MAC CEs that can be used to realize this, where Figure 3-11 (a) shows an example with a context ID of a preconfigured DRB setting to be used for a DRB setup, reconfiguration or release. Figure 3-11 (b) is an example that allow for a delta (re-) configuration, where bitmap “C0 ... C6” may be used for indicating (re-)configuration of certain parameters (e.g., “C0” used

for Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) reordering timer, which if set to 1 indicates that the octet to which it is mapped gives the timer value in milliseconds, etc.).

Figure 3-12 (a) and (b) show a Message Sequence Chart (MSC) and MAC CE, respectively, highlighting a DRB setup example. In this example the UE indicates a “MAC CE for setup” indicating new LCID = 3 with a preloaded Context ID A. For DRB delta configuration and DRB release MSCs, please refer to section A.1.1.

Figure 3-12 DRB setup example: (a) message sequence chart, (b) MAC CE.

Another way to realize the ad-hoc bearer setup/release/reconfiguration via inline signalling, is using the Service Data Application Protocol (SDAP) layer and header. This would require the split of the SDAP functionality moving the labelling and SDAP header part below RLC, while QoS flow mapping remains as in 5G [38.323]. This means that the SDAP header is created after RLC PDU creation allowing for the addition of a Context ID within the SDAP header, so that a required ad-hoc bearer setup/reconfiguration/release can be indicated towards the Rx side. On the Rx side, the SDAP header can be decoded and ad-hoc bearers could be established/reconfigured/released before the QoS flow is handed over to RLC (i.e., for more details please refer to Section A.1.1).

Moreover, since the UE is more application-aware than the NW and in order to enable more UE control on the QoS in the RAN an UL reflective QoS by mirroring the DL reflective QoS scheme of 5G [38.323] could be introduced. The UE could signal “inline” in UL, similar to in DL, how the QoS Flow Identifier (QFI) shall be mapped to DRBs in DL based on the applied mapping in UL (i.e., reflective QoS flow to DRB mapping indication (RDI)), and also how the DL packets shall be mapped to QFIs based on the characteristics of UL packet that actually carries this information (i.e., reflective QoS indication, RQI)). Figure 3-13 shows an example realization of SDAP header to allow for UL reflective QoS along with DRB (re-)configuration.

Figure 3-13 Proposed UL Service Data Application Protocol (SDAP) Data PDU with UL Reflective QoS.

3.1.3.2 UE quality level-aware scheduling

The current 3GPP QoS framework [37.324] offers either guaranteed bitrate (GBR) or non-guaranteed bitrate (non-GBR) bearers. The GBR bearers are inflexible and impacts the NW's resources, where the NW has to reserve bandwidth and is responsible for admission control and the users have to pay for such bearer. Additionally, such bearers are non-adaptive and slow signalling to setup and modify and are not really in use except for the NW owned voice over internet protocol. The non-GBR bearers on the other hand offer no guarantees and are best effort bearers and are usually configured by the NW as a single default bearer that carries all data. Hence, in the current QoS framework there is no quick method for UE and NW to align and rapidly adjust the provided NW UL grants and the UE's target bitrate. Inability to offer such quick alignment to avoid the filling of the UL buffers on the UE side may lead to buffer bloat and resource waste (e.g., outdated packets to be sent). Figure 3-14 shows an example of the effect of the slow adaptation of UE's bitrate to a drop in UL grants from NW.

Figure 3-14 Effect of the slow adaptation of UE's bitrate to a drop in UL grants from NW.

In order to overcome the shortcomings of the current QoS framework above, a new procedure is proposed that is formed of two stages: Stage#1 - UE indicated quality-levels and Stage#2 - level-aware scheduling. In Stage#1 - UE indicated quality-levels, the UE agrees with the NW on multiple different quality levels that can then be used as a reference for Stage#2 - level-aware scheduling. In Stage#2 - level-aware scheduling, the UE is informed on a regular basis about the quality level the NW is able to serve to this UE currently and/or in the future steering the UE to known and sustainable levels. For more details on an example on a set of quality levels that are agreed between the UE and the NW, please refer to A.1.2. Figure 3-15 gives an example MSC for a possible realization of Stage#1 - UE indicated quality-levels, where the UE agrees with the NW on different quality level profiles it would like to support, and the NW may optionally propose some modifications to the shared profiles. Note that such signalling may be done via MAC CEs, and this can be an extension to the periodic cadence report MAC CE proposed in [HX224-D23].

Figure 3-15 Possible realization of stage#1 - UE indicated quality levels.

Since the NW is responsible for capacity planning and scheduling, it informs and steers the UE to a sustainable quality level (e.g., downgrade to a lower bitrate under loaded conditions). In legacy operation, the NW could only limit the grants for every UE in an indistinctive manner or let some UEs starve and there was no control from the NW to steer UEs to lower but sustainable levels, where a running application might still work and at the same time avoid buffer bloat and resource waste. UEs offering multiple quality options allows for more flexibility in scheduling by the NW and, additionally, can enable more fairness in the scheduling, where UEs offering opportunities for meaningful downgrades in loaded situations could be rewarded by faster quality ramp up under good quality conditions. It would also enable a better planning and more efficiency on RAN level, leading to a better service for all UEs in the cell. Finally, it applies to both GBR and non-GBR bearers. The non-GBR bearers are best effort, but UE indicated quality levels can help the NW achieving better and more predictable service at the UE side without any guarantees. While for the GBR bearer, the GBR bitrate could for example be defined as Q_{low} and Q_{high} could be defined to allowing for upscaling beyond the GBR bitrate, or GBR bitrate could be set to Q_{med} to allow for a controlled degradation instead of losing the GBR bearer via Release by the NW.

Figure 3-16 Example for quick UE bitrate adaptation based on exchanged quality levels and level-aware scheduling.

For more details on Stage#2 – Level-aware scheduling an example MSC for a possible realization, please refer to A.1.2. Figure 3-16 shows how the new two stage QoS framework the bitrate adaptation on UE side and therefore an enhanced user experience.

3.2 Integration of new radio capabilities

The integration of new radio capabilities into the 6G E2E system requires full support from the 6G radio interface and protocols. This section provides an analysis of the impact of JCAS, NTN and AI-ML on the radio interface and protocols.

3.2.1 JCAS radio protocols

3.2.1.1 Overall sensing procedure

New network elements, functions, and procedures to support JCAS have been discussed in previous Hexa-X-II deliverables ([HEX223-D32], [HEX223-D33]). Notably, [HEX224-D34] outlines high-level sensing procedures and APIs, detailing how applications can request sensing operations, how UEs participate in sensing processes, and how identity and authorisation for sensing data are managed [HEX224-D34]. Furthermore, protocols and components for JCAS security and privacy are detailed in Section 5.3. This section details protocol to support fundamental JCAS operations in mobile networks. As shown in Figure 3-17 and discussed in [HEX223-D33], the Sensing Management Function (SeMF) is introduced to coordinate sensing procedures. It includes the Sensing Control Unit (SCU), which configures network elements for sensing tasks, and the Sensing Processing Unit (SPU), which processes the sensing data. To contextualise the requirements of the sensing protocol, the following presents a multistatic sensing procedure. Although described with reference to multistatic sensing, the methodology also applies to monostatic and bistatic sensing.

Figure 3-17 Example multistatic sensing procedure

The key steps in the protocol procedure include:

1. Transmission/Reception Points (TRP) configuration and capability transfer: The SCU exchanges information with TRPs to assess their suitability for the sensing task, requiring protocols for secure capability negotiation.
2. Configuration of transmitting devices: The SCU configures the selected transmitting BS/TRPs with the necessary parameters via control messages.
3. Activation of broadcast transmission: Transmitters begin broadcasting specific reference signals required for sensing, requiring synchronization protocols.

4. Measurement requests: The SCU sends measurement requests to receive devices, needing protocols to coordinate measurement instructions.
5. Measurement execution: UEs and BS/TRPs perform measurements by receiving and processing the reference signals, this calls for protocols to coordinate timing and execution.
6. Measurement reporting to SPU: Receivers report the measurement data back to the SPU, requiring standardized data reporting formats.
7. Sensing procedure deactivation: The SCU instructs transmitters to cease broadcasts, which needs protocols to manage the termination of sensing tasks.

These steps describe the coordination required in JCAS operations and underscore the need for dedicated protocols. Given the parallels between sensing and positioning procedures, existing 3GPP standards for NR Positioning Protocol A and LTE Positioning Protocol (LPP) provide a reference protocol design for JCAS protocols. These protocols define procedures for capability transfer, device configuration, synchronisation, measurement execution, and reporting in ways compatible with JCAS. This introduces the possibility of unifying the protocol for sensing and positioning, thereby simplifying system design.

While NR Positioning Protocol A and LPP provide a substantial foundation for a sensing protocol, extensions are necessary. New procedures must be defined to accommodate monostatic, bistatic, and multistatic sensing scenarios. The protocol will need to introduce additional reference signals and processing techniques to support measurements such as Channel State Information (CSI), in-phase and quadrature samples, range, and Doppler. Furthermore, new collection and reporting mechanisms will be required to ensure measurement acquisition from multiple TRPs and the amalgamation of data through standardised data fusion processes in the SPU. Finally, protocol extensions related to security and privacy, as discussed in section 5.3, will be required to ensure legal and ethical JCAS operations.

By extending existing protocols, we minimise the need for extensive new standardisation work. This approach accelerates deployment, reduces costs, and utilises the existing ecosystem of devices and infrastructure, thereby lowering barriers to entry for JCAS in mobile networks.

3.2.1.2 Radio bearer for sensing measurements in Uu

UE transmitting measurements to the base station has been a crucial component on radio protocol, and in 5G, there are different types of measurements delivered in a different manner. UE transmits mobility-related measurements, e.g., in the RRC message *MeasurementReport*, carried over by signalling radio bearer 1 (SRB1). UE transmits positioning related measurements in the RRC message *ULInformationTransfer* carrier over by SRB2 in which SRB2 is specifically designed to transfer non-access stratum (NAS) messages. The detailed format definition of the measurements is in the LPP protocol and forwarded by the gNB to the core network. Each one of these SRBs is mapped to a logical channel in the lower layer radio protocols, in which by default SRB1 has a higher priority than SRB2, while both have a higher priority than DRBs.

Regarding sensing related measurements on radio protocol, it is unclear which one to choose (SRB1, SRB2 or DRBs) or even a new radio bearer may be needed. As background information, the essential difference between SRB and DRB is what is possible to configure, the related operations on the RAN-CN interface, and some default configuration for SRBs. Here is a list of examples:

- SRB is designed to carry radio configuration, and this is associated with one specific base station or cell. Thus, after PDCP entity re-establishment, the UE shall discard all stored PDCP Service Data Units (SDUs) and PDCP PDUs for SRB; it is only SRB that can be configured with *discardOnPDCP* so that the UE can also discard stored PDCP PDU/SDUs upon receiving a RRC reconfiguration that does not trigger PDCP entity re-establishment but changes resource configurations.
- For SRBs, the amount of data transmitted is small and it is of high importance to deliver reliably. Consequently, there are some default configurations, e.g., the SN can only be 12 bits, the 32-bit MAC-I field (Message Authentication Code for Integrity) is always present in PDCP PDU, RLC AM mode is used, etc.

- Default configurations in SRB1 and SRB2 are motivated to save RRC message size so that it works in a bad coverage, and during RRC re-establishment/resume, it is possible to get to a known state.
- DRB is designed to carry user data. It is only for acknowledged mode (AM) DRB one can configure recover PDCP so that the data is retransmitted in the target cell after handover. Additionally, it must have a *SDAP-Config* configuration to link to a PDU session.
- The base station can access the content of an SRB part of the data and further deliver relevant information to the core network using Next Generation Application Protocol/Stream Control Transmission Protocol.

The design for sensing is complicated by that the use case and their requirements are not settled yet, and optimizations can be envisioned on both RAN-CN and RAN-UE interfaces depending on the requirements. In this section, we discuss in detail how the radio protocol needs to be changed to support one such example. In this example, the UE measurements are not processed at the UE but forwarded to the network. These measurements can be raw sensing data and the size can be potentially very large.

- A new radio bearer is needed. If these sensing measurements would be multiplexed with SRB1/SRB2, it would stall other control signalling related messages. This means that there is a need for a different logical channel for sensing measurements other than those associated with SRB1 or SRB2. This logical channel could even have a lower priority than the logical channel of a specific DRB which may be used to carry high priority data like voice call.
- A new radio bearer type other than DRB might be needed. DRB is meant for high-layer application data and so it is forwarded to User Plane Function (UPF) by a PDU session. Therefore, if there is a need to forward to a network entity other than UPF, then some changes on DRB handling are needed. One approach is to have a dedicated sensing flow that is routed to another Network Function (NF) that is not UPF. The sensing measurement can be mapped to an existing DRB together potentially with other user plane data of a QoS flow. In this case, there is a need to modify the SDAP protocol and the configuration therein [HEX224-D23]. Additionally, it is further complicated by that the base station might process the measurement data. The format of these measurements needs to be defined, and the base station might need to further deliver the processed data to the core network. The possibility that gNB access and process the content is not supported for DRB.
- A new radio bearer type other than SRB might be needed. For SRB, a smaller number of bits for SN, and additional MAC-I field are not essential for these types of measurements. Additionally, since UE is sensing surrounding environments, the sensing measurement is not related to the UE itself but in general applicable across cells, e.g., in the case of UE mono-static sensing, and the case when sensing reference signals are common within an area. It is, thus, useful to have *recoverPDCP* for this radio bearer (i.e., the UE can retransmit the unacknowledged data after the handover) and not to mandatorily discard upon handover. Note that discard upon handover was the default action for SRB.

As one can see, this set of requirements may lead to a rather large change on the radio protocols, together with impacts on RAN-CN interface which is not concluded yet. It is not clear yet if another set of requirements may lead to a different design. For example, if UEs are always fixed in one location as dedicated UEs to assist in sensing, then a new SRB with configurable logical channel priority might be sufficient. Overall, in 6G, it is not preferred to have many options in radio interface/protocols. The discussion on this part must be postponed until the most relevant baseline use case (in terms of business opportunity, implementation challenges) and requirements are clear, and the fundamental capabilities and limitations of the PHY layer are clear. One conclusion one may draw is that the radio protocol framework is already flexible enough to support potential needs with modifications.

3.2.2 Non-Terrestrial Networks

NTN deployments and the integration of NTN with TN is expected to improve service coverage of existing cellular deployments towards full global coverage. To minimize the cost of increase of deployments and equipment, reusing existing TN spectrum for NTN deployments is beneficial. Such tight integration of TN and NTN may lead to deployments where the satellites reuse TN spectrum outside TN coverage areas to improve

overall 6G coverage. Hence, coexistence between TN and NTN will be a key aspect both from spectrum and coverage perspectives. Although NTN would serve users outside TN coverage, NTN transmissions could still interfere TN mobiles.

As it is shown in the section 9.4 of [HEX225-D45], depending on the network parameters, one co-existence case may outperform the other. Urban regions see less performance degradation when TN downlink shares the same band with NTN downlink. The impact of Low-Earth Orbit (LEO) satellite altitude is also more significant in rural regions. In other scenarios, such as a reverse duplex scheme, i.e., NTN uplink reuses TN downlink band, the performance varies significantly depending on the user's location relative to the base station. Specifically, performance degradation increases for cell-edge users. Interference from NTN may not always be harmful to TN, but separation distance and power limits must be defined to protect TN cell-edge users, especially for rural areas. It is also possible, of course, to mitigate interference within the UE, for instance by handshaking between TN and NTN modules, optimized antenna patterns, circuit techniques, or digital signal processing [HEX225-D45].

Next to satellite-based NTN, other NTN types can be considered, like high-altitude platforms (HAPS). HAPS-mounted gateways provide reduced path loss and greater predictability compared to satellites. In [HEX225-D45], a HAPS-mounted Long Range (LoRa) gateway at an altitude of 30 km is compared against a satellite-mounted gateway at 780 km altitude resulting in longer distances but more favourable elevation angles. Depending on UE location and used LoRa spreading factors there can be a significant performance gain with HAPS-mounted links.

A critical aspect for TN and NTN integration is the HO of users between cells. In many NTN scenarios, frequent HO even of a stationary UE can happen. To avoid related overheads, NTN-NTN HO can be predicted to some extent and new designs can be considered compared to legacy TN. A description of the approaches proposed in [HEX225-D45] can be found in section 3.1.2.7.

3.2.3 AI-ML for radio interface optimisations

The *AI-driven air interface* is a radio air interface for communication and/or sensing, where AI-based methods replace one or more functionalities in the lower layers across the transmitter and/or receiver [HEX2-FBB+24]. The innovative solutions that leverage AI to refine air interface design, marking a shift towards smarter, more efficient networks can be outlined in the following groups:

- *Learning for waveform, modulation, and coding*: Utilizing AI to enhance modulation and coding techniques, including the optimization of waveforms (for communication and/or sensing) [HEX2-KHH23], and error correction strategies.
- *AI-Based CSI acquisition*: Advancing CSI acquisition including channel estimation, CSI feedback and CSI prediction through AI, optimizing network spectral efficiency while reducing overhead for CSI feedback.
- *AI-Enhanced MIMO transmissions*: Enhancing MIMO transmissions through advanced antenna management, power control and user pairing strategies based on AI/ML.
- *AI solutions for hardware impairments*: Leveraging on AI's potential to address hardware challenges, specifically by compensating for power amplifier non-linearities, e.g., using AI-based receiver of compensating PA nonlinearity [FHS23].

The integration of AI-driven air interfaces into radio access networks requires new radio procedures, protocols, and signalling mechanisms to enable effective and efficient operation. Several potential areas for standard support are needed to accommodate the AI/ML-based functionalities across different layers, especially in the PHY layer. The following points highlight the need for such mechanisms:

- *AI/ML Model life cycle management*: One of the essential aspects for enabling AI-driven air interfaces is the lifecycle management of AI/ML models, particularly for PHY use cases. This includes processes like data collection, and model monitoring. Standards need to support procedures for triggering these processes to ensure that the AI/ML models can be updated when and where needed and retrained to adapt to evolving communication environments.

- Revision of signals and waveforms: AI/ML-based capabilities within the network can drive the need to revise traditional signals and waveforms. For instance, new learned Low-Density Parity-Check (LDPC) codes or non-Quadrature Amplitude Modulation learned constellations may emerge as more optimal alternatives [HEX2-KHH23]. Protocols and signalling would be required to accommodate these new waveforms and ensure their seamless integration into existing radio environments.
- Signalling and protocols for PHY layer integration: The physical layer would need specific signalling and protocol revisions to support the integration of AI/ML-based functionalities. This may involve new signalling methods to initiate data collection processes that AI/ML-based receivers rely on. Additionally, signalling may need to be adjusted to support the AI/ML based functionalities in the network, for example, power headroom reduction in UE may need to be revised based on the AI/ML-driven Digital Post Distortion (DPoD) capabilities at the gNB [FHS23].
- Reduction of reference signals: Another area requiring revision is the reference signalling for AI-driven air interfaces. With AI/ML technologies like DeepRx, the need for traditional reference signals like Demodulation Reference Signal (DMRS) may be reduced, resulting in more efficient utilization of spectral resources [HEX2-KHH23]. Standards will need to outline how such reductions can be implemented while maintaining system integrity and performance.
- Revision of requirements based on AI/ML capabilities: With AI/ML integrated into the network, certain physical layer requirements might need adjustments. For example, in-band distortion requirements could be relaxed based on the AI/ML DPoD capabilities [FHS23]. This could lead to more flexible and efficient operation, but it would necessitate new protocols and signalling to ensure compatibility and performance consistency.
- Testing of AI/ML-based methods: To comply with regulatory requirements, it is essential to establish protocols for testing AI/ML-based methods. The dynamic nature of an AI-driven air interface means that testing procedures must be designed to ensure that these systems adhere to regulatory standards. This would involve creating test frameworks for real-time adaptability and the proper functioning of AI/ML algorithms within the air interface.
- Trustworthiness: A crucial aspect of integrating AI-driven air interfaces is addressing the trustworthiness of the underlying AI/ML models. This includes ensuring robustness against attacks, protecting data privacy, and providing transparency and explainability in AI/ML-driven decisions. Further details on trustworthiness of AI are provided in section 5.4.

The transition to an AI-driven air interface requires updates to radio procedures, protocols, and signalling. These updates ensure the seamless operation, adaptability, and compliance of AI/ML-based functionalities within modern communication systems. The impact is mostly due to solutions where an exchange of information between device and network is needed. The content, format, and size of the exchanged information depends on where the AI/ML models are trained, applied and monitored, as well as on the level of collaboration between device and network. For instance, the models can be applied for inference at the device side or at the network side, depending on the use-case and the entity consuming the results. Furthermore, e.g., for private federated learning, models are locally trained on the device side and model weights are aggregated at the network, so they need to be transmitted over the air, resulting in a rather large volume of exchanged model parameters. In the example case, where the device collects data for training and applies the inference model, limited information exchanged with the network is sufficient for AI/ML purposes, i.e., mainly signalling for configuring the device with correct radio resources and related reports. In other examples, where the network performs the training, a larger amount of radio measurements may be needed from the device.

The next question to address is what radio resources are required for such information exchanges. Depending on the specifics of the aspects discussed above, the resources used can either be regular user plane resources, or control/configuration resources. This is also captured in the system proposed in the privacy preserving data collection and training framework [HEX224-D33], which enables the network to collect data and share data/models to perform learning or optimization tasks.

3.3 Conclusion on radio interface and protocols

This chapter has delved into innovations in 6G radio protocols, focusing on three areas: radio user plane protocols, mobility procedures, and application-network interactions. User plane enablers have proposed solutions to improve HARQ retransmissions in 6G by extending the functionality at MAC and/or RLC layers, or the modularization of the user plane functionality for different device types. Mobility procedures have explored a wide range of potential innovations for 6G, including extensions to existing 5G procedures, new mechanisms to minimize interruption time, new scheme to harmonize mobility procedures, and new information for evaluating mobility events, among others. Application-network interactions enablers have explored innovations for the UE and the base station to optimize service provisioning in 6G. These innovations complement and extend the 6G radio research presented in previous reports [HEX223-D22] and [HEX224-D23], aiming to improve one or multiple of the radio design principles outlined in [HEX223-D22], such as a flexible protocol stack for different scenarios that maximizes the use of single protocol components for different scenarios and fast, reliable protocol operation, taking the lessons learned from 5G.

The chapter has also discussed the integration of other 6G capabilities that will influence the radio protocols design and operation. This analysis is crucial for ensuring E2E support of new 6G capabilities like JCAS and the evolution of existing 5G capabilities like NTN and AI-ML for 6G. The analysis identifies various needs, such as extending current procedures for new cases foreseen, updating reference signals and radio bearers, and adding additional capabilities to be exchanged between the UE and the network, among others.

The content of this chapter provides the final pieces for the 6G radio interface and protocol design, considering issues identified in 5G, new opportunities foreseen for 6G, and the integration of various capabilities in the radio. Most of the innovations presented in this chapter and previous reports extend existing 5G radio protocols and operations to minimize standardization work and utilize the existing ecosystem of devices and infrastructure, positioning 6G radio design as an evolution of 5G. Key take aways of the innovations in this area have highlighted three key aspects: i) the need for further simplifying the radio protocols for the control and the user planes, ii) enable tighter coordination between protocol layers and how their operation impact control procedures for UE configuration, QoS management, or mobility management, and iii) allow more adaptiveness in the radio interface operation for service provisioning. Still, future work is needed to achieve all the radio design principles identified in [HEX223-D22] (i.e., focus on fundamental requirements, flexible protocol stack, simplicity compared to previous generations, practical optimization for the use case's needs, fast and reliable protocol operation, separation of protocol layer concerns per layer, design compatible with spectrum sharing) together in consideration with the 6G KVis.

4 Intent-based E2E service management automation framework

As described in [HEX223-D22], the evolution towards 6G networks requires enhanced collaboration among administrative domains to ensure seamless E2E service consistency. Traditionally inter-domain collaboration relied on wholesale agreements among major operators, which, while effective for earlier network generations, lacks the flexibility that is expected in the next generation of networks.

The shift from the traditional “Telco” model to a Technology Company (TechCo)” ecosystem, as envisioned for 6G, redefines roles and expands service capabilities. In this new landscape, the list of value network roles is the following: Network Operators (NOPs) manage network and cloud resources, while Communication Service Providers (CSPs) build and deliver services to different customer segments. Tier-1 operators often assume both roles, with NOPs focusing on control and network management, and CSPs handling commercial operations. However, as the industry evolves, the scope broadens to include digital services beyond conventional communication, offered through APIs by Digital Service Providers (DSPs). This shift motivates the breakdown of the NOP role into specialized Capability Operators (COPs) and resource providers to cater to the diversified needs of modern service offerings resulting on the framework illustrated in Figure 4 1.

Figure 4-1 E2E Digital Service management automation framework.

As presented in [HEX223-D22] and illustrated in Figure 4-1, a high-level architecture for automating E2E intent-based service management outlines interactions among key actors: tenants (i.e., Digital Service Consumers (DSCs)), DSPs, COPs, and resource providers. Three tenant types—aggregators, verticals, and application service providers (ASPs)—interact with DSPs to initiate and manage service intents. The DSP, equipped with an intent-based Digital Service Manager (DSM), processes these requests and translates them into specific requirements for COPs, who manage domain-specific resources using enablers such as the Integration Fabric (IF). Resource providers span various domains, offering network, AI, and cloud resources. This multi-layered architecture supports DSP federation, enabling cross-domain cooperation for comprehensive service delivery, facilitated through the Intent-DSC API.

Based on the presented aspects, this chapter outlines how telecommunication actors are anticipated to evolve to support 6G multi-stakeholder scenarios, detailing their roles and their involvement in managing intent-based services.

4.1 Intent-based service framework

This section aims to explore the potential actions of the actor responsible for managing intent-based services, referred to as the DSP, based on the type of tenants (i.e., users) requesting intents and the interactions with other DSPs in separate administrative domains. To this end, this section aims to present two models for orchestrating intent-based services across multiple domains. In addition, and to complement the two multi-stakeholder management models, this section presents an evaluation of the current standards to identify what was missing in the Intent-based DSM version presented in D2.3 [HEX224-D23]. Based on this work, the final DSM component utilized by the DSP and its primary functions and evolutions are properly introduced.

4.1.1 Intent-based DSP service management (single and multi-domain)

Due to the various types of tenants in a multi-stakeholder scenario, two models for intent-based service provisioning were identified: a) the aggregation model, where one tenant takes full responsibility for issuing the necessary intents and maintains direct communication with the intent-based DSMs of involved administrative domains, and b) the federation model, where this responsibility shifts to the intent-based DSM of a single administrative domain that has received the tenant's request. In the federation model, this DSM then communicates with other DSMs in different administrative domains to request the required intents.

To fully grasp the workflows of these two models (illustrated in Figure 4-2 and Figure 4-3), it is essential to note that in both diagrams, interactions between the intent-based DSM and other components within its single administrative domain (e.g., service orchestrators, resource managers, etc.) are summarized using a red annotation. This approach helps clarify the figures and emphasizes the differences between the two models. For a clearer comparison, both workflow descriptions are based on the same use case in which a vertical service (e.g., video streaming, gaming session, etc.) needs to be provided to a group of users located in a certain domain (e.g., domain B). The figures distinguish between the roles of the DSC (where the tenants are) and the Single Administrative Domains (SAD) (where the intent-based DSMs reside) that supply resources to the DSCs.

4.1.1.1 Aggregation

As shown in Figure 4-2, the aggregation model starts (step 1) when a tenant-2 type (e.g., a vertical business) submits a request to a tenant-1 type (i.e., aggregator) for the service it plans to deliver to its clients (e.g., vertical clients or end users).

From that point, the aggregator becomes responsible for requesting the appropriate intents from the most suitable SAD. In the described example, the request specifies "users in domain B", so the aggregator may initially approach domain B to check for the required services (e.g., vertical service connectivity). However, since the aggregator lacks knowledge of service availability, it first queries all known SADs by requesting intents to understand each SAD's available capabilities (steps 2 – 4). Using the responses from the SADs, the aggregator will identify and choose the best domain capabilities for meeting the expectations outlined in the original intent from vertical (step 5). In the example we are describing, the aggregator would identify that domain B does not have the vertical service and this is located in another domain (e.g., domain A). This selection process is based on factors such as: a) service availability in each SAD, b) capability to meet KPIs/KVIs, and c) other resource-related details (e.g., load distribution) shared by the SADs.

Once the aggregator has determined the specific intents to request from each SAD (e.g., a vertical service from SAD A and connectivity service linking SAD A to SAD B), it initiates these requests to the corresponding intent-based DSM of each SAD (steps 6 and 13). While each intent is managed independently by its respective DSM, their performance may be interconnected; thus, the aggregator must understand the sequence for requesting each intent. In the example in Figure 4-2, the vertical service is requested first from SAD A (step 6). The DSM in SAD A receives and processes the request (step 7) to: a) identify and validate the expectations within the intent against KPIs/KVIs defined in the SLAs between SAD A and the aggregator, and b) create and store the intent data object.

Once the request is processed and validated, the aggregator receives a notification (step 8), and the DSM proceeds with intent provisioning. To fully provision the intent, the DSM maps the expectations into executable services (step 9). It then evaluates the feasibility of these expectations by assessing local resources (step 10). If feasible, the intent is deployed locally (highlighted in red, as noted in [HEX2-AMO+24]). After each

expectation is met without conflicts (or once conflicts are resolved), the intent data object is updated (step 11), and the aggregator receives an intent report (step 12).

At this stage, the first intent is complete, allowing the aggregator to proceed with subsequent intent requests based on the SAD selections made in step 5. The process for the second intent, now involving SAD B, follows the same steps: starting with steps 13 and 14 when the DSM in SAD B receives the request, identifies and validates the expectations within the intent against KPIs/KVIs defined in the SLAs between SAD B and the aggregator, and concluding at step 19 with a report on the status of the fulfilled expectations and any conflicts. Finally, after all identified intents are successfully deployed and configured, the aggregator can inform the vertical that the requests have been fulfilled, and the vertical service is ready for use by its end users.

Figure 4-2 Multi-DSP aggregation intent-based service provisioning workflow.

4.1.1.2 Federation model

The federation model is designed to eliminate the need for an aggregator, shifting the responsibility of identifying and selecting the appropriate SADs to the intent-based DSM in the SAD that receives the initial request from the tenant. This primary distinction is illustrated in the workflow shown in Figure 4-3. In this model, tenants submit their complete intent requests directly to the intent-based DSM to secure the vertical service for their end users, bypassing the need for an aggregator. The intent-based DSM that receives the initial request then takes charge of coordinating with other intent-based DSMs as needed to facilitate the deployment of resources for the tenant's request.

Figure 4-3 Multi-DSP federation intent-based service provisioning workflow

With these points in mind, the federated service provisioning process begins when a vertical submits an intent request with E2E service requirements (step 1) to the intent-based DSM serving as the main point of contact. The DSM proceeds by processing the request, identifying and validating the expectations, and creating and storing the intent data object (step 2). After notifying the tenant of the request's acceptance (step 3), the intent-based DSM continues with the provisioning process by mapping the intent to executable services (step 4) and evaluating the feasibility of these expectations using local resources (step 5). At this stage, the main difference from the aggregation model becomes evident: the “east-west” interaction between the intent-based DSMs of different domains. If the local resources can fulfil the expectations, the intent-based DSM manages the deployment as per the procedure detailed in [HEX2-AMO+24]. However, if local resources (i.e., services or capabilities) are insufficient, the intent-based DSM reaches out to other known SADs to request their available capabilities and services (steps 6 and 7). Based on the responses, the DSM selects the most suitable domains to fulfil the unmet expectations (step 8). The selection is based on service and resource availability, as well as the required and offered KPIs/KVIs. Once the domain for each “non-local” expectation is determined, an intent-based provisioning process (steps 9 – 14) is initiated between DSMs, following the steps outlined in Figure 4-3 (e.g., steps 6 to 12, 13 to 19). Finally, after all non-local expectations have been successfully provisioned through “federated” intents, the original intent-based DSM updates the “E2E” intent data object

(Step 15) and notifies the vertical. The tenant then follows internal procedures to deliver the access information for the deployed vertical service to its end users.

4.1.1.3 Single domain workflow updates

Figure 4-4 Updated Digital Service Manager Intent Management Entity (DSM-IME) internal workflow with negotiation functionality.

Since its first version presented in D2.3 [HEX224-D23], the DSM-Intent Management Entity (IME) has evolved with the work presented previously related to the multi-stakeholder scenario. Due to its closeness, this section advances the updated workflow about how the updated DSM-IME internal functionalities collaborate among them to deploy an intent within the domain resources. Further details about the how the missing functionalities for the multi-stakeholder scenario were identified and the updated DSM-IME architecture are presented later in sections 4.1.2 and 4.1.3, respectively.

Regarding the updated workflow that illustrates how an intent is deployed and processed by the proposed internal functionalities of the DSM-IME, it is presented in Figure 4-4. As most of the workflow keeps the same interactions as it was presented in D2.3 [HEX224-D23]- section 5.1.1, the novelties in the workflow are marked in blue colour. In there, once an intent request is received and the services are identified (steps 1 – 2), the intent interface functionality will verify the identified KPIs/KVIs based on the tenant that has generated the intent requests (steps 3 – 5) and, in case it has requested one of the possible negotiation options (later described in sections 4.1.2 and 4.1.3), the “intent negotiation” functionality takes care to apply the necessary actions (steps 6 – 8) to return back the intent-based negotiation outcomes to the tenant, so they both (i.e., DSM-IME and tenant) can agree with the final intent-based request (steps 9-10) that will be deployed and provisioned using the rest of the workflow (steps 11 – 30), as it was described in D2.3 [HEX224-D23].

4.1.2 Intent-based interfaces for E2E DSP service management

Figure 4-5 describes each functionality of the vertical intent interface between the stakeholder acting as intent owner and the DSP acting as intent handler. It is composed of six functions: “Intent interpreter”, “intent handling capability exposure”, “intent negotiation management”, “intent Create, Read, Update, Delete operations” (CRUD), “intent Activate, Deactivate, Suspend, Resume” (ADSR), and “intent report management”.

Figure 4-5 Northbound intent interface functions list.

This vertical intent interface supports the provisioning and continuous assurance of services required by the DSP. However, in certain situations, a single DSP might be unable to fulfil the request of a tenant (either for single tenant or aggregators). Moreover, since the vertical interfaces support managing the intents within a single DSP, they could also be used for horizontal interfaces to support managing intents between multiple DSPs. Thus, there is a need to evaluate whether the vertical interfaces, identified in D2.3 [HEX224-D23], interfaces support all functionalities for multiple DSPs. For this aim, a divide-and-conquer methodology is done to determine whether the vertical interfaces support handling the intents with multiple DSPs.

In the first step we describe the functionalities covered by the existing North-Interfaces, as shown in Figure 4-5. The “intent interpreter” creates an intent object from a request while the “intent handling capability exposure” must assist the user on showing the services offered by the enabler towards the user. The “intent negotiation management” is responsible for the communication between the intent owner and handler regarding feasibility and preference/action to make. The “intent interface” also provides the CRUD functionality (i.e., “intent CRUD”) providing the set of public actions to manage intents. The “intent ADSR” provides the ADSR functionality and manages actions that allow intents to remain active in standby mode until they are needed again. Lastly, the “intent report management” offers the actions related to the expected reporting of intents.

The next step is to analyse each block compared to different functionalities from standardization forums such as TM Forum [TMFIG24], 3GPP [28.312] and ETSI Zero-Touch Management (ZSM) [ZSM011]. These include setting intents, reporting intents, negotiating intents, and handling the capability profiles.

Lastly, we try to map the standard interfaces functionalities to the ones we already identified in Figure 4-5 to check whether they match the functionality of one of the existing APIs. The result of applying this methodology is shown in Figure 4-6. It shows the missing functionalities when negotiating the intent. These include judging (proposing alternative potential actions to fulfil an intent’s expectation), probing (asserting if an intent can have all expectations fulfilled), and best proposal (finding the best values for intent’s expectations).

Intent Functionalities	Supported			Unsupported	
	3GPP	ETSI ZSM	TM Forum	ETSI ZSM	TM Forum
Setting intents	Create intent	Create	SET intent		
	Modify intent	Update			
	Query intent	Read	GET intent		
	Delete intent	Delete	Remove intent		
	Activate intent	Activate			
	Deactivate intent	Deactivate			
	Translate intent				
				Suspend	
			Resume		
Reporting on the intent		Notify/Report	Report intent		
Negotiating intent				Judge	Judge/preference
				Feasibility	Probe
				Best	Best/propose
Handling intent profile		Capability exposure	Capability profiling		

Figure 4-6 Functionality map analysis for supported and unsupported blocks coming from vertical interface. Missing blocks include negotiation of the intent and activation/deactivation which appear only in ETSI ZSM and TM Forum.

The evaluation of the previous DSM design highlighted that the North-Bound Interface (NBI) in [HEX224-D23] lacks support for a federation of DSPs. This limitation arises from missing functionalities that are necessary for negotiation between tenants and DSPs (i.e., DSMs), particularly in enabling east-west interactions, through a horizontal interface, among DSPs. Furthermore, in the comparison of the three standards, as depicted in Figure 4-6, it is recognized that two functionalities from the “setting the intent” block (i.e., suspend/resume) and the entire “negotiating an intent” block are absent. These two blocks are present in ETSI ZSM [ZSM011] and TM Forum [TMFIG24] but, at the time of writing, missing in 3GPP specifications. Moreover, to support the federation of DSPs, these missing blocks need to be considered in the interface. To resolve this, the “intent ADSR” and the “intent negotiation” functional blocks are introduced, enabling the DSM to engage in federated, east-west interactions with other DSPs’ DSMs. For example, the “intent ADSR” functionality would allow the DSP to suspend intents while negotiation takes place through the probe function, during intent negotiation between two DSPs to prevent conflicts. In this respect, the negotiation block can be applied in several ways for handling multiple-DSPs, as described in section 4.1.1, for the aggregation and federation models. If there are only a pair of DSPs, negotiation will suffice; however, if more than a pair, then intent decomposition and negotiation are required. This happens as the intent will be split in several DSPs.

Finally, as an example of a possible technological solution to achieve the north-south API interface between tenants and DSP and the east-west API interface between DSP, CAMARA API [CAMARA] seems to accomplish the needs and could become a good option.

4.1.3 Final intent-based DSM functional architecture

This section outlines the functional architecture of the DSM based on the needs to achieve the multi-stakeholder scenarios and the interfaces presented in the previous section. It then introduces a collection of enablers, each tailored to fulfil specific functionalities within the described architecture, before providing an evaluation on how it aligns with interfaces established by various standard organizations.

The DSM-IME, an advanced functional architecture illustrated in Figure 4-7, is organized into seven distinct functional blocks. It interfaces with both the service Management Domains (MDs) and the resource MDs via an IF.

Figure 4-7 DSM-IME functional architecture.

The presented functional architecture has evolved since its first version in [HEX2-AMO+24][HEX224-D24]. The novelties compared to this previous version are described during each functional block description. Internally, the DSM-IME has the following modules:

- Intent interface:** This functional block serves as the primary access point for users to engage with the entire intent management solution and is a central component of the architecture. It manages intent data objects and supports various actions for intent lifecycle management. Its capabilities include: an “intent interpreter”, which processes user requests and enables DSM-IME to understand the user’s intentions; “intent handling capability exposure”, which displays what the system can offer and manage through intents; “intent CRUD” for initiating operations to manage intents; “intent report management”, which provides reporting methods related to the intent reporting functional block; and the “intent ADSR”, a feature that keeps intents in standby mode until they are needed, an enhancement from the previous design in [HEX2-AMO+24]. This functionality has been integrated after the thorough review of current standards and requirements discussed in the previous section 4.1.2.
- Intent fulfilment internals:** This functional block comprises capabilities that remain inaccessible to users but are essential for supporting user-facing functions. Key features within this module include “intent translation”, which converts intents and their expected KPIs and KVIs into actionable service management tasks and policies as outlined in an SLA. The “intent feasibility check” ensures that an incoming intent request can be executed properly. The “intent Closed Loop (CL) governance and coordination service” serves two main functions: a) to manage the lifecycle of the instances of “intent-driven CL control for fulfilment evaluation” for each request to ensure proper deployment and meeting requirements, and b) to coordinated coexistence of multiple CLs [ZSM009] within DSM-IME. Lastly, the “intent conflict detection/resolution” capability identifies potential negative impacts of new intents or actions on existing ones and resolves conflicts when they arise.
- Intent reporting:** This functional block is responsible for managing various types of information related to intents. The “intent feasibility check information” indicates whether an intent can be deployed, considering current resource availability. The “intent fulfilment information” collects data on the status of intent fulfilment and the achieved target values. Lastly, the “intent conflict information” manages details about conflicts and their resolutions.
- Intent negotiation:** This functional block represents a significant evolution from the previous work in [HEX2-AMO+24]. It enables DSM-IME users to access detailed information about intents before they are provisioned. The core functionalities include: a) probing an intent to determine if all its expectations can be met, providing tenants with insight into whether their requirements can be fulfilled; b) allowing tenants to request the intent with the strictest manageable requirements, closely linked to feasibility checks; and c) simulating potential outcomes for alternative actions (i.e., preferences) as a basis for decision-making to assess different strategies and solutions before

execution. This final function relies on predictive capabilities to estimate the impact of actions on the system state.

- **Intent SLA:** This functional block marks a significant enhancement compared to [HEX2-AMO+24], featuring third-party (3P) profiling and the service portfolio for managing SLAs related to intents. The 3P profiling provides a comprehensive characterization of a tenant (i.e., a 3P) through a profile that includes tenant-specific data on security (such as supported credentials and access control mechanisms), and user profiling based on contracted services and SLAs. The service portfolio, on the other hand, presents abstracted information about available 6G services and their associated SLAs (essentially a product catalogue). This allows tenants to make more informed and tailored intent requests. The service information includes details such as service status (e.g., defined, designed, built, tested, released), ownership, variations in service offerings (e.g., different SLA options), costs, and dependencies on other services.
- **Intent-driven CL control for fulfilment evaluation:** This functional block provides the capabilities needed to manage the lifecycle of intent CL instances and ensure they always meet fulfilment requirements. Once an intent CL instance is established, it includes the following capabilities: a) the “intent CL governance service,” which orchestrates and controls actions related to its specific intent instance; b) the “intent CL execution,” responsible for carrying out tasks as directed by the governance service; c) the “intent CL analytics (KPI & KVI),” which processes monitored metrics and extracts insights; d) the “intent CL decision,” which utilizes these insights to make optimal decisions about the intent CL instance status; e) the “intent CL monitoring,” which gathers data and metrics on predefined KPIs for analysis by the analytics capability; and f) the “intent CL data services,” which stores data specific to each intent CL instance.
- **Data services:** This functional block is in charge of storing the intent data objects and other possible information such as SLAs and policies.

In summary, as previously mentioned, these functional blocks collaborate with both the service MDs and resource MDs to achieve E2E IBM for services requested by various tenants. The communication between the DSM-IME and the service MDs, as well as the resource MDs, is facilitated by a cross-domain IF. This interface supports the exchange of information between different solutions through a unified protocol.

4.2 Intent-based specific enablers for the E2E service management

This section brings together all the previously discussed elements, including the architectural aspects of the multi-stakeholder model, the functional components of the intent-based DSM, related enablers, and security measures to protect intents. The goal is to demonstrate how these elements can be effectively combined for the proper management and orchestration (M&O) of intent-based end-to-end services. To illustrate this, four use cases are presented, focusing on intent-driven fulfilment management, intent-driven service evaluation management, coordination of intent-driven CLs, and trust management in intent-based scenarios.

4.2.1 E2E intent-based service fulfilment management

Telecommunications operators have faced various complex scenarios over time. Initially, they managed diverse access and transport technologies. Later, they integrated resources from third-parties and navigated different wholesale models. Most recently, they have embraced new capabilities and digital suppliers, creating a complex ecosystem to deliver products built on the services developed by DSPs.

This complexity impacts the end customer, who often lacks a clear understanding of what is being offered and how it meets their specific needs. The intent-based service fulfilment management model addresses this by enabling the creation of personalized services tailored to each customer. It interprets customer requirements in a more natural language and dynamically assembles services. Through effective monitoring, it can activate automated policies to ensure satisfaction levels for the end user are consistently met.

Figure 4-8 Intent based management stages.

The intent-based fulfilment process (Figure 4-8) involves the following stages between the customer and the Digital Service Provider:

- **Discovery:** the DSP identifies and translates customer (e.g., verticals or end-customers) needs, possibly expressed as high-level service intents by a human, into IBM-IME manipulable intents, reflecting their targets and expectations.
- **Feasibility:** the DSP verifies that the request can be fulfilled using available resources and capabilities, evaluating the service definitions and possible discrepancies in the resources required to achieve the desired outcomes.
- **Design-deployment:** The DSP utilizes a dynamic design and deployment process to configure and activate the necessary capabilities across the end-to-end domain
- **Monitoring:** The DSP implements detailed monitoring of the service components and associated policies, ensuring services operate in line with the agreed service levels and trust expectations.
- **Management:** Completing these tasks requires management systems that store information about each intent, its lifecycle, and associated actions. Additionally, a set of interfaces is needed to serve as a communication channel between the customer and the DSP, conveying customer needs and providing related reports.

The different stages involved in the E2E IBM process have several functional components, performing the diverse actions included in the process as summarized in the following table.

Table 4-1 Stages and components involved in an E2E IBM process

Stage	Module	Functionality
Discovery	Intent NLP	Extracts the customer requirements translating them into understandable objects by the IBM-IME with the use of Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques. Included in the Human Machine intent interface enabler described in [HEX224-D24].
	Intent interpreter	Transforms the requirements in target/expectations for E2E domain. The expectations could generate complex relationships when composite expectations are considered. Included in the Intent Translation & Provisioning enabler ([HEX224-D24]) and in the DSM IME as Intent Interpreter at Intent Interface module.
	Intent validation handling	Ensures the DSP has the capabilities to meet the specified expectations, identifying intra-intent conflicts and communicating any associated issues to the customer. Included in the Intent Translation & Provisioning enabler ([HEX224-D24]) and in the DSM-IME as Intent Handling Capability Exposure at Intent Interface module.

Feasibility	Intent matching	Aligns expectations, targets, and context with the DSP's service portfolio and profiles. This process may involve integrating components from federated stakeholders. Included in the Intent Translation & Provisioning and the third-party Facing services enablers ([HEX224-D24]) and in the DSM IME as the Intent SLA module.
	Intent feasibility check	Evaluates the feasibility of the intent considering the expectations, previous services, constraints and context. Managed sub domains are evaluated, often requiring orchestration. Included in the Intent Translation & Provisioning and the Intent reporting enablers ([HEX224-D24]) and in the DSM-IME as Intent Feasibility check at the Intent Fulfilment module and Intent Feasibility Check Information at the Intent Reporting module.
Design & deployment	Intent translation	Establishes the design of the E2E service needed for fulfil the expectations with service actions in the domains managed by DSP. Some actions will need to be coordinated/orchestrated among managed subdomains. Included in the Intent Translation & Provisioning enabler in the [HEX224-D24] and in the DSM-IME as Intent translation at Intent Fulfilment module.
	Intent fulfilment	Implements the deployment actions in the MDs based on the design proposed in the intent translation module, using established integration channels. Included in the Intent Translation & Provisioning and the Intent reporting enablers ([HEX224-D24]) and in the DSM-IME as Intent CL execution at CL Control at fulfilment evaluation module and Intent Fulfilment information at the Intent Reporting module.
	Intent negotiation	When multiple options exist to achieve the desired target, the negotiation component determines the best choice among available alternatives Included in the Intent Translation & Provisioning enabler ([HEX224-D24]) in the DSM- IME at Intent negotiation module.
Monitoring	Intent Close Loop	Intent assurance activities: conduct assurance activities as part of a closed-loop process to address conflicts and deviations, further detailed in the E2E intent-based closed-loop coordination section. Included in the Intent Translation & Provisioning and Intent reporting enablers ([HEX224-D24]) and in the DSM-IME at CL Control and fulfilment evaluation module.
Management	Intent CRUD	Interface exposed by DSP. Provides an interface for managing the lifecycle of intents, including expectations and targets. Included in the Intent Translation & Provisioning and the Intent reporting enablers ([HEX224-D24]) and in the DSM-IME as Intent CRUD at Intent interface module.
	Intent report	Generates and notifies reports: Creates and shares reports on fulfilment, feasibility checks, and conflict resolution activities. Included in the Intent reporting enabler ([HEX224-D24]) and in the DSM IME at Intent Reporting module.
	Intent Database	Stores intent management data: maintains a structured data model and repository for storing information related to intent management. Included in the Intent Translation & Provisioning and the Intent reporting enablers ([HEX224-D24]) and in the DSM IME at Data services module.

Involved enablers (from T2.3 and WP3/WP6)

Some of the functionalities detailed in the previous section has been developed completely or partially in the Hexa-X-II project. Figure 4-9 depicts the relationship among the (WP2, WP6) enablers and the functionality covered / related.

Figure 4-9 Relationship among E2E IBM service fulfilment components and Hexa-X-II enablers

E2E Service Workflow

Following section 4.1.3, a complete intent-based management E2E process starts when the customer (typically a tenant) has a new expectation related with a digital service environment. That expectation is a specific and personalized desire that a DSP could tackle with its own capabilities or external ones (if it has management access) creating a service to fulfil the expectations. Following are the steps considered in this E2E process:

1. The customer typically expresses in its language. An *intent NLP* module processes this input, extracting valuable information to model the customer’s expectation and target. The *intent interpreter* component then identifies the target (e.g., a network or service) and associated expectations, while also determining the responsible E2E domain to handle the request in multi-domain scenarios.
2. The structured output from the Intent Interpreter is formatted according to 3GPP-defined intent structures. This output forms a request that can be managed through the *intent CRUD* interface, allowing the DSP to store it in the *intent database* for future reference.
3. The *intent validation/handling* component evaluates the request's validity from the DSP's perspective, identifying and addressing potential intra-intent conflicts.
4. The DSP takes all the information needed to establish the context for this specific intent. The *intent matching* component considers running services, definitions of the services that compose the e2e service, and resource or capability availability within the service portfolio and 3P profiling components of the IME.
5. The *intent translation* component initiates the dynamic design of the entire service. The E2E process orchestrate the actions with the collaboration of the different domains needed for fulfil the service, defining the relationship between the involved domains, the execution order, the dependencies, and the definition of the configuration in each domain. It also establishes the E2E SLA and Trust Level Agreement (TLA) to support subsequent CL automation. This process may involve multi-technology and multi-provider environments, including external administrative domains, leveraging a network and capabilities continuum.
6. Before deployment, the *intent feasibility check* ensures the service requirements are achievable. The results are communicated to the customer via a detailed report, and if the service is not feasible, alternative proposals may be suggested.
7. When multiple ways to support the E2E service are identified, the *intent negotiation* component proposes alternatives for select one of them using a judgment (customer decision in the process), a set of preferences (at least, the best, others) and probably some kind of probing will be necessary for a final decision

8. Once all prior steps are complete, the *intent fulfilment* component activates the new service. It orchestrates the process across all domains in the E2E ecosystem and initiates monitoring activities. These are managed by *intent CL* elements, which observe service KPIs and execute corrective actions to maintain customer-defined targets.
9. The *intent report* component provides the customer with information about the fulfilment process and key metrics observed during E2E operations. Reports may be delivered once or periodically, depending on the agreement between the customer and the DSP

4.2.2 E2E intent-based service evaluation management

Considering the deployment of services based on the defined intent, continuous monitoring and evaluation of the intent fulfilment is required. Such an evaluation must be continuous and be offered in real-time. To achieve so, the high-level intents must be translated to specific Service Level Objectives (SLOs) that can be continuously monitored. However, monitoring and assessment of the intent satisfaction is challenging, considering the distributed nature of the deployed networks services and applications and the activation of multiple orchestration components over the available infrastructure that spans across the computing continuum. Under this perspective, it can be claimed that is of paramount importance to efficiently translate user needs into actionable objectives and continuously optimize service configurations. With the availability of a representation of user intents, the system can identify relevant metrics that are key for meeting the specified SLOs. In case of failure to fulfil the defined intent or if anomalies are detected in the service's normal operation, the system should conduct a root cause analysis to pinpoint the issues and suggest/take appropriate mitigation actions.

The E2E intent-driven service evaluation management aims to fill these gaps by combining the identification of intent-related metrics, real-time data fusion of heterogeneous observability signals and orchestration enablers to guarantee the fulfilment evaluation and lifecycle management of services in the computing continuum. These features enable the system to adapt dynamically to changing network conditions and demands. For instance, if the service-level configuration needs adjustment, an orchestration agent can automatically identify the configurations that are needed and implement the necessary changes if possible. Similarly, if infrastructure-level configuration adjustments are required, the corresponding orchestration agents take the appropriate actions to ensure seamless service delivery and performance.

Involved enablers (from T2.3 and WP3/WP6)

The service operates through a series of enablers that facilitate different aspects of intent-driven orchestration. These are described below:

- Data fusion mechanisms based on telemetry data: Data fusion and analysis mechanisms enable the identification of hidden relations in the data, enhancing orchestration performance.
- Intent-driven placement: Intent translation into performance efficient placement directives.
- Monitoring and telemetry framework: Responsible for collecting and providing access to observability data.
- Multi-agent systems for multi-cluster orchestration: Orchestration intelligence mechanisms that allow multistakeholder environments to efficiently deploy and manage services in alignment with SLOs, ensuring SLA guarantees.

These enablers work in tandem to provide a robust framework for managing complex network environments and ensuring the fulfilment of user intents. The interactions of these enablers can be seen in Figure 4-10.

An observability data fusion mechanism focuses on translating low-level information into fulfilment evaluation values and monitoring service normal operation and continuity. Collaboration among multiple agents is envisaged to support orchestration decisions and actions, considering both local (e.g., within a specific cluster) and global objectives (e.g., for the overall reserved infrastructure across the computing continuum). Indicative actions may regard autoscaling and migration of part of the provided service, ensuring efficient resource utilization and service performance. Intent-driven placement tackles the issue of translating intent into performance efficient placement directives, while intent translation can make the connection between a high-level service description and low-level fulfilment evaluation.

Figure 4-10 E2E service evaluation and management enabler interaction.

E2E Service Workflow

The workflow description of the E2E service is given in Figure 4-11.

Figure 4-11 E2E service evaluation and management workflow

The E2E service workflow begins with the *intent owner* providing their intent to the *intent translation* component, which activates both *SLO fulfilment monitoring* (to ensure compliance with SLAs) and *anomaly detection* (to identify unusual events or deviations). Based on monitoring, *intent-driven placement* identifies optimal service placement, while any detected SLO violations or anomalies trigger *Root Cause Analysis (RCA)* to diagnose performance issues or failure causes. The *RCA* interacts with *orchestration mechanisms* to apply corrective actions or adjust configurations, feeding into the *infrastructure* where these changes are implemented. The infrastructure provides real-time metrics to the *observability data fusion access*, which feeds back into the orchestration mechanisms to enable continuous optimization and adaptation. This system ensures an intent-driven, closed-loop process for automated service placement, monitoring, issue resolution, and infrastructure management.

4.2.3 E2E intent-based closed loop coordination

E2E service workflow

Figure 4-12 shows the CLs within the DSM framework where each level implements automation mechanisms to guarantee the automatic fulfilment of service requirements.

Figure 4-12 Closed Loops within the digital service management framework.

At the level of the DSP, the CL are basically business-level loops, aiming at guaranteeing the constraints negotiated in the SLAs. In the COP, the CL are service-oriented with the main focus on technical constraints such as QoS parameters for services deployed across different capability providers. At the lower level, in the capability providers, the automation mechanisms mainly consider the status of the resources, e.g., network, computing, etc. With reference to the figure, it can be noted that a single service request at DSP can generate multiple CLs in all parts of the hierarchy, which allows their coexistence at the same time, in the same domain, and in all the levels: multiple services belonging to different tenants generate dozens of coexisting CLs which may enforce conflictual configurations. CL governance and coordination are two CL management functions defined to guarantee automatic tuning of the systems while minimizing the risk of system instability [ZSM009]. The CL governance offers specific interfaces to allow third-parties (i.e., entities not belonging to the loop such as CL coordination or orchestrators) to interact with the loop for e.g., configuration, status retrieval, start and stop, etc. The coordination function incorporates an internal logic dedicated to the management of multiple CLs, which includes functionalities to avoid/mitigate conflicts and mechanisms to enable collaboration between loops. The loop is created at orchestration time and, once its provisioning is completed, the CL governance notifies the CL coordination function that the CL is up and running, specifying its characteristics, such as configuration, goals, etc. DSP and COP implement their own CL coordination functions so that each provider coordinates its own internal loops, business and service respectively. Nevertheless, given the relationship between the two entities, as represented in Figure 4-12, additional considerations are required.

The IF in the architecture represents the communication system between the actors at the different levels, which allows to create flatness in the hierarchy of the providers. In particular, the DSP and the COP belongs to the same administrative domain (e.g., a network operator covering both roles) and access to the same information related to the resource providers, including monitoring data: this implies that both DSP and COP CLs, insisting on the same set of resources, may reacts to the same events generating system instability. This creates a challenging situation where the coordination is no more between CLs rather between CL coordination functions belonging to different entities, a use case also mentioned by ETSI ZSM [ZSM009]. Such a coordination mechanism between coordinators requires i) awareness, i.e., each coordination function must know the other, ii) interaction, i.e., the functions must be able to communicate, and iii) a common set of information related to the CLs.

Figure 4-13 illustrates how the CL provisioning and their registration to the CL Coordination changes to address new coordination context.

Figure 4-13 CL Coordination functions' interaction at Orchestration time.

When a tenant submits an intent (e.g., a service provisioning) at DSP, the corresponding request is orchestrated and triggers the creation of a business-oriented CL at DSP and, in parallel, a service provisioning request at COP (1)(2). The DSP CL is registered to the CL coordination function (3) while at the COP the service is orchestrated, creating related CLs (one or more) (4)(5). At (6) COP CL Coordination is notified: at this point it notifies its own homologue at DSP, through the IF, about the creation of service's CLs related to a given business CL. The workflow for the decommissioning follows similar steps. At runtime, the coordination can be two-fold: i) conflict mitigation/avoidance and ii) collaboration.

In (i) the CL Coordination at DSP is assisted by the intent conflict detection/resolution modules, belonging to the intent fulfilment set of service. When a conflict is detected, the CL coordination logic decides the mitigation actions, in the case the affected CLs all belong to the DSP. The CL coordination exploits the interfaces provided by the CL governance to steer the CLs' execution, avoiding race conditions and conflicting decisions. It may happen the case where the conflict is between DSP and COP CLs, as shown in Figure 4-14a. In this case, both the CLs react to the same input from the IF, trying to enforce some decision on the respective orchestrators (1). To avoid conflicting decisions, simple strategy is to give priority to the CL belongs to the DSP. Once the decision is enforced at the DSP, the consequent request of service modification at COP (2) results into a modification of its dedicated CL. So, the existing COP CL will be stopped and modified to fit service modification (3)(4), while the service orchestration will resolve any potential inconsistencies created by the execution of the previous CL.

Figure 4-14 a) Race condition; b) Cooperation through escalation; c) Conflict mitigation through escalation

With respect to the case (ii), ETSI ZSM considers three types of collaboration: the delegation, where a hierarchically higher CL (e.g., DSP CL) delegates its goal to a lower layer CLs (e.g., COP) and the escalation, representing the opposite case. The third type of collaboration studied by ETSI ZSM, peer-to-peer, involves CLs at the same level of hierarchy. As for the conflict, also in collaboration, the base idea is that the higher layer takes the final decision and, consequently, the form of collaboration considered is the escalation, from COP to DSP. The collaboration between loops is applied when the coordination module detects that one loop is not able to fulfil its own goal or, in general, another loop may be more effective than another. In this case, the CL coordination at COP detects that a given loop cannot fulfil its own goal (and no other CLs at the same level can do that). At this point, the CL coordination at COP level notifies the one at the DSP that any adjustment should be performed by the correspondent business-oriented CL. This operation is shown in Figure 4-14b. A more complex example is represented Figure 4-14c: in this case, the CL coordination at COP takes advance of the escalation to solve a local CL conflict. In the figure are represented several loops grouped by services (green and yellow). At the COP level, CLs belonging to the yellow service start conflicting with the one belonging to the green service and the CL governance requests the intervention of the local CL coordination which, in this example, is not able to solve the conflict. Hence, the COP CL coordination escalates to its own homologue at the DSP, which will act to the local CLs to enforce corrective action at the DSP resulting in a tuning of the service at COP and the consequent update of the CLs at that level.

Figure 4-15 Component interaction for CLs management in the multi-DSP federation scenario

In the multi-DSP aggregation scenario, the tenant-1 type (aggregator) is in charge of coordinating a set of required intents in order to deliver a complete service towards the vertical client or final user. Each intent is fulfilled independently by an intent-based DSM in a SAD. Thus, the operational scope of CL governance and CL coordination is limited within one administrative domain, where they share the same information of resource capabilities and monitoring data. On the other hand, the multi-DSP federation scenario delegates the responsibility of intent coordination to the intent-based DSM that receives the request. If the selected intent-based DSM's local resource is not eligible to fulfil the vertical service on its own, DSMs from other known SADs are invoked to contribute their resource capabilities. In this case, the leading DSM not only manages its CL but also monitors other DSMs' CLs status in order to have an overview of the E2E intent provisioning process. The intent object and CL information must be kept consistent and available among involved parties. Moreover, the order of intent executions can be efficiently organized by the leading DSM and informed to assigned DSMs so that they are aware of their roles in the process. Additionally, any deviation between the operating resources and the declared intent object, CL information, intent delivery pipeline, must trigger an autonomous reconciliation. As a result, the Declarative Intent Reconciliation (DIR) enabler, presented in D2.3 [HEX224-D23], is essential for this purpose and its function is shown in Figure 4-15.

When the leading DSM receives an intent request from the tenant and determines that external resources are needed, it follows the workflow outlined in Section 4.1.1.2 to identify the required participants. Once all participants have been selected, the DIR module in the leading DSM creates a repository on the Version Control System (VCS) (i.e., Git server) with the intent object description and registers the contributors to deliver the E2E service. All related DSMs are notified by the VCS, then each DSM pushes its business CL created by the CL governance to the VCS. In addition, DIR constructs a workflow to specify the optimal

execution order to ensure service delivery. Once the leading DSM pushes this pipeline description to the repository, the intent delivery process is activated. VCS oversees invoking corresponding DSMs according to the declared workflow. The final step of the pipeline corresponds to the creation of the intent. If a conflict arises in one or more domains that could necessitate changes in CL goals or actions, the CL Coordinator and CL governance inform the affected DSMs' DIR modules with a new version of the business CL. The DIR then pushes this update to the VCS, where the new desired state is recorded. Also, it is important to note that DSMs use intent-DSP APIs as the communication channel for managing intents as described previously. Meanwhile, communication between DSM DIR modules and the VCS is specifically intended for notifications, as well as for intents, CLs, and pipeline information updates.

4.2.4 E2E intent-based trust management

The emergence of 6G networks introduces multi-stakeholder scenarios that offer significant benefits for innovative solutions. However, these scenarios also present unprecedented challenges, such as establishing reliable relationships amid numerous entities and domains. To navigate potential uncertainties and enhance decision-making in such complex environments, incorporating trust mechanisms becomes essential. Trust acts as a bridge over the gap of uncertainty in multi-stakeholder and cross-domain interactions [VLP+24].

A foundational element in addressing trustworthiness within Hexa-X-II ecosystem is the concept of the Level of Trust (LoT). The LoT is designed to assess security aspects of network services in the cloud continuum. This objective is reached via the LoT Framework that is, in turn, divided into two main modules: i) trust-based intent management and ii) the LoT assessment function. Both modules complement each other to ensure a trust establishment for E2E connections in decentralised 6G scenarios (see Figure 4-16).

Figure 4-16 Level of trust framework architecture.

On the one hand, the *trust-based intent management* module is in charge of understanding DSC/DSP trust intents before starting a business relationship. To this end, such a module provides an entry point for end-user through a graphical user interface (UI) where they may type their trust-related requirements using natural language. Since no trust-based intent interpreters were discovered in the literature review, we have designed our ad-hoc trust-based interpreter. In this regard, a high-level descriptive language is defined which, in turn, brings the chance to represent the knowledge regarding trust assessment and the cloud continuum. Thus, an ontology is published [VPG24] by following the well-known Linked Open Term methodology [PFF+22] which is also contemplated in ETSI SAREF [GLP+23] standards. The ontology uses a soft-reuse strategy including the Uniform Resource Identifiers of other existing ontologies to reduce redundancy and ease interoperability. For example, such an ontology inherits classes and properties from the TR292 TM Forum intent ontology [TMFIO24]. Nevertheless, the core of the ontology is built from scratch as terms like cloud continuum, service assurance, TLA, or LoT have not been considered in prior solutions. After finding out the descriptive language and the knowledge to represent, the next step of the *trust-based intent management*

module is to create and train a Named Entity Recognition (NER) model. By means of a NER model, it is possible to recognise, manually or automatically, certain tags expressed in natural language sentences. For this purpose, spaCy is selected as a library to custom our NER model via a blank approach to discover keywords using an Inside-Outside-Beginning tagging scheme. Regarding the encoding actions, *word2vec* has been selected since it leverages a neural network to learn dense vector representations of words contemplating their semantic and syntactic contexts. Therefore, the outcome of *word2vec* is later the input of a Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory, which produces better results for English language, to link information and deliver a final outcome.

On another hand, the *Level of Trust Assessment Function (LoTAF)* is the module responsible for beginning the monitoring and decision phases concerning trust requirements. Regarding the monitoring activities, LoTAF follows the guidelines of the [CQL+21] theoretical framework for Intent-Based Networking (IBN) architectures. Concretely, the *Trust Intent Monitoring* gathers quantitative parameters that may determine the health score of network services and services running through the continuum. The information to be retrieved is determined by the TLA settled between all parties. Nevertheless, service assurance can assess health scores by analysing parameters from the Central Processing Unit (CPU), memory, internal processes, sensors, disk, etc. In addition, external monitoring tools may be connected to our *Trust Intent Monitoring* as external collectors. In addition to quantitative parameters, information like feedback, reputation, or historical interactions may also be considered by LoTAF to determine a final LoT, which combines both objective and subjective trust indicators. Afterward, the LoT is forwarded to the *Trust Manager* who is responsible of handling coordination actions, *Manager* in conjunction with the *Decision Agent*, regarding the trust lifecycle, e.g., inform potential deviations on the trust agreements or notify punishments to be applied on DSPs if they carry out violations on TLAs.

When it comes to interactions with other enablers, the LoT framework directly reaches out the trust management system, user-centric service provisioning system, monitoring and telemetry framework, Management Capability Exposure (MCE), intent reporting, and 3P services (see Figure 4-17). Note that user-centric service provisioning system, monitoring and telemetry framework, management capability exposure comes from the enablers defined in [HEX225-D65].

Figure 4-17 E2E intent-based trust management sequence diagram.

The sequence diagram outlines a workflow where an end-user, referred to as DSC/DSP, submits a trust intent request to the trust capability exposure component. This request is forwarded to the trust-based interpreter, which analyses the content by identifying trust-related tokens. The interpreter double-checks these details with the DSC/DSP to ensure that the trust requirements are accurately captured. After verification, the interpreter passes the extracted trust requirements to the intent fulfilment component. Intent fulfilment consults the service portfolio to identify the necessary services, focusing on KPIs and KVIs. It then verifies these trust requirements against the contracted TLA by consulting the 3P profiling system, considering the user's profile. The component maps the intent to executable services, performs a feasibility check to ensure the services can meet the trust requirements, and stores the trust intent in the knowledge representation database. Once the intent is accepted, the user-centric service provisioning system is informed. This module communicates with the trust management system, which initiates the trust evaluation process. Note that the trust management system starts both LoTAF and the trust evaluation function (not included in the sequence diagram). The trust intent monitoring component begins monitoring the deployed services by interacting with the service portfolio and checking internal monitoring agents. It also subscribes to external attributes published by the monitoring and telemetry Framework to ensure comprehensive oversight.

The system continuously reassesses the LoT by analysing real-time data for any deviations from the TLA using the trust analysis engine. If deviations are detected, the trust decision controller applies necessary adjustments to the LoT and informs the provisioning system of the issues. All evaluation data is stored in the knowledge representation database, and the user is updated about the trust status of their services. In summary, this workflow ensures that the user's trust intent is thoroughly processed and maintained through continuous monitoring and evaluation. It provides transparency and upholds trustworthiness throughout the service delivery by actively managing compliance with the agreed trust levels and promptly addressing any deviations.

4.3 Conclusions on intent-based E2E service management automation framework

The next generation of networks is steering towards enhanced resource M&O, focusing on greater automation and efficiency. This chapter has explored new pathways and possibilities for designing and implementing intent-based M&O systems to further evolve current networks towards more autonomous and high-performing solutions. It has described the architecture components, management models, and E2E services required to meet the demands of 6G multi-stakeholder scenarios where intent-based technologies are expected to be applied.

Intent-based M&O aims to eliminate the need for human operators to understand the intricate technical details of the control infrastructure and underlying resources to effectively manage them for delivering E2E services. This approach seeks to enhance interactions with tenants, enabling them to define desired services and allowing the system to autonomously assess feasibility or suggest viable alternatives when needed. To achieve this level of autonomy, the chapter presented how intent-based components across various administrative domains can interact, outlining two primary models: aggregation and federation. The aggregation model retains decision-making (such as selecting the domain for specific intents) at the tenant level, whereas the federation model promotes increased automation by allowing the control and management system (i.e., DSM) to independently generate and manage intent-based requests across other domains to deliver comprehensive E2E services. Furthermore, the chapter identified essential DSM functionalities required for full-scale intent-based service orchestration. Finally, a set of use cases, that demonstrate how intent-based M&O systems should be structured and implemented, is presented. Specific scenarios are included to showcase how different functionalities and enablers contribute to maximizing the advantages of intent-based systems. The proposed use cases cover four main areas: a) intent provisioning and fulfilment, b) continuous evaluation to ensure the intent delivers as expected, c) managing intent-based CLs, and d) incorporating trust parameters for secure and reliable network services.

Despite the new architectural framework, functionalities, and services described several challenges and areas for future work remain. For instance, the development of specific policies for intent conflict resolution is still in its early stages, with no standardized solutions available. Other challenges include potential security vulnerabilities during the intent lifecycle or fulfilment phase due to the abstraction layer used to generate intents based on lower-layer information, as well as deliberate conflict generation.

5 Security, privacy and resilience

This chapter provides a final view on the identification, description and evaluation of the SPR features of the 6G system. Work on this matter started with the identification of a *6G delta*, related to the specific threats and potential mitigation tools associated with the technology evolution being proposed for 6G [HEX223-D22], continuing with a detailed analysis of the detection and mitigation functionalities identified to address the 6G delta, structured as *controls* (essential components providing core SPR functionality as safeguard, detector, or countermeasure with respect to specific threats) and grouped into enablers [HEX224-D23]. The evaluation of these proposed controls and their integration patterns with the enablers defined within the project was provided in [HEX224-D24].

The chapter provides a final evaluation of these controls and patterns, updating the experimental results on low-Technology Readiness Level (TRL) controls, especially focused on Physical Layer Security (PLS), analysing the latest results on resilience simulations, discussing the integration patterns for privacy and data security in support of JCAS and trustworthy AI, and introducing the proposal for a Trusted Notary Service as reliable source of evidence for assessing trustworthiness of components and services, acting as a focal point for sources and consumers of data related to this assessment procedures. This evaluation is completed with a review of three significant enablers in development by other SNS projects, especially connected with SPR controls. In addition to this, an analysis of the security considerations applicable to the 6G enablers defined in Hexa-X-II is provided in section 8.2, as conclusion of the coordination work regarding SPR issues with the other activities in the project.

5.1 Experimental results on PLS

5.1.1 Physical context awareness

The effectiveness of Secret Key Generation (SKG) algorithms using PLS depends on real-time wireless channel conditions unlike the traditional cryptographic algorithms, which rely on the mathematical properties like integer factorization and discrete logarithm problem to ensure security. However, deriving these mathematical properties from the wireless channel in PLS is challenging. Therefore, since SKG rates depend on the randomness of observed data in the environment, identifying different contexts in the channel environment and leveraging these properties can lead to higher SKG rates compared to traditional SKG approaches.

5.1.1.1 USRP-based hardware demonstrator setup details

The demonstrator hardware setup consists of two Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) X410 devices operating at a carrier frequency of 3.75 GHz and a sample rate of 491.52 MS/s. This configuration provides a usable bandwidth of 400 MHz. The two USRPs are synchronized using a shared reference clock and a time source, enabling the synchronized exchange of frames. Figure 5-1 shows a photo of the current hardware setup.

Figure 5-1 Demonstrator hardware setup featuring two synchronized USRP X410 devices.

The structure of the measurements and the transmitted signals is illustrated in Figure 5-2 below. In this setup, Alice and Bob exchange frames in burst mode. During each measurement, a total of NUM_FRAMES=5 frames (for illustration purposes, below figure only shows 3 frames) are exchanged, with a temporal gap of FRAME_DELAY=0.1s between each frame. The transmission delay between Alice and Bob is DELAY_AB=0.01s. Each frame consists of a chirp signal, 2048 samples in length, with a 400 MHz bandwidth. Once the frames are collected, they are passed to the SKG and context-detection algorithms, as shown in the figure below. The context-detection algorithm then determines the parameters for key generation, and the keys are subsequently generated.

Figure 5-2 Left: Structure of the transmitted signals to measure the wireless channels, indicating when Alice and Bob transmit. Right: Information flow at the receiver, indicating the processing steps involved at the receiver side.

5.1.1.2 Measurements done in different environments

This setup enabled a thorough evaluation of the random forest-based feature extraction classifier's performance under varying environmental and mobility conditions. The measurements and real-time Carrier Frequency References (CFRs) were captured across the following three distinct scenarios:

- *Line-of-Sight, static positions (LOS-Static)*: Both USRPs remained stationary with a direct line-of-sight (LOS) path between them.
- *Non-Line-of-Sight, static positions (NLOS-Static)*: Both USRPs remained stationary without a direct LOS path between them.
- *Dynamic USRPs (dynamic)*: Both USRPs were in motion during the measurement.

5.1.1.3 Integration of context-aware algorithm in the demonstrator and test

In the context-aware detection step, ML techniques were employed to classify environments based on CFRs, leveraging feature extraction to capture essential signal characteristics. Two types of features were extracted: momentary features, which describe the intrinsic properties of individual channel impulse responses, and temporal variation features, which capture changes between consecutive CFRs over time. Momentary features included statistical and signal-specific attributes such as absolute and phase differences between samples, LOS component attributes (including amplitude and phase), and statistical measures like average, variance, kurtosis, and skewness. Temporal variation features were designed to capture the dynamics of CFRs over time and included cross-correlation between consecutive CFRs, rates of change in LOS component attributes over time, and principal component analysis to summarize patterns across CFR sequences.

The extracted features were used to label windows of CFR data, which were then evaluated using various classification algorithms, e.g., logistic regression, decision trees, random forest, support vector machines, k-nearest neighbours, and convolutional neural networks. Among the tested methods, random forest emerged as the most effective classifier. The success of this model was attributed to the careful selection of key features, including cross-correlation, sample differences, component variance, and LOS amplitude and phase change rate. These features proved instrumental in accurately distinguishing between environments, highlighting their importance in environment classification tasks based on CFRs.

The confusion matrix (Figure 5-3), provides a visual representation of the model's performance in classifying three distinct scenarios: LOS-Static, NLOS-Static, and Dynamic. It shows high classification accuracy: LOS-

Static (93.4%), NLOS-Static (95.8%), and dynamic (96.6%). Misclassifications are minimal, mainly between dynamic and static scenarios. Overall, the model performs strongly with minor areas for refinement.

Figure 5-3 Confusion matrix showcasing accuracy in classifying LOS-Static, NLOS-Static, and dynamic scenarios

5.1.1.4 Identification of SKG parameters based on the context and SKG algorithm

Figure 5-4 shows the number of secure bits generated for each chirp frame, plotted against different combinations of filter and quantization levels (on the X-axis) and the corresponding environmental scenarios (on the Y-axis). It can be observed that, for each scenario, using a higher number of filters and quantization levels results in a greater number of secure bits generated per frame. This data is used as a lookup table to determine the secret key generation parameters for the context-based algorithms. Based on the key generation rate and the cross-correlation between consecutive generated keys, as well as a predefined security threshold for the similarity between these keys, we can optimize parameters such as the frame period for key generation, the number of filters, and the quantization levels. In dynamic scenarios, shorter periods for key generation can be employed compared to static scenarios, as the environmental changes allow the security threshold to be satisfied more easily. Additionally, in NLOS scenarios within static environments, the increased multipath reflections result in greater environmental variations. Consequently, a higher number of keys can be generated within a given time frame compared to LOS scenarios.

Figure 5-4 Number of secure bits generated per chirp frame for various combinations of filter and quantization

5.1.1.5 Analysis of SKG rates with/without context awareness

The channel reciprocity between the two USRPs, considered as Alice and Bob, is utilized to extract secret keys. The received signals from the USRPs are processed and converted into binary digits, which are then used as secret keys through the secret key generation algorithm. The process can be split into the following steps:

- *Channel probing:* The received samples are passed through a filterbank to extract randomness in the frequency domain. The filterbank consists of band-pass filters, and the time-averaged power over the specified frequency bands is measured. The bandwidth of each subband is determined by the number of filters in the filterbank, and the received signals are sampled in the frequency domain to capture the received power.
- *Quantization:* A linear quantizer converts the received power values into binary vectors (1's and 0's). The quantizer's granularity depends on the number of quantization levels, and the number of generated bits is influenced by both the number of filters and quantization levels.
- *Information reconciliation:* Due to channel noise imperfections, the generated bits at Alice and Bob after quantization may differ. This discrepancy is corrected using Slepian-Wolf-based reconciliation with forward error correction codes, specifically Polar codes in this case [SC21].
- A syndrome is generated based on Alice's quantized information and transmitted to Bob. Bob uses this syndrome to correct errors in the quantized bits, ensuring that both Alice and Bob end up with the same binary vectors. In order to avoid the leakage of information in the syndrome during transmission, proper privacy amplification should be imposed, which is not considered in this work.
- In Table 5-1, the randomness of the generated keys is evaluated using the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) test suite for all scenarios. The table shows the quality of the keys based on the percentage of block of bits passing the corresponding randomness tests. It should be noted that these keys are not the final keys and considered for post processing like privacy amplification. The derived key is subjected to entropy tests and randomness tests again to ensure it meets cryptographic standards. If the final key fails these tests, it is either discarded or further refined. The strength of the generated keys in the case of attacks (passive or active) require further scrutiny and is not in the scope of this work.

Table 5-1 Randomness evaluation of generated keys for scenarios based on NIST test results (% of frames passing the randomness tests once converted to bits)

Tests (%)	NLOS Static	LOS Static	Dynamic	LOS Static 2
Monobit	52.70	74.44	80.95	97.48
Freq_block	27.37	24.87	24.55	35.84
Runs	85.40	89.19	92.21	97.48
Longest block	98.11	98.37	96.76	99.54
Serial	55.24	50.94	64.67	68.26
Cumulative Sums	55.90	63.63	67.90	86.52

5.1.2 Physical anomaly detection

5.1.2.1 Placement of anomaly detection in RAN

In 6G networks, energy and cost efficiency as well as security are key design principles. Thus, the design of security solutions needs to be also efficient and follow cost-aware cybersecurity practices. This necessitates the joint optimization of security with other criteria, such as resource utilization and QoS. The joint security-QoS optimization in RAN involves fine-tuning security mechanisms to achieve the best performance without compromising protection. This includes balancing the load on network elements for security operations, ensuring efficient resource use, and minimizing latency introduced by security processes. Given the disaggregated architecture of RAN, the joint optimization ensures that security measures are tailored to specific components and interfaces, maintaining overall network performance. By identifying attempts of adversarial

attacks at the earliest possible stages will limit the spread of the distribution of unwanted traffic within the network. By discarding such redundant traffic close to the entry point can significantly reduce the total energy consumption in the network. Next generation RAN, with its flexible and disaggregated architecture, enables the implementation of such strategies more effectively. By using open interfaces and modular components, network operators can deploy customized intrusion detection systems/mechanisms (IDS/IDM) that suit their specific needs. The flexibility of RAN allows for a more adaptive security strategy, where the IDS strategy can be periodically or dynamically adjusted based on the actual state of the network, the required QoS, the expected security level, and the risk level toward the goal of improving energy efficiency. This adaptive approach, supported by the scalable and programmable nature of RAN, ensures optimal performance while maintaining security and conserving energy resources, ultimately enhancing the overall efficiency and resilience of the network.

Features like disaggregation, openness, cloudification, and added intelligence of next generation RAN, has broadened the threat surface, which become complex compared to previous generations. For instance, in the below open RAN architecture, there are RAN components operating in different control loops. Such disaggregated architecture should include security agents (SecAs), capable of detecting anomalies, deployed in different locations in RAN (i.e., as exemplified in Figure 5-5). Each of these SecAs contains several different detection models with different performance and resource/energy consumption profiles. These models can be trained online or offline based on factors such as data availability, real-time requirements, and resource availability. To achieve higher efficiency, the detection model in each SecA can be changed periodically or dynamically. For example, one SecA can operate with a basic detection model where the environment it is in is stable, while another SecA resides in a threatened environment and has the option to utilize an advanced detection model considering the resources available and QoS constraints. To address this security performance and resource/QoS trade-off, a ML-based joint optimization approach would be beneficial. The model can be placed in a centralized location where it has access to multiple data streams. There can be different types of inputs, one being security performance metrics such as detection accuracy and detection time provided from SecAs, and another being resource utilization and QoS inputs like CPU/memory consumption, bandwidth, and latency. In addition, there is a possibility to input non-RAN-specific data such as geopolitical, SLAs, and regulatory and policy data. The joint-optimization model can process the data and enforce the adjustment of detection level in each SecA periodically or dynamically to achieve the best possible balance between security performance and resource efficiency and QoS. Depending on the severity and the context of the anomalies further actions should be taken by the respective SecAs. This may vary from the notification of the non-critical anomaly to the taking immediate remediation actions. The study needs to be extended how such remediation actions can be incorporated in real-time or non-real time CLs as per required by the system.

Figure 5-5 An exemplified scenario for the deployment of security agents and joint security-QoS optimization applications in the RAN domain.

5.1.2.2 Digital Twin-enabled spectrum anomaly detection

Due to the inherent nature of 6G as wireless technology of using an open communication medium, the QoS delivered by 6G might be severely degraded by interference. Such interference can be caused unintentionally, but might also be caused intentionally, referred to as jamming, to cause a denial of service (DoS). With keeping in mind that 6G is intended to enable various critical applications, for example in manufacturing use cases, it is essential to ensure integrity of the spectrum used by the network. For this reason, a DT-based approach on detecting spectrum anomalies which is particularly tailored to non-public networks has been developed. The approach aims on achieving a strong detection performance while following a general perspective, i.e., not focussing on a special type of anomalies.

The approach suggests employing a digital twin of the radio environment to estimate an expectation of the spectrum occupation in real-time. The approach builds upon recent advancements in ray tracing and machine learning and compares the expectation from the digital twin with the actual spectrum occupation which is perceived by distributed sensing units. This approach allows for the integration of contextual awareness in the anomaly detection process. Since the last deliverable [HEX224-D24], simulation implementation and investigations has been proceeded. Exemplarily, receiver operating characteristics curves for the detection of an interfering transmitter are shown in Figure 5-6. Major findings include that sensing units with LOS connection to most of the monitored area (e.g., at the ceiling), can achieve the best performance but are on the downside sensitive to DT modelling errors which significantly degrade detection performance in opposite to sensing units which predominantly have NLOS connections to most of the monitored area. Moreover, the substitution of ray tracing by an ML model was investigated for this specific use case. It was shown that the minor deviations between ray tracing and ML do not affect the detection performance but significantly reduce the computational complexity which paves the way towards implementation in a real-time detection system. An extensive discussion of the results is provided in [HEX2-SBS+24].

Figure 5-6 Receiver operating characteristics curve for spectrum anomaly detection using a DT for a sensing unit height of 1.5 m and different accuracies of the DT model

Referring to the blueprint of the Hexa-X-II 6G E2E architecture (Chapter 6), the proposed approach belongs to the SPR features which are part of the pervasive functionalities overarching the four specified network layers. The approach can be seen as foundation of an automated control loop for ensuring spectrum integrity in the 6G (non-public) networks. For the implementation of the approach, the service exposure capabilities, enabling the interfaces between the anomaly detection application and the 6G RAN NF and the SeMF, are key. Since the technology readiness of the proposed solution is at an early stage, future work will focus on the interfaces enabling network adjustments in case an anomaly has been detected.

5.1.3 Physical layer deception

Physical Layer Deception (PLD), which was first proposed in [HEX2-HZS+23] and later examined in [HEX224-D23], [HEX224-D24], and [CHZ+25], demonstrates significant potential for active defence against wireless eavesdropping attacks. However, implementing PLD in real-world systems faces several technical hurdles, particularly in developing effective ciphering algorithms and their associated codebooks.

Research in [HEX2-HZS+25] demonstrates that codebook cardinality plays a critical role in PLD's security performance. Higher cardinality codebooks enable more robust deception capabilities when eavesdroppers fail to obtain the correct ciphering key. Additionally, small codebooks present inherent limitations, as each codeword carries minimal information, thus reducing the impact of individual deception attempts at the codeword level. While distributing information across multiple codewords might seem appealing, this approach risks introducing detectable patterns that eavesdroppers could exploit to identify deceptive ciphering. Consequently, larger codebooks emerge as the preferred choice for PLD implementations.

However, implementing large codebooks for general message transmission presents significant challenges for traditional ciphering algorithms. These algorithms must maintain closure - ensuring that every ciphertext codeword remains valid as a plaintext codeword. One promising approach to address this constraint involves pre-mapping source messages into a semantic space where closed deceptive ciphering becomes more tractable. This strategy proves especially valuable in systems where semantic accuracy takes precedence over exact source message reproduction. Message reconstruction at the receiver can then leverage semantic decoders, potentially implemented using generative models, to interpret the decoded semantic information.

A novel framework called Visual ENcryption for Eavesdropping NegAtion (VENENA) was developed as a demonstrator, combining PLD with image poisoning for a deceptive graphics-based encryption.

Figure 5-7 Sample scenario for physical layer deception evaluation

As illustrated in Figure 5-7, we consider a simple scenario where each confidential message contains only an integer in range 0 to 9, which is mapped to one of ten tags with respect to a predefined table. For each tag, an image dataset is prepared, and a Deep Neural Networks (DNN)-based classification network is trained to extract the tag of each image. Thus, Alice can transmit an image randomly selected from the dataset with corresponding tag to represent the confidential message, which can be recognized by Bob with the classification network. This can be understood as building a semantic communication system.

Then, to realize deceptive transmission, Alice does not directly send the image carrying the confidential message. Instead, it generates a randomly falsified message and selects an image carrying this falsified message. A pre-trained poisoning network is then used by Alice to “poison” the original image, aiming at inducing the classification network recognizing the poisoned image with the target tag that corresponds to the correct confidential message, while minimizing the energy of the differential error (i.e., the poison mask image). Thus, the original image is playing the role of ciphertext, and the poison mask image is the key. Both images are individually channel-encoded and then combined in the power domain, with the original image’s power overwhelming the poison mask image’s power, which closes the PLD encryption process. Bob is supposed to carry out successive interference cancellation to decode the original image and the poison mask sequentially, and therewith reconstruct the poisoned image, which it classifies with the DNN to obtain the tag

representing the confidential message. In contrast, Eve, which is supposed to suffer from poor channel conditions, is unlikely to do so, but only able to decode the original image and therewith obtain the deceptive falsified message.

To evaluate the capability of this VENENA framework we conducted numerical simulations, where we considered the system to have a channel bandwidth of 1MHz and the gross bit rate of 1 Mbps. The transmission power budget was set to 100mW, the mean legitimate channel gain -85 dB, the mean eavesdropping channel gain -95 dB. We considered both channels to undergo Rayleigh fading and an Additive white Gaussian noise of -174 dBW/Hz. We set the following three schemes for benchmarking:

1. Deception off, full power: No deception is applied, i.e., the image carrying the correct message will be directly transmitted. The transmission power is 100 mW.
2. Deception off, 75% power: No deception is applied, transmitted at 75 mW; and
3. Deception on, 75% mixing: Deception applied, image and poison mixed at a power ratio of 75% to 25%.

Furthermore, we considered both a full-knowledge Eve that shares the full information about the system design (including the mapping table and the deceptive mechanism design, which represents the cases of insider attackers and eavesdroppers with high computation power to undermine the cryptographic security), and a naive Eve that knows the mapping table but is unaware of the deceptive scheme (which represents the case of classical attackers). The results of 10,000 independent Monte-Carlo trails are listed in Table 5-2

Table 5-2 Evaluation results for Physical Layer Deception.

	Deception off, full power	Deception off, 75% power	Deception on, 75% mixing
Bob	97.22%	96.91%	93.43%
Eve (full knowledge)	88.96%	86.82%	51.12%
Eve (partial knowledge)	89.14%	86.66%	5.18%

A more systematic sensitivity test regarding the power mixing ratio, the transmission power budget, and the eavesdropping channel gain was carried out considering three different scenes:

- Scene 1: 100 mW transmission power, -95 dB eavesdropping channel gain.
- Scene 2: 200 mW transmission power, -95 dB eavesdropping channel gain.
- Scene 3: 100 mW transmission power, -90 dB eavesdropping channel gain.

Figure 5-8 shows results of 1000 independent Monte-Carlo trails conducted for each scene and power mixing ratio. In all three scenes, Bob is able to maintain a satisfactory perception accuracy over 80% while keeping full-knowledge Eve's perception accuracy below 50%. Meanwhile, Eve with partial knowledge can hardly perceive correct information any more than 10%.

Figure 5-8 Results of power mixing ratio tests for Physical Layer Deception

The VENENA example demonstrated here has a tremendous overhead by transmitting a coloured picture to convey only one integer. Nevertheless, the experiment is only a proof-of-concept with extensively simplified semantic knowledge base (e.g., only ten semantic tags) for the PLD technique without concerning the

efficiency. By deploying more efficient semantic codec (including well-designed classical symmetric block encryptors), this overhead rate can be suppressed to a reasonable level for practical deployment.

5.2 Results examples of E2E resilience simulations

During the network planning phase, it is crucial to ensure that the E2E architecture meets resilience requirements, particularly in terms of availability. To address this, an availability calculation tool has been developed to cover VNF level, virtualization layer and servers hosting the VNFs. It is designed to be highly flexible, allowing users to explore different configurations to meet their specific needs. It can simulate scenarios based on the Lower Layer split (LLS) architecture:

- With customizable parameters such as the number of microservices per Virtual Network Function (VNF), repair rates for each element (Mean Time to Repair), etc.
- With or without microservice replicas.
- With or without VNF redundancy.

The following four scenarios illustrate the tool's flexibility and the impact of VNF redundancy and microservices replication on E2E architecture availability. The scenarios are illustrated with diagrams, showing the involved network functions and the corresponding microservice replicas involved:

Scenario 1: Reference communication system (baseline Case): This scenario models a simple communication system as a chain of VNFs:

Scenario 2: Communication system with microservice replicas: This scenario builds on the base case by introducing replicas for microservices to improve fault tolerance.

Scenario 3: Microservice replicas + core VNF redundancy: This scenario introduces redundancy for core VNFs (e.g., UPFs) while retaining microservice replicas.

Scenario 4: Fully Redundant End-to-End VNF Chain: This scenario represents the most resilient configuration, with full redundancy applied throughout the VNF chain.

To assess system availability, the tool leverages *Reliability Block Diagrams (RBDs)* to model and analyse the dependencies between components. RBDs are graphical representations that depict how components in a system are connected in series or parallel, reflecting the logical dependencies and redundancy between them. In this context, RBDs are used to model the interdependencies of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs), microservices, and replicas, enabling a detailed calculation of system availability. Using this approach, the tool computes availability rapidly, allowing for detailed analysis. For demonstration purposes, the following assumptions were made consistently across all scenarios: 2 microservices for each RAN, 3 microservices for each UPF, 2 replicas by microservice in case of replication, 2 VNF instantiations in case of redundancy.

The results are presented in the graph shown in Figure 5-9, illustrating the progressive improvements in availability knowing that the availability for Scenario 1 = 0.98999859.

Figure 5-9 Availability evaluation for different scenarios generated by the resilience simulation tool

The results show how adding replicas and redundancy enhances system availability. Depending on service requirements, the planner can select the architecture that best aligns with the desired availability, the closest can help in optimizing investment and avoiding unnecessary costs.

5.3 JCAS threat mitigation

Considering the architectural components of a JCAS system [HEX224-D23], the security and privacy controls must focus on the UE, gNB, core network, and associated interfaces. The security controls help to ensure confidentiality, integrity, and privacy in the JCAS system. Security controls for JCAS are discussed along following dimensions.

5.3.1 Security controls

5.3.1.1 Authentication and authorization

Authentication and authorization controls between various entities in JCAS system are required to assure that communication is happening with the expected, verified and authorized entity. That is the sensing configuration at sensing radio units (RU) at UE and gNB should come from authenticated and authorized Sensing Control Function (SCF), applications should receive the sensing results (RESULT_STREAM) they are authorized to receive as per the sensing and access control policies. 5G authentication methods can be reused in JCAS system such as 5G authentication and key agreement or extensible authentication protocol - authentication and key Agreement to authenticate UE and the network, and IPsec Internet key exchange v2 certificates-based authentication to mutually authenticate gNB and core network. Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) should take care of verifying and authorizing third-parties interacting with JCAS system [DUN+24].

To schedule sensing on UE or use UE resources (sensing hardware, memory, CPU) for sensing purpose, explicit authorization of sensing request is required in JCAS, which could be based on agreement between UE/subscriber and network. Access control and sensing policies that reflect real-life constraints (geographical restrictions on sensing, privacy and regulations constraints on sensing, UE consent and agreement for sensing) need to be designed and considered for each sensing request in timely manner. In our proposed architecture, a sensing policy, consent, and transparency management component [DUN+24] provides the framework for managing and applying these sensing policies on sensing request.

5.3.1.2 Logging and data provenance

Logging and data provenance as security controls are currently implemented as per operator specific policies. In JCAS, due to involvement of UE in sensing, in addition to gNB and core side, logging would be beneficial at UE side to serve multiple purposes. One purpose could be to collect the evidence to assure the subscriber that sensing is happening in compliance with the consent and agreement policies set by the subscriber, other purpose could be to provide the logs (data/metadata from Rx/Tx on sensing signals, on processing, on disclosure) to network in case of a security incident. At the same time, data provenance can be used to verify data origin, guarantee the authenticity of sensing measurements and provide evidence of processing done on the data by various entities. Provenance information is used internally but can also be exposed to some extent to the user of sensing data, thus enhancing trust in the information produced by the JCAS system.

5.3.1.3 Protecting JCAS data in transit

Data produced by a JCAS system can be broadly classified into control data (to control/schedule resources to initiate sensing), sensing data (produced as a result of sensing activity including raw Rx/Tx sensing signals, pre-processed data and sensing results) and transparency data (notification sent to UE/targets).

Control data in JCAS can be secured in-transit using the confidentiality, integrity protection and replay protection from the 5G control plane security. For sensing data, user plane security can be used for providing similar protections. However, based on the novel operational and technical JCAS requirements, a new plane e.g., data plane can be designed to transmit sensing data. Regardless, confidentiality and integrity protection should be applied to securely transmit the sensing data. Future studies shall investigate how the sensing signals (Rx/Tx) can be encrypted and integrity protected to deter tampering and unauthorized disclosure threats. It is also important to ensure the integrity of transparency data received by UE/target from network.

5.3.1.4 Sensing data security

Insecure processing of sensitive sensing data may leak Personally Identifiable Information (PII) of targets/UE and physical environment to unauthorized entities while insecure storage may cause unauthorized data disclosure threat, so it is important to secure sensing data at-rest (storage) and in-process (processing) at UE and network side. Sensing data security controls should ensure sensing data protection through entire lifecycle (secure collection, storage to secure disposal), data retention policies, secure handling of keys for encryption and integrity protection, strict access control, and monitoring and logging access to the sensitive data. Depending on the sensitivity of sensing information, various Trusted Execution Environment [SAB15] technologies can be utilized for processing sensing information in a secure manner.

5.3.1.5 Physical layer security

By eavesdropping on lower layer sensing signals (reflections from Rx signals), adversaries may create impression of surroundings/target objects. Anomaly/misbehaviour detection systems [HWD+18], similar to other radar systems, could be explored for detecting and protecting against jamming in physical environment. In addition, further studies could investigate methods to protect against physical layer attacks such as adversaries creating false objects or ghosting real objects in the physical environment. Integrity protection algorithm for sensing signals may protect against such tampering. Attestation mechanisms may be necessary to verify the integrity of entities at UE and gNB collecting and producing data.

5.3.1.6 UE sensing security

In addition to implementing above controls related to authorisation, logging and sensing data security, UE should consider implementing transparency solutions and network could utilize such solutions to notify UE owners/subscribers when a sensing session has started on the UE and further inform about the type of data transmitted, duration and UE resources used in sensing.

5.3.2 Privacy controls

The privacy controls in JCAS system should ensure the protection of the PII in the sensing data during collection, use, storage, processing, retention, and deletion. Figure 5-10 represents a privacy-preserving framework for JCAS systems by illustrating key network components and where specific privacy controls can be implemented. The figure divides the system into three main blocks: UE, gNB, and the Core Network. The UE and gNB include sensing functions similar to those in the core network, not only the SCF but also the Sensing Processing Function (SPF). These are designated as UE-SCF and UE-SPF for the UE, and gNB-SCF and gNB-SPF for the gNB. The Core Network includes the SCF and SPF.

Figure 5-10 Privacy-preserving JCAS framework

Data minimization and anonymization techniques like joint obfuscation, differential privacy, k-anonymization, data redaction, etc. can be applicable to the SPF while processing the sensing data to protect the PII in sensing data while processing and disclosing the results. These privacy controls can also be applied at the hardware-level to ensure the sensing data collected already privacy-preserved. Beamforming capabilities allow selective coverage and exclusion zones by adjusting beam angles and null steering, which creates low-gain areas while preventing detection in private spaces. Adaptive beam narrowing and dynamic adjustment enable focused sensing on high-priority zones, such as entry points, while reducing coverage of unnecessary areas. Adjustable bandwidth and frequency allocation further help control sensing resolution. For instance, narrowing bandwidth lowers detail, and switching to lower frequency bands enables broader but less precise sensing coverage. Transmission power control adjusts sensing range and detail by modulating power levels, with lower power focusing on closer objects and higher power for precise sensing nearby. Pulse duration and subcarrier modulation also impact resolution that shorter pulses or narrower subcarrier spacing provide finer detail, while longer pulses or wider spacing reduce data volume. Configuring sensing sessions with dynamic time and

frequency division allocates resources between sensing and communication, allowing for adaptable resolution by adjusting frame duration and subcarrier allocation based on situational requirements.

Pseudonymization techniques substitute identifiable data with pseudonyms, enabling data linkage across sessions without directly revealing identities. In the 5G system, the Subscription Concealed Identifier acts as a pseudonym to protect the Subscription Permanent Identifier of users. In JCAS, however, sensitive PII must also be safeguarded; therefore, pseudonymization should be applied to the sensing data at the SPF to protect the PII of sensing targets as well as the entities involved in data collection and processing. Additionally, JCAS systems with distributed sensing processing across UEs and gNBs, privacy-preserving computation techniques, such as secure multi-party computation, homomorphic encryption, and federated learning (FL) can also be applied at the SPF to protect the PII during transfer and processing of sensing data.

5.3.2.1 Consent and Transparency

Besides security and privacy controls which prevent unauthorized access to sensing data and the PII, other important controls in the privacy domain are related to consent and transparency. In many JCAS use cases, data minimization techniques play a crucial role in consent-aware sensing. For instance, the sensing unit's hardware can be configured pre-sensing, or specific data can be filtered post-sensing, to exclude geographical areas where consent for data collection has not been granted. In public spaces, obtaining consent from individuals within the sensing area presents a significant challenge. In contrast, in private spaces typically owned by an individual, consent may be obtained from the property owner. However, determining the appropriate methods for obtaining consent and ensuring its enforcement remains a complex issue.

Transparency means that a human sensing target receives information addressing key questions, such as: Who is collecting which sensing data and for what purposes? How long will the data be stored? With whom will the data be shared? Providing such transparency is a legal requirement, as outlined in regulations like the General Data Protection Regulation GDPR [EU16]. Furthermore, it is important to note that other legal bases may also apply depending on the context, such as compliance with legal obligations, the protection of vital interests, or the performance of a contract. In the case of JCAS, the 6G system shall provide the transparency information. Thereby different means of making the transparency information accessible shall be implemented. On the one hand each gNB should broadcast transparency information while sensing is going on. This information can be made available to UEs e.g., with the help of a smartphone app. On the other hand, there should be a central platform (e.g., a website) that allows, for instance, bystanders (e.g., individuals without a smartphone) to look up past sensing activities and, if available, information about planned future sensing activities.

5.4 Integration patterns for trustworthy AI

This section provides further evaluation of the framework introduced in [HEX224-D24] for security and privacy in FL and then discusses how to utilize it in the 6G system. That framework is called FASIL (A challenge-based FrAmework for Secure and prIvacy-preserving federated Learning) in [HEX2-KPK+24]. In addition to the proposed framework, this section summarizes other enablers and observations about the potential use of such enablers in the 6G system. How to use explainable AI (XAI) for robustness of AI/ML in 6G system is also discussed.

5.4.1 Further evaluation of the FASIL framework

The FASIL framework introduced in [HEX2-KPK+24] enhances privacy in FL by preventing information leakage about the training data of the clients from the individual local model updates and simultaneously allows the FL server to perform security attack detection to prevent poisoning attacks. This is achieved by allowing the server to access only some parts of the individual local model updates. New experiments were performed by using the Tensorflow library and the homomorphic encryption scheme from Cheon-Kim-Kim-Song (CKKS) in [CKK+17] to evaluate the success of the framework and to evaluate concrete computation and communication performance on top of FL with secure aggregation. For the privacy attack related experiments Cifar-100 dataset was used while for the security attack related experiment and performance evaluations Edge-Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) dataset was used, respectively. Table 5-3 presents resistance to the deep leakage from gradients privacy attack [ZLH19] for different number of neural network layers accessible by the FL server where the neural network consists of 10 layers. For the evaluation metric, mean squared error is selected. Less error implies more success in terms of privacy attack.

Table 5-3 Evaluation of resistance to the deep leakage from gradients privacy attack

Setup	Attack success metric
Secure Aggregation FL	0.1013
FASIL with 0/10 opened layer	0.1013
FASIL with 1/10 opened layer	0.0975
FASIL with 2/10 opened layer	0.0929
FASIL with 3/10 opened layer	0.0881
FASIL with 4/10 opened layer	0.0844
FASIL with 5/10 opened layer	0.0708
FASIL with 6/10 opened layer	0.0428
FASIL with 7/10 opened layer	0.0213
FASIL with 8/10 opened layer	0.0139
FASIL with 9/10 opened layer	0.0116
FASIL with 10/10 opened layer	0.0014
Plain FL	0.0014

To evaluate the resistance against the training data poisoning attacks, a label flipping attack was conducted with the edge-IIot dataset. For the experiment, a malicious client who flips local dataset's labels was introduced to the FL setup. For detection of the poisoning attacks, sum of absolute pairwise differences between the weight vector of the client and the other clients. In the experiment, client 0 was selected as the malicious one and only one layer of the neural network was revealed to the server. Figure 5-11 presents the pairwise distances of all clients for layers 0 and 2, where the malicious client was correctly identified as client 0 by using the distance for layer 0. According to our experiments, the layers 0, 1, 3, 5, 7, 8, and 9 can be useful for the server to identify the malicious client as client 0. However, the layers 2, 4, and 6 are not sufficient because in our setup these layers represent maxpooling layers failing to contribute meaningfully to the pairwise distance calculation.

Figure 5-11 Pairwise distances of the clients for different layers computed by the server.

To evaluate the concrete performance overhead of the proposed framework, computation cost in terms of seconds and amount of data to be transmitted (in MB) were obtained not only for the proposed framework with the CKKS encryption scheme but also for the plain FL and secure aggregation FL with CKKS scheme. The results are shown in Table 5-4. According to the table the computation overhead of the proposed protocol on top of FL with secure aggregation is negligible and the communication overhead also less than 20%.

Table 5-4 Concrete computation and communication cost and overhead of FASIL

Plain FL		Secure aggregation FL		Proposed protocol	
Comp [s]	Comm [MB]	Comp [s]	Comm [MB]	Comp [s]	Comm [MB]
170.03	6.87	179.35	6.91	182.30	8.09

Details of further evaluation is presented in a scientific paper submitted to the Annals of Telecommunications journal.

5.4.2 On the utilization of FASIL and other enablers in the 6G system

AI/ML is one of the promising tools to be utilized in different components, such as RAN, CN, management layer and exposure layer, of the data driven 6G system. Examples of motivation of utilization of AI/ML can be to increase the management automation level, reduce operational costs, reduce energy consumption, and

increase security level. AI/ML becomes a critical building block in the 6G systems and impacts the SPR of the 6G system because wrong decisions done by the AI/ML will have impact on performance, energy consumption, and security attack detection etc. Since AI/ML means processing of data, privacy aspects will also be available. Thus, SPR of the AI/ML is important for the SPR of the 6G system. It is in general called AI/ML trustworthiness which is a kind of big umbrella including robustness of AI/ML (i.e., being resistant against AI/ML security attacks such as poisoning attacks), privacy and data confidentiality aspects, transparency, and explainability. To increase the utilization of AI/ML, huge amount of diverse data would be preferred, but instead of collecting all the data in one centre, collaborative and distributed AI/ML approaches can be preferred because of some aspects such as performance and privacy aspects.

One of the collaborative ML methods is the FL whose utilization has already been standardized in 3GPP specs. Two main SPR controls in the FL are about prevention against AI/ML security attacks and prevention of sensitive data leakage which can be private data of individuals or sensitive data of corporates/enterprises. From the client perspective, privacy and data confidentiality becomes important because they may not want to expose their private training data with the other clients and the server. From the server perspective, robustness against the AI/ML security attack can be important because the contributors to the AI/ML training can intentionally or unintentionally try to poison the trained ML model. To make the AI/ML training secure against poisoning attacks, the solutions are based on anomaly analysis done by the server on the individual local model updates. To increase the privacy level which means prevention of data leakage about the private training data sets, there are privacy enhancing technologies such as hardware based confidential computing and cryptography-based mechanisms such as homomorphic encryption, secure multi-party computation, secret sharing, zero-knowledge proofs. Each mechanism can have its own pros and cons, so the preferred solution should be decided by considering the properties of the mechanisms and constraints of the AI/ML application area.

Before focusing on solutions, first the SPR requirements need to be identified because the requirements can vary depending on the trust assumptions and trust boundaries. For example, if the server is trusted and it is ok for each client to share their training data with the server, then it may not be necessary to deploy privacy enhancing mechanisms, or if the clients are trusted by the server and if there is an assumption that the training data of the client is valid data then the server may not need to execute security attack detection mechanisms. Thus, each AI/ML application area should be analysed first, and then considering the AI/ML SPR requirements, system constraints and the properties of the mechanisms should be taken into account for the construction of the solution. Since the 6G system will be consisting of different components and since it will be multi-vendor, multi-stakeholder, multi-domain, and multi-tenant environment, it is difficult to identify a solution addressing all the requirements for all the AI/ML application areas in the system. However, a generic framework allowing utilization of different mechanisms can be valuable to address the SPR aspects in AI/ML.

Consequently, a framework called FASIL was introduced in [HEX224-D24] and is further analysed in this document. FASIL is mainly focusing on addressing simultaneously security and privacy aspects in FL which is a challenging problem because when privacy level increased then the server will not be able to perform security attack detection on the individual local model updates. Several approaches are proposed in the literature to address this challenge. One approach is the usage of secret-sharing and two or more non-colluding servers. Some solution constructions of this approach have a good performance, but the main problem is the requirement of having two or more non-colluding servers, which means that if the server collaborate then there will be no prevention against private data leakage. Another approach is based on utilization of zero-knowledge proofs to prove that the clients are not performing poisoning attacks without exposing their private training data, yet this kind of solutions do not perform well in terms of computation because of heavy cryptographic operations. Secure comparison approaches utilize secure multi-party computation techniques so that the clients can prove that their local model updates fulfil some expectations, but again this type of solutions may require heavy cryptographic operations. Finally, anonymizing the local model updates approaches requires a multi-hop communication. Thus, each approach has its own drawbacks, so to have a usable solution for privacy enhanced robust FL mechanism, FASIL has been designed. It is not a concrete solution but a kind of framework allowing utilization of different secure aggregation and partially or fully homomorphic encryption solutions for privacy and also allowing different security attack detection mechanisms. Since it does not require two or more non-colluding servers, does not require multi-hop communication and does not require heavy cryptographic operations, FASIL can be a good candidate to be utilized in the 6G system.

Instead of deploying the framework in the central point covering the whole E2E 6G system, it should be considered utilization of it in different components of the 6G systems independently for each FL usage area. For example, the UEs can be clients and one network element in the RAN or core can be the server, Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) instances in different regulation areas of a big CSP can be clients and a central NWDAF can be the server, application functions outside the CSP domain can be the clients and an NWDAF of the CSP can be the server, or NWDAFs in different slices can be clients and an NWDAF can be the server, BSs can be the client and a network function in the core network can be the server. Similar scenarios can also be generated for the management layer. To summarize, if privacy and security need to be addressed simultaneously, the FASIL framework could fit in many different AI/ML usage scenarios in the 6G systems.

5.4.3 On the utilization of XAI for robustness of AI/ML in the 6G system

Trustworthy AI can be integrated into 6G networks to tackle security issues arising from the increasing number of IoT devices, while also ensuring reliable service. This approach helps to protect sensitive information and improve technological advancement that is both safe and reliable.

For example, advanced monitoring systems known as IDS are essential for detecting anomalous activities in network traffic. However, traditional IDS methods often struggle to differentiate between normal and malicious traffic due to the complex and fast-evolving nature of mobile networks, leading to a high rate of false alarms. On the other hand, ML advancements have improved IDS capabilities to identify anomalies resulting from Distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks. However, while integrating ML methods can enhance DDoS detection, their susceptibility to adversarial attacks could create new vulnerabilities, potentially enabling attackers to bypass defence mechanisms.

This is where Explainable AI (XAI) proves to be especially effective. By incorporating XAI into IDS, the security of 6G networks can be greatly improved through enhanced transparency in AI decision-making processes and also allowing to identify the key features contributing to detected anomalies. In the context of adversarial attacks, XAI can assess how well security systems resist attempts to bypass detection by analysing changes in top important features before and after an attack. This analysis helps to pinpoint specific vulnerabilities and adapt security measures proactively. Furthermore, by adopting a comprehensive strategy which was given in [HEX224-D24] that includes XAI, the system can effectively respond to adversarial attacks with minimal human intervention. This proactive approach not only speeds up response times but also enhances the overall security framework of essential systems.

5.5 Notary service for transparency

The underlying assumption is that a 6G transparency services might inherit from the supply chain integrity, transparency and trust (SCITT) architecture currently defined by the IETF [BDF+24] and the standardization is still work in progress. A potential path towards adoption with a focus on standardization needs is provided as a complete description of the used technologies and concepts is beyond the scope of this document.

5.5.1 Main components of transparency service

In a nutshell a transparency service offers an issuer the possibility to register statements about artefacts in such a way, that others can cryptographically verify the registration of the signed statement in the service. The main components of the transparency service are summarized in Figure 5-12.

Figure 5-12 Component of the transparency service and their relations.

In more detail the main notions of the concept are:

Artefact: The entity about which a statement is made.

Issuer: The entity, who is making the statement about the artefact. Before registration of a statement the issuer signs the statement leading to a signed statement. The signed statement might not include the statement itself, but a hash of the statement and a link to the actual storage of the statement. In this way the recording of the statement and the recording of the registration can be decoupled.

Statement: Any piece of information, which can be made about an artefact, and which should be registered in the transparency service.

Client: The entity registering a signed statement at the transparency service on behalf of the issuer. The client and issuer may be the same entities. The interaction of a client with a SCITT based transparency service is currently defined by IETF [BSG24].

Transparency Service: The main task of the transparency service is the registration of new signed statements. If the transparency service receives a signed statement from a client, the transparency service verifies the formal validity of the statement and adds it to the ledger. Thus, the ledger consists of an ordered sequence of all registered signed statements.

The integrity guarantees of the ledger (append-only, immutability, auditability) are ensured using Merkle binary hash trees [LMS21]. The hashes of registered signed statements are the leaves of the tree. By iteratively calculating the hash of a branch node by hashing the values of its child nodes the hash value of the root node of the tree is calculated, which contains the complete state of the ledger at a certain time.

After having registered a signed statement, the transparency service provides a receipt to the client, which contains a prove that the statement has been added to the ledger. In summary, the proof contains the signed hash value of the root of the Merkle tree, and the hash value of all branch nodes needed to reconstruct the tree root from the hash value of the signed statement [LMS21].

Whether the main purpose of the transparency service is to ensure the integrity of the ledger through maintaining the hash tree, or if the transparency service should also provide as a searchable archive for the registered statements needs to be discussed and depends on the specific requirements of the eco-system.

The transparency service is not implemented by a single node, but by several nodes, which are operating together via a consensus protocol. However, it is not expected that the operation of the transparency service is completely open (like for instance in case of bitcoin), but that nodes of consortium partners act together based on a set of agreed rules.

Relying Parties: Relying parties are the entities consuming the content of the signed statements. With the help of the proof of inclusion in the receipt the relying party can verify independent from the transparency service that the signed statement is part of the ledger.

5.5.2 Relevant SPR use cases

The potential use cases of transparency can be grouped according to the entities generating and consuming the signed statements.

5.5.2.1 *Vendor-to-operator use cases*

Typical supply chain use cases fall into this category. A vendor is registering a signed statement about one of its products. Thus, the vendor takes the role of the issuer and the client. The artefact is the product, e.g., the image of a certain network function, and the statement could be anything characterizing the product, e.g., a software bill of materials. In case of confidential workloads, also artefacts about known reference values used for remote attestation could be part of the registered signed statement.

The operator can use the statements to verify the product and properties of the product. Since the operator can also proof the registration of the statement, the operator can have additional trust that the vendor did not produce a dedicated version only to it. This additional trust through transparency, however, only works, if a larger number of vendors and operators agree on using the same transparency service. On the other hand, possible effects of unintended disclosure of business sensitive information, like roadmaps, through the transparency service need to be considered as well.

5.5.2.2 *Intra-operator use cases*

An operator might want to use a transparency service also for the purpose of logging of information, which is sensitive to the operation of the network. In this context the append-only characteristics and the auditability of the ledger (due to the cryptographic backing with the Merkle binary hash tree) are the distinctive feature from traditional logging systems. An example for usage of transparency services for logging purposes could be the registration of attestation statements. In this case, the attestation server is issuing and registering a statement about the result of a remote attestation pursued by e.g., a booting network function (“artefact”).

The transparency service could also be used by network functions for reporting of configured security policies and all kinds of security relevant incidents. Another application where such an operator internal transparency service might be useful is the tracking of data provenance in complex AI/ML scenarios in which data undergo several different process steps.

Furthermore, also network functions fulfilling monitoring operations, like behavioural analysis, trust evaluation, or intrusion detection could use the transparency service for logging of their observations.

5.5.2.3 *Operator-to-operator use cases*

A transparency service could also be used for inter-operator relationships: detailed use cases still need to be discussed but potential areas include logging the utilization of shared resources (e.g., to log current spectrum utilizations in scenarios with shared or flexibly allocated spectrum resources).

5.5.2.4 *Cross-domain relationships in the cloud continuum*

A transparency service can be used for level-of-trust assessment of cross-domain relationships in cloud continuum scenarios [VOP+24]. In this case, a DSP (e.g., network service provider, cloud service provider, etc.) might register on the transparency service the level-of-trust of its network service regarding a contracted TLA amongst several DSPs to compose a 6G E2E service. The signed statements may be issued by the level-of-trust assessment function of a given DSP that oversees continuously monitoring service assurance and evaluating statements.

Furthermore, transparency services may also support a digital service consumer’s level-of-trust assessment function to verify the fulfilment of a trust agreement when different DSPs participate in an E2E relationship. Each DSP should log the service assurance outcomes of its network service running under its domain to the joint transparency service.

Figure 5-13 Example of a joint Transparency Service to assess LoT in cross-domain DSP relations

Thus, the transparency service supports the verification (through external audits) of statements of a decomposing E2E service coming from multiple services and different DSPs. Such verifications make use of the proof of inclusion in the receipt, so an external auditor can confirm independently from the transparency service, that the signed statement is recorded in the ledger and quantitative metrics fulfil the performance of the TLA. Additionally, the transparency service may also help to digital service consumers to analyse forthcoming trustworthy relationships as the level-of-trust assessment function evaluates previous interactions registered in the transparency service and determines who are the most reliable DSPs to compose a new 6G E2E service [JTG+23]. Figure 5-13 shows the possible position of the transparency service in the architecture for the enablement for cross-domain trust.

5.5.3 Standardization needs

In this section the need for standardization a transparency service for 6G and possible gaps are discussed.

5.5.3.1 Definition of signed statements and receipts

The formal definition of the content of statements, signed statements and receipts is expected to continue and to be finalized in the IETF (see for instance [SBD+24, SDF+24, Bry24]).

The contributors to certain ecosystem, like 6G, might need to review these specifications. To avoid incompatibilities among options in the applicable standards, profiling them according to the specific needs of the ecosystem will be required. This could be done by working groups in the 3GPP or GSMA.

5.5.3.2 Syntax and semantics of statements

The actual content of a statement, i.e., the payload of the signed statement, strongly depends on the use case. There for the definition of syntax of the payload needs to be done by the ecosystem partners, which plan to setup and use the transparency service.

For the 6G ecosystem the corresponding standardization is expected depending on the use case to happen by working groups in the 3GPP or GSMA.

Depending on the use case already existing definitions could be used, for instance those relating to software supply chain management [NTIA21]

5.5.3.3 APIs of transparency services

A very central aspect of the transparency service is the mechanism how clients interact with the transparency service. In the context of a transparency service following the SCITT architecture this API, referred to as SCITT Reference APIs (SCRAPI) is defined by the IETF [BSG24]. Currently only two mandatory endpoints

are defined, i.e., the endpoint for the retrieval of the configuration of the transparency service and the endpoint for the registration of the signed statement.

The SCRAPI API contains a lot of optional APIs. Thus, the ecosystem intending to use a transparency service might profile or, if necessary, extend the SCRAPI. In case of the 6G ecosystem this could be done by the 3GPP. One important design decision in this context will be, if the transparency service stores the signed statements (in addition to merely maintaining the hash tree of the ledger to ensure immutability and auditability) and offers functionality for search and retrieval of signed statement.

5.5.3.4 Identity management

One of the key aspects of the transparency service is the identification of the involved entities.

First, the artefact about which a statement is made needs to be identifiable. The way, the artefact is identified will be typically defined by the same group of stakeholders, who are defining the syntax and semantics of the artefact. Typically, the identifier could be a hash of the digital representation of the image. If for instance, the artefact is a container image, the artefact could be identifiable through the container digest.

Issuers and clients could be identified through binding the public key belonging to a private key owned by the issuer or client to a public key. This binding could be done using well established X.509 Certificates. Alternatively, also distributed identifiers can be used, which are more recently applied in the context of distributed ledger technologies (see [W3C22] for the specification of distributed identifiers). The approach for identifying issuers and clients in the context of 6G networks could be potentially standardized by the 3GPP.

5.5.3.5 Implementation and operation of transparency services

Finally, also the way how a transparency service is technically realized and operated needs to be addressed. A transparency service could be jointly operated by different members of an ecosystem. For instance, operators could jointly run a transparency service with each operator contributing one node to a distributed ledger.

One approach for realizing a transparency service is the utilization of the Confidential Consortium Framework (CCF), which is an open-source solution based on work from Microsoft research, which allows multiple parties to jointly handle confidential data in an auditable way using hash-tree-based ledgers [CCF24]. The CCF includes also mechanism to ensure governance between the stakeholders implementing the joint service. Using a suitable applications running on the CCF, like the scitt-ccf- ledger application [SCL24], a multi-party transparency service can be realized.

Mentioning of the CCF and the scitt-ccf-ledger here should not be regarded as endorsement of these solutions for the realization of the transparency service. The decision how to deploy and operate a joint transparency service is obviously up to the stakeholders. In case of a transparency service for 6G used by the operators the GSMA might be the right forum to agree on the realization of a cross-operator transparency service and the used technologies. However, it is also unlikely that the internals of a transparency service, i.e., the protocols and governance between the nodes, will be standardized outside of a specific software solution.

5.6 External enablers to be considered

To address the complex security, privacy, and resilience challenges of next-generation networks, it is essential to leverage insights and innovations from relevant projects that have tackled similar issues. By considering enablers from these projects, we ensure that our solutions are built upon proven concepts, methodologies, and technologies, accelerating progress and promoting interoperability. These enablers provide valuable components, such as privacy quantification mechanisms, simulation frameworks for security impact analysis, and zero-touch orchestration techniques, which can be adapted and integrated into our approach.

The external projects considered for their significant contributions are:

- *RIGOUROUS Project [SNS-RIG]*: Focuses on Development, Security and Operations (DevSecOps) practices, privacy modelling, and quantification through privacy manifests, enabling continuous privacy evaluation during service updates.
- *HORSE Project [SNS-HOR]*: Introduces a what-if scenario framework using DT to simulate and assess the impact of security countermeasures on network performance.

- *ACROSS Project [SNS-ACR]*: Develops a zero-touch intelligent and secure orchestration framework, integrating Network Digital Twin (NDT) services, AI-based decision-making, and automated security operations to manage 5G and beyond networks effectively.

5.6.1 DevSecOps and enhanced privacy

The RIGOUROUS project [SNS-RIG] addresses privacy modelling and formalization applying data management through a systematic method and accommodates service updates via a control version to maintain a privacy benchmark as the service evolves.

The quantification of service privacy levels uses a declarative, service-specific privacy manifest. This privacy manifest, a statement outlining privacy service definitions, employs predefined metrics and algorithms to assess the service privacy level. The quantification can be customized according to user preferences or regulatory standards and provides a privacy related score. Two sources are considered for this score: developer provided information and automatically assessed information. The first one results from the developer specifically stating the data processing characteristics of the application, including which data is processed, which data is stored and how, and which data is communicated with specific external endpoints on a service cloud. The second source relies on tools that estimate how data is processed/stored, and which is the connectivity graph with external endpoints. As stated, both methods result in a quantified composite score. The privacy quantification component is utilized to re-evaluate the privacy level of the updated service, thereby updating the final metric.

In the design phase, the architecture addresses different parts of the DevSecOps paradigm, including mechanisms for automatic enforcement of security policies defined by administrators, software developers or security operators within the network. accommodates service updates. It establishes a control version to maintain a privacy benchmark as the service evolves. This approach establishes a continuous cycle of privacy testing and monitoring, that can be termed as development, privacy and operations. Privacy quantification and re-quantification ensure ongoing assessment and refinement of the service privacy practices. Privacy quantification considers a set of indicators based on metrics applied to software quality assurance and applicable legislation considering data in transit across multiple jurisdictions.

Privacy manifests are intended to become part of the descriptors composing the network service, i.e., the service description itself, the networking requirements of the service, or the tests that validate its operation from a performance and functional perspective. Privacy information is thus provided before service onboarding, and developers can include their own information in the privacy manifest, to be later processed together with automatically assessed information. This information follows the models described in [TMF63321] definitions, regarding models and dependencies of the different software artifacts composing a service. The service specification is modelled as a service order, following [TMF64121], including also instantiation parameters. Privacy manifests are modelled following [TMF65321], which provides a standardized mechanism for placing a service test with all the necessary test parameters.

To address [NISTZT20] adapted to mobile networks, the architecture is complemented with a zero-trust security and identity management component, performing continuous trust evaluation of network functions and entities, application functions and end-user devices associated to the network. Any network or application function which consumes or provides services, to and from the evaluation target, can subscribe to the service as consumer to get proactive notifications about the trustworthiness of the target. These data can also be utilized by the operator to configure network management functions to isolate and fix security issues (e.g., vulnerabilities) of the evaluated target.

5.6.2 What-if scenarios

The HORSE project [SNS-HOR] has introduced a new concept that works with two core elements in the security control loop the project proposes: the *Sandboxing Environment* (SAN) and the *Intent-Based Interface* (IBI). This concept is the *what-if scenario*, supporting the verification of the impact of any mitigation measure on the performance (and any other relevant characteristics) of the network.

Whenever a series of countermeasures have been identified, the IBI sends a request to the impact analysis DT within the SAN, describing the countermeasures and the relevant KPIs to be evaluated. As an example, let us

consider a DDoS Domain Name System (DNS) attack, where a what-if request would consist of these questions:

- WHAT is the latency in <interface> of DNS client IF we apply a 20 Mbps rate limit in the DNS server.
- WHAT is the bandwidth in <interface> of DNS client IF we block port 53 in the DNS server.

With these definitions, the Impact Analysis DT can work in testing the concrete scenarios proposed by the IBI. Then, the DT will answer those questions by sending the KPIs that were specified on the what-if requests.

The HORSE project is currently working on the data models for these what-if requests, and has already identified the following relevant parameters:

- Type of mitigation action (e.g., FILTER)
- Point of the network where the mitigation action is applied (e. g. eth1 of DNS server)
- Value of the mitigation action (e. g. port 53)
- Point of the network to be measured (e. g. eth1 of DNS client)
- KPI to be measured (e.g., bandwidth)

Finally, the IBI, with the information of the different impacts that the mitigations have on the network, can take the necessary decisions to be later applied to the real infrastructure.

5.6.3 Remediation actions

In terms of remediation actions and based on the work presented in section 6.4 of [HEX224-D23], the ACROSS project [SNS-ACR] has developed and presented its initial framework release to manage the security around network slices through a set of enablers based on the principles of “zero touch intelligent and secure orchestration”, supporting automated, intelligent, secure, and trusted management of 5G and beyond 5G networks, addressing their complexity and dynamic nature.

The ACROSS project is committed to the development of core components within its orchestration framework, including NDT services for generating synthetic data for AI training; AI services comprising training, inference, repository, and data aggregation for dynamic decision-making; zero-touch automation services such as the automation event handler, policy executor, service adaptation, and SLA management API for automated operations; and security and trust services featuring device attestation, secure container migration, and software-defined mechanisms for DoS and DDoS mitigation.

This approach implies relevant advancements in orchestration platform capabilities, emphasizing improvements in automation, intelligence, and security. Robust security features, such as device attestation, secure container migration, and DDoS mitigation, have been incorporated to fortify the platform defence against potential threats. Additionally, the platform enhances operational efficiency by automating complex network management tasks and creates new business opportunities through more reliable and scalable network services.

5.7 Conclusions

Since the task on security, privacy and resilience started with the identification of specific threats and enhanced opportunities for detection and mitigation (what was identified as the *6G security delta*), the team has worked in addressing this security delta and in fulfilling the objectives related to trustworthy networking. The concept of control, providing the different threat detection and mitigation functionalities to be taken into consideration, exposed to any other enablers in the 6G systems and consumed by these other enablers using the most appropriate integration pattern, constituted the base of the analysis of the SPR objectives and shaped the evaluation of the proposed solutions. The team has worked on technologies at different TRLs, rather guided by the 6G security delta mentioned above than by considerations related to technology maturity. This way, the Hexa-X-II security team has followed the commitment to act as a flagship for 6G technologies, identifying ways for future work in consolidating the identified controls and enablers. Among the technologies evaluated in the project, it is worth noting for future work the initial steps on physical layer security techniques, the data-sensitive aspects related to JCAS and the application of AI as a pervasive enabler, and the proposal of a transparent notary service as a base enabler for trustworthiness assessment.

6 Overall 6G system design

6.1 Final Hexa-X-II 6G E2E system blueprint

This section presents an update of the overarching system blueprint, outlining the fundamental functionalities and key interfaces of the 6G system, both internally and externally. This holistic approach of the blueprint serves as the foundation for further detailed exploration of specific system views. These views provide multiple perspectives on radio protocols and flexible topologies, new 6G services and the related exposure framework, multistakeholder aspects in the realization of an E2E 6G system, pervasive functionalities including the AI/ML and data frameworks, pervasive security, privacy and resilience, and migration path from 5G to 6G. By combining a holistic system blueprint with detailed views of specific aspects, this approach ensures a robust and comprehensive design for the 6G system.

6.1.1 Overall system blueprint

Figure 6-1 Final update of the Hexa-X-II 6G E2E system blueprint

An updated version of the Hexa-X-II 6G E2E system blueprint introduced in [HEX224-D23] is presented in Figure 6-1. It reflects the final progress of work on the various individual enablers and how they are interacting in the E2E system. It includes the following updates:

- *The Application Enablement Platform (AEP) layer*, as the main access to the services of the 6G system as a platform, now includes a developer portal, emphasizing the importance of a streamlined developer experience beyond simplified APIs. This portal provides resources like specifications, documentation, Software Development Kits (SDKs), and test environments to facilitate development. Details of the architecture are provided in section 6.1.3.1.
- *The service exposure framework* has been extended to reflect the programmability of the network. Many of the expected 6G services are aiming at providing a programmatic control, or influence over the 6G network capabilities, such as configuring QoS for specific UE. This programmability also applies to the management capabilities, enabling the exposure of management services previously only used internally.
- The CN comprises 6G functions and 5G functions. The previous naming of 6G core NFs might have led to ambiguous interpretation. To clarify, the new naming scheme emphasizes that the core is an evolution of the 5G core.
- *The pervasive functionalities* have been expanded with new aspects:

- M&O: The blueprint now includes an NDT management box, highlighting the role of NDTs in managing and orchestrating the 6G services, in accordance with the recommendations from the M&O framework developed in [HEX225-D65]. The M&O has been expanded to include a federation APIs box, representing the functionalities required for establishing and managing collaboration between different service or resource stakeholders. This APIs highlights one important multi-stakeholder interface. It worths noting that numerous other relationships and interfaces exist within the 6G system, which cannot all be depicted in the figure shown in the blueprint. Therefore, they are illustrated via the multi-stakeholder box surrounding the various layers and domains of the 6G platform. The key concepts of the integration of multi-stakeholders in the 6G system is further expanded in section 6.1.4.
- AI framework: It is now detailed with an AI orchestrator, AI/ML catalogue, and Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) orchestrator. These components work together to manage the lifecycle of AI services, ensuring efficient deployment, optimization, and continuous improvement. A system view focused on AI/ML is provided in section 6.1.5.1.
- Data management framework: Previously known as data framework, it has been renamed as the data management framework to better reflect its scope. It plays a crucial role in ensuring the effective collection, processing, governance and quality of data, which is essential for AI/ML operations. While not explicitly depicted in the blueprint figure due to space constraints, these key functions are integral to the overall architecture. Further details are provided in section 6.1.5.1.
- Security, privacy and resilience: it represents the fundamental pillars related to 6G system trustworthiness. It is now structured around six functional blocks: Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability (CIA) triad; Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting (AAA) mechanisms; Data minimization, consent and transparency to safeguard data privacy and confidentiality; "What-if" environment with NDTs to simulate various scenarios and optimize network resilience; security closed loops to ensure the 6G network is autonomously secure and reliable. These controls are implemented across all the layers of the system, as further detailed in 6.1.5.2.

The 6G E2E system blueprint provides a comprehensive overview of the 6G system. However, due to its high-level nature, it cannot encompass all detailed aspects within a single diagram. To address this, we introduce specific-system views that offer focused perspectives on various aspects of the overall system. These views, which are elaborated in the following sections, complement the E2E system blueprint specifications.

6.1.2 Specific system views on access, devices and flexible topologies

6.1.2.1 RAN specific view of system blueprint

Given the challenges that were faced during 5G due to the Higher Layer Split (HLS), it is conceived that the RAN deployments and LLS options, i.e., HIGH-PHY up to SDAP in the gNB and LOW-PHY and RF in the RU, will be carried over from 5G to 6G. This will be an important component vis-à-vis the smooth migration from 5G to 6G. Additional considerations about security anchoring also play an important role in determining the LLS approach as being more viable. For further information, we refer the reader to section 6.1.6 on Migration as well as section 5.5.2 in [HEX223-D32] and section 2.2.4 in [HEX223-D33].

6.1.2.2 Specific view on new access and flexible topologies

Figure 6-2 provides a specific view of the Network function layer of Figure 6-1, involving the UE, 6G RAN, Transport NFs, and Core NFs. The specific view is focusing on new access and flexible topologies and the interfaces between the different system components.

As shown in Figure 6-2, a UE may be connected to a terrestrial BS and to a satellite [HEX224-D33, HEX225-D35]. The Uu interface will continue being used between the UE and the terrestrial BS. Additionally, the UE-satellite link, also termed as service link [HEX224-D33], may also use the Uu interface. In the case where multiple satellites form multi-hop routes until the ground BS is reached, the inter-satellite links [HEX224-D33] and the feeder link shall be specified. The terrestrial BSs are connected to the CN via the N2/N3 interfaces through the transport network, which may include multiple Software Defined Network (SDN) domains [HEX224-D33].

Figure 6-2 New access and flexible topologies-specific view

Shifting the focus to the Management Node (MgtN)-coordinated subnetworks, there are multiple architectural options [HEX225-D35], including MgtN-Standalone (SA), Base Station – Management Node Dual Connectivity (BS-MgtN DC) and Base Station Standalone (BS-SA) with MgtN support. In each of them, one UE takes the role of a MgtN, which is responsible for the communication within the subnetwork as well as for the coordination with the overlay cellular network. The local UE-MgtN link could use one of various interfaces, such as Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN), Uu, PC5, while the MgtN-BS link would use the Uu interface. As explained in [HEX223-D32, HEX224-D33, HEX225-D35], subnetwork CP and UP shall be defined, so that certain procedures or parts of them may be offloaded from the BS to the MgtN. Such procedures may include RRC procedures, Radio Resource Management (RRM) procedures, as well as Idle mode and connected mode procedures, as stated in Figure 6-2. Still referring to subnetworks, new procedures shall be defined in the CN, as briefly discussed in the annex B.2.2.2 and described in more detail in [6GS24-D42]. These CN processes are related to the mobility management of the subnetwork, to the authentication of the nodes that are part of the subnetwork and to the concept of device groups. Furthermore, the support for Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)-based multi-hop backhaul using Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB) or Proximity Services (ProSe), enables flexible and on-demand network extension in areas with limited infrastructure. IAB and ProSe function as access points and wireless relays, ensure seamless connectivity by forwarding data through multi-hop wireless links to the nearest base station.

As part of multi-connectivity, a UE may be simultaneously connected to a WLAN terminal (WT) via the WLAN interface and to a terrestrial BS via the Uu interface [HEX224-D33, HEX225-D35]. The WT may itself be wirelessly connected to the same or a different terrestrial BS via the Uu interface, essentially enabling two routes between the UE and the cellular network. In the scenarios where two terrestrial BSs are present, these may either be co-located, as in Carrier Aggregation (CA) or be connected to each other via the Xn interface, as in Dual Connectivity (DC). Hexa-X-II proposal, outlined in [HEX224-D35], suggests an improved CA architecture as the sole solution for multi-connectivity in 6G, replacing the DC options.

6.1.2.3 Specific view for radio protocols

The RAN protocol specific view captures the main functionalities develop in the RAN network and in which layer of the radio protocol stack those functionalities will operate. This RAN protocol specific view zooms in on the Application, UE, 6G RAN NF blocks of the network functions layer in the 6G E2E system blueprint illustrated in Figure 6-3.

Figure 6-3 Specific view for 6G radio protocols.

The diagram highlights four key protocol layers that influence the management of the RAN interface/e directly or indirectly, i.e., application layer, Layer 3 (network layer), Layer 2 (data link layer), and Layer 1 (physical layer). Layer 3 is divided into three different subtypes in the figure to represent different bridging protocols such as L3a NAS signalling between the UE and the CN network, L3b RRC between the UE and the 6G RAN node, and L3c between the RAN node and the CN network. Layer 2 in the figure consists of a structure of protocols for CP or UP operation in the radio interface, i.e., SDAP, PDCP, RLC, MAC.

The RAN protocol specific view illustrates part of the RAN related enablers developed in Hexa-X-II, those enablers are building blocks of the radio connection management of the 6G RAN node controls. The representation of the enabler illustrates the protocol layers at which the enabler operates and where Hexa-X-II has focused its research, not precluding additional impacts to other protocol layers or network components. While there are enablers that interact with application layer (e.g., such as mobility management enablers), other enablers are scoped within lower layers of the radio protocol stack (e.g., L2 data recovery mechanisms). More details on those enablers can be found in Chapter 3 and [HEX224-D23].

Among the RAN related enablers, the “Integrated new services” box references the relevance in the UE and 6G RAN node for the support in 6G of services such as Sensing, AI and Compute as a service (SeaaS, AIaaS, and CaaS). Those services will bring new signalling exchanges and operations in the 6G radio interface, among other innovations as illustrated in Figure 6-5 and described in clause 3.3.

Focusing on L1, the diagram represents a few of the operations the UE and the 6G RAN perform to communicate through the radio interface. The holistic radio design framework and enablers consist of many other components not illustrated in the figure, such as channel/parameter estimation, MIMO, resource allocation, etc. More details on the holistic radio design framework can be found in [HEX223-D42], [HEX224-D43] and [HEX225-D45].

Below L1 PHY operation, the transceiver architecture is placed at the UE and 6G RAN. This box is a simplified view of the main areas investigated for 6G transceivers: transceiver architectures for sub-THz frequency bands, hardware nonidealities for the components of the transceiver architecture (e.g., power amplifier, local oscillator, etc.) for those high frequency bands, as described in [HEX224-D53], and lower frequency transceivers (FR1/2/3), as described in [HEX225-D55]. The last block within the device illustrated in the diagram is the system-on-chip (SoC), were for example advanced digital signal processor and AI capabilities will be required for 6G systems. Three components are highlighted in the SoC: Secure and scalable SoC architecture tailored to a microkernel-based OS, digital signal processor and AI capability of 6G SoC, and multi-source energy harvesting for energy neutral devices. More details on those enablers can be found in [HEX224-D53] and [HEX225-D55].

Taking one step back from the focused RAN protocol view this diagram provides, where only one UE and one 6G RAN NF block are represented, there may be different topologies in the access network as shown in Figure 6-2. Those different topologies could include interfaces between RANs or within a RAN such as NTN-TN coexistence, multi-RAT, subnetworks at the UE side, etc. More details on topologies and evolution of the interactions between entities can be found in [HEX224-D33] and [HEX225-D35].

6.1.3 Specific system views on service exposure and new 6G services

6.1.3.1 Service exposure framework

Supporting the exposure of the new 6G services involves capabilities coming from all the layers in the 6G E2E system blueprint. These capabilities are detailed below and highlighted in Figure 6-4 which presented an exposure-centric view of the 6G E2E system blueprint.

Figure 6-4 Exposure centric view of the 6G E2E system blueprint

Support various flavours of the service exposure delivery

The main role of the AEP layer is to provide the applications with an easy access to the 6G capabilities, through APIs that are offered via the service exposure. However, to ensure that the applications can build upon these APIs, their providers need to be supported with additional functionalities (① in Figure 6-4). First, for the mobile network to successfully become an API supplier for aggregator platforms or individual software vendors, it needs to provide them with operation, administration, and management (OAM) services. These services provide the capabilities that are needed for the API consumers to integrate the APIs from the operational and business perspectives. This could be for instance discovering the available APIs, ordering access, or monitoring the delivery. Second, the network further needs to support the developer of the application in its task of integrating the APIs. Beyond simplifying the APIs themselves, the developer experience also needs to be improved by providing a developer portal containing all the resources needed during the development: e.g., specifications, documentations, SDK, test environment (e.g., sandbox).

As 6G networks will provide diverse capabilities, the service exposure framework needs to be flexible enough to support the way each of them need be exposed. Looking at the application layer, an application client in the UE, or server on the internet, can consume the service exposure through out-of-band as well as in-band channels. Out-of-band APIs can either be consumed over-the-top (② in Figure 6-4), e.g., Representational State Transfer (REST) API available over the internet, or through the user-network interface (③ in Figure 6-4), e.g., via interfaces offered on the UE by the operating system or modem. As for in-band, the capabilities are made available by the transport protocol and accessible both by the application at the endpoints or by the intermediary nodes in the mobile network. This includes for instance the mobile network signalling congestion to the application layer through explicit congestion notification marking [ED21] or providing “throughput advice” to the application. Each of these options comes with its own set of requirements that the service exposure framework needs to comply with. This could be for instance the protocols to use, the technical capabilities available at the consumers, or how trusted they are.

Enabling the exposure of new 6G services

Looking at the details of the new 6G service types, it is relevant to highlight two aspects of the services that generate some requirements on the various layers of the 6G system for their exposure. First, the technical delivery of the API. While simple REST APIs are sufficient for many services, some may have higher requirements (e.g., in terms of throughput or latency) that would need to be supported by the service exposure framework. For instance, a sensing service may require supporting the delivery of a large stream of spatial data with low latency [HEX225-D35]. The second aspect to highlight concerns the integration of the API with the

underlying network capabilities. Many of the APIs expected to be exposed in 6G are aiming at providing a programmatic way to manage, or influence, the services offered by the 6G system. For instance, providing an API that allows to configure the desired quality of service for the connectivity service of a particular UE. Such functionalities rely on the programmability of underlying capabilities of the 6G system. Introducing more programmability can lead to new requirements on the management capabilities exposure framework (④ in Figure 6-4) to enable the exposure of management services that were previously only internally consumed. This could be, for instance, additional requirements in term of automation, scalability, or security.

Another aspect that needs to be facilitated by the management capabilities exposure framework is the creation of multi-domain services. That is, services that are built by composing capabilities coming from multiple domains (⑤ in Figure 6-4). For instance, the realization of a quality on demand service requires capabilities from the RAN, CN and operation support systems to allow for the configuration of the connectivity as well as the monitoring of its fulfilment. To enable the implementation of such multi-domain APIs, the service exposure framework needs to facilitate the integration of services coming from multiple domains and the AEP layer needs to provide the tools and services needed to compose them, e.g., workflow engine or information translation service.

Finally, the AEP layer also needs to facilitate the implementation of each API by providing common functionalities that help solve the challenges stemming from its external, and commercial, exposure. These challenges include concerns related to monetization (e.g., charging), authorization, and legislation compliance (e.g., privacy). The AEP layer could for instance offer a set of common functions that could be leveraged in the realization of the APIs. This could be based on the CAPIF Core Function, defined in the 3GPP for Northbound APIs, that already defines services that can be used to solve some of the above-mentioned challenges.

6.1.3.2 New 6G services – integrated services view

Figure 6-5 Integrated services view

6G is foreseen to provide new services [HX225-D35] including the followings:

- *Sensing as a Service (SeaaS)*: provides sensing results and data to a SeaaS external or internal consumer. The sensing results could be for instance the location of a given device, or the device identification. The sensing data could be either raw data provided by sensors or some abstracted or aggregated forms of those. The SeaaS also provides the joint optimization of communication and sensing resources for meeting a JCAS service (e.g., sensing-assisted resilient and secured communications).
- *AI as a Service (AIaaS)*: provides AI inferring results and AI models to an external or internal AIaaS consumer. As opposed to SeaaS, AI data are not foreseen to be provided within the AIaaS. Please refer to full AI/ML view in section 6.1.5.1.

- *Compute as a Service (CaaS)*: provides compute and storage resources to an external or internal CaaS consumer. The CaaS may also provide optimal placement of application (or generally processing) modules optimizing E2E communication and compute metrics (e.g., E2E communication and processing latency). Compute offload is a specific case of CaaS where there is a requirement for a protocol allowing the UE to request computing offloading in addition to the offering of compute and storage resources. This protocol is proposed to be implemented at the AEP layer in Hexa-X-II (see point 3) below).

Figure 6-5 illustrates a specific view of the E2E 6G system blueprint which integrates the new services, focusing on how the MNO could provide new services to the application layer and how different services could take benefits from each other internally. Details services offered at each layer are described in [HX225-D35].

1) Infrastructure layer

At this layer, one can find different resources especially the following:

- Sensing resources (e.g., sensors), sensing radio resources, etc; and dedicated (i.e., statically or manually configured) compute and storage resources for sensing (e.g., for processing sensing data).
- Dedicated (i.e., statically or manually configured) compute and storage resources for AI such as the ones used for training and inference operations.
- Compute (e.g., CPU, or more specialized graphics and neural processing units, GPUs/NPUs) and storage resources to be dynamically provided via the CaaS service APIs. This includes ‘In-Network’ compute and storage resources. ‘In-Network’ means the resources are owned and orchestrated by the MNO, as part of the MNO-owned Data Networks (DN).

2) Network function layer

In the following, network functions are described with respect to their impacts in various segments (UE, RAN, CN and DN).

2.1) UE

It contains Sensing Unit (SU) allowing the UE to participate into sensing operations as per commands or policies set by the network. The SU on the UE is controlled by the Sensing Management Function (SeMF) via the CP (see description on SeMF in the ‘Core Network’ section below). It may provide data to the network as part of the AIaaS in case the user agrees to do so (i.e., participates to the AI data bus). Such data could be for instance mobility patterns, traffics patterns, etc. The UE provides sensing and AI data to the network using an appropriate UP or using a new Data Plane (DP) as introduced by [HX225-D35].

2.2) RAN

It contains SU allowing the RAN to participate into sensing operations as per commands or policies set by the 6G Core network. Possibly, it may deploy some local Sensing Processing Functions (SPFs). In this case, there is a need for local edge computing resources. These compute resources may be statically configured by the management, or they could be dynamically allocated by CaaS as internal service provider via the Service-Based Architecture (SBA). The SPFs are connected to SUs via the User Plane. This has not been shown in the figure as it is an optional and implementation-specific feature. It participates into the AI data and model bus which is an illustrative deployment for AI data and AI model internal communication. For instance, the RAN could use such bus to provide data such as RAN radio resource consumption history to data analytics functionalities in the CN (e.g., NWDAF) or/and AI models such as AI model trained on RAN local data. But it could also consume via the same bus AI data (e.g., application traffics history provided by the CN) or/and AI models from the AI data and model bus (e.g., AI models provided by the CN).

2.3) Core Network

Each of the new services has a dedicated CN function responsible for aggregating, exposing and providing the related services. Additionally, those dedicated CN functions have direct interfaces to the infrastructure layer for managing their resources (sensing resources, computing resources, or storage resources), as illustrated with solid lines in Figure 6-5.

For SeaaS, the associated core network function is the SeMF. A dedicated pool of compute and storage resources could statically be allocated (e.g., via OAM) to such functions, but they could also use compute and storage resources dynamically allocated by the CaaS (e.g., via SBA). In the latter case, statistical multiplexing and sharing amongst different type of functions allow for optimizing the utilization of compute and storage resources. SeMF is connected to SUs via the CP. Eventually, the SeMF provides joint optimization of resources (e.g., UE radio resources for sensing versus UE radio resources for communication) for JCAS services such as sensing-assisted resilient and secured communications.

For CaaS, there is no new CN functionality, instead, the proposal is that the Compute Management Function (CMF) is located in the DN (see below). For MNO's owned DN, the CMF is a trusted function and could be directly connected to the CN (e.g., via the SBA) and could be considered in this case as part of the CN.

For AIaaS, the associated core network function is the AI as a Service Function (AIaaSF). The discussion regarding the use of static (e.g., dedicated via OAM) versus dynamic (e.g., via CaaS) allocation of compute and storage resources performed for SeMF can also apply here.

2.4) Data Networks

DN via the CMF bring compute resources to the system via the CaaS. These DNs could be owned by the MNO (i.e., 'in-network' compute and storage resources) or alternatively could be provided by an external computing service provider such as a hyper-scaler. The DN is represented by the CMF at the control plane level. The latter can expose compute resources to the 6G system similarly to an internal infrastructure layer and/or can consume communication service similarly to an application function. We could distinguish two cases:

In the first case, the DN belongs to another organization than the MNO. In this case, the CMF is considered by the CN as untrusted. The CMF should connect to the CN via an exposure layer functionality which implements some authentication and authorization framework (e.g., Network Exposure Function, NEF). The DN (e.g., edge computing service provider) could offer compute resources to the MNO. In this case (① in Figure 6-5), the CMF (DN) behaves similarly to an Infrastructure Layer component (i.e., southbound to the network Function Layer) and exposes compute resources to the CN (MNO). Alternatively, the CMF (DN) could consume communication services offered by the CN via the exposure layer similarly as an application function (② in Figure 6-5).

In the second case, the DN belongs to the MNO (i.e., 'in-network' compute and storage resources). In this case, the CMF is trusted and could be directly connected to the internal exposure framework such as SBA. CMF offers CaaS services directly via the system CP – e.g., internal service bus. It can also consume other services such as AIaaS via the same CP.

3) Application enablement platform layer

For processing offload situations where the application (e.g., XR) running on the UE requests for offloading some processing onto some compute resources (e.g., edge computing), the CaaS could be provided at the AEP Layer. In this case, the UE represented by the Offloading Node (ON) is the CaaS consumer and the DN represented by the Compute Controlling Node (CCN) is the CaaS provider.

The CCN relies on the CMF to control 'in-network' compute and storage resources deployed at the DN. It is also responsible for interfacing with the 6G system to establish and to configure the appropriate communication path from the UE (or more precisely from the application client running on the UE) to the application server instantiated and configured by the CCN on the DN.

4) Pervasive functionalities

We simply duplicate here the AI/ML framework and data management framework from Figure 6-7. The security and privacy aspects are now represented by the more specific 'SeaaS, CaaS, AIaaS Security & Privacy' box.

5) Interactions between new services

Each of the previous described news services, can expose its service offers both internally to internal consumers and externally to external customers (e.g., Application Function). In the former case, the service-related functions (e.g., SeMF, CMF) could be connected to an internal exposure framework such as SBA. In

the latter case, the external customers are often residing out of the operator network. These customers need to go through some additional exposure functionalities such as NEF or CAPIF. Please refer to section 6.1.3.1 for further information on the exposure framework.

There may be numerous internal/external interactions between the news services as summarized in Table 6-1.

Table 6-1 lists non-exhaustive possible interactions between the new services

Service provider \ Service consumer	SeaaS		CaaS		AIaaS	
	Results	Data	Compute	Processing placement	Inference results	Models
SeaaS			X	X	X	X
CaaS					X	X
AIaaS	X	X	X	X		

6.1.4 Specific system view on multi-stakeholder support

The 6G ecosystem detailed in [HEX223-D11], [HEX223-D12] and [HEX225-D1.4] encompasses a multitude of role-stakeholder relationships, considered in [HX224-D63] and [HX223-D22]. These relationships, outlined in section 4.1, involve TechCo with DSP, COP, and resource provider roles, alongside various digital service customers (B2B, ASP, aggregator). Multi-stakeholder scenarios arise when an E2E construct spans distinct administrative domains, particularly relevant in the 6G cloud network continuum. Scenarios of interest cover E2E constructs at both resource and service levels. For instance, interactions between multiple DSPs to offer digital services to customers are important as discussed in Chapter 4. Similarly, the collaboration between capability operators and diverse resource providers (network, cloud, AI, applications) is essential for the effective M&O of E2E services [HEX225-D65]. Furthermore, the integration of resources provided by vertical industries (acting as both infrastructure providers and DSCs) and extreme-edge resources belonging to end-users (also acting as infrastructure providers) is essential for the aggregation of heterogeneous resources into a network cloud continuum [HX225-D35].

Fundamental concepts underpinning this ecosystem include controllable capability exposure, where M&O capabilities are offered as services accessible via APIs with access and security controls. A federation model enables the aggregation of resources and services across different administrative domains, employing either peer-to-peer or broker-based approaches. A single federation interface can suffice, provided its primitives and data model are adaptable to the needs of diverse federation partners. Intent APIs for service APIs allow the same intent APIs to be used on NBI or east/west bound interface for service requests from service customers.

The multi-stakeholder specific view of the system blueprint depicted in Figure 6-6 elaborates on these concepts, illustrating entities (blue boxes) for intent-based digital service managers, (E2E) service orchestrations, and resource managers, each exposing APIs for ordering, managing, and orchestrating services or resources. These entities also support federation functionality at the resource and service levels, with dedicated functionality embedded in the intent manager for agreements on business/product sharing between partners. At the infrastructure layer, broader resource sharing via federation includes network, cloud, and AI resources with federation APIs for establishment and lifecycle management, including resource sharing agreements. Federations can be established in peer-to-peer mode or through a resource broker acting as a central point for partner interactions. This allows for unified resource exposure to upper-layer service orchestration via cloud continuum management APIs. At the network layer, different service operators can federate to offer network services and beyond communications services (e.g., AIaaS, SeaaS, CaaS), extending beyond the 5G federation designed for cloud services. The intent-based digital service manager exposes services to 6G system consumers (application developers, aggregators, verticals, etc.) and handles federation functionality at the business/product level between partners. Once a federation is established, the same service intent APIs are used to access and manage partner services. Business-level communication is facilitated by a common controllable exposure framework between digital service providers. Similarly, at the service

orchestration and resource management levels, a dedicated controllable exposure framework facilitates exchange between entities.

Figure 6-6 Multi-stakeholder view of the system blueprint

6.1.5 Specific system views on pervasive functionalities

6.1.5.1 Architecture supporting AI/ML based functionalities

The simplified architecture is structured into distinct layers, each playing a crucial role in enabling AI/ML functionalities within 6G (next generation) networks. In Figure 6-7 AI/ML specific view of 6G blueprint architecture, which is delivered in [HEX225-D35], is demonstrated.

Figure 6-7 AI/ML specific view of 6G blueprint architecture

The proposed architecture supports a sequence of operations and data exchanges between various layers. In particular, different components interact to ensure that AI/ML processes are seamlessly integrated into network operations. The process begins at the application layer, where end-user applications or enterprise services initiate requests for specific resources or capabilities, extending beyond traditional network resources to include novel RAN services such as CaaS and AIaaS. These applications can range from communication services

and media streaming to advanced industrial automation or AI-driven analytics tools. The service exposure interface plays a pivotal role at this stage by providing standardized APIs and aggregation services tailored for AI functionalities and capabilities. The exposure mechanism streamline access to AI-driven features such as model inference, training orchestration, and data processing, which enable applications to harness advanced AI capabilities without requiring deep integration into the network's core infrastructure.

Once a service request is generated, it traverses the AEP Layer, which acts as a mediator between applications and network functions. This layer ensures that service requests are enriched with AI-driven context, properly formatted, authenticated, and routed to the appropriate AI function for training, inference or testing (possibly integrated with NFs in the network functions layer). It leverages AI capabilities to provide advanced tools for service orchestration and aggregation, translating high-level application requirements into specific network commands while optimizing for dynamic network conditions and resource availability.

Service requests are processed within the network functions layer, encompassing 6G RAN NFs, transport NFs, and 5G/6G core NFs. RAN may utilize AI to manage wireless access, optimize connectivity, and predictively allocate resources to ensure seamless communication between UEs and the network. Transport network functions employ AI algorithms to enhance data routing, transmission efficiency, and fault prediction. Core NFs integrate AI-driven mechanisms for e.g., mobility management, session management, and intelligent data routing, enabling adaptive and context-aware service delivery across the network. The AI-driven air interface is part of the access within the infrastructure layer and is a radio air interface for communication and/or sensing, where AI-based methods replace one or more functionalities in the physical and MAC layers across the transmitter and/or receiver [HEX225-D45]. The innovative solutions that leverage AI to refine air interface design including learning for waveform, modulation, and coding [HEX2-KHH23], AI-Based CSI acquisition, AI-Enhanced MIMO transmissions, and AI solutions for hardware impairments compensation [FHS23]. The integration of AI-driven air interfaces into radio access networks requires new radio procedures, protocols, and signalling mechanisms to enable effective and efficient operation as outlined in Section 3.2.3.

The integration of AI/ML within the architecture is pivotal for ensuring intelligent, adaptive, and efficient network operations. At the core of this integration is a unified AI/ML/data framework, designed to support diverse use cases across the entire network ecosystem. This comprehensive suite of tools and components enables advanced machine learning workflows, ensuring seamless adaptability and scalability. The framework comprises three key elements: the AI orchestrator, the AI/ML Catalogue, and the MLOps Orchestrator.

A clear identification and definition of AI capabilities to be offered as services are essential to position the AI/ML framework depicted in Figure 6-7 as a critical asset in the 6G network and service architecture. While the overarching goal is to establish a data-driven architecture with native and in-network AI capabilities, adopting an AIaaS approach enables the provision of customized AI services to various consumers across both the application and the 6G M&O layers. Unlike generic AI services, which may operate independently of network-specific contexts, the AI services discussed here are tailored for integration within the 6G ecosystem. These services leverage network-native features to optimize performance, scalability, and reliability while addressing the unique demands of telecom environments. The proposed approach streamlines access to and consumption of these AI functionalities through standardized exposure APIs, enabling consumers such as vertical players or application providers, who may lack advanced AI expertise or infrastructure, to benefit from AI-enabled services. The targeted AI services to be exposed include capabilities specific to telecom networks, such as AI/ML model management, training, validation, testing, emulation, deployment, inference, and monitoring. These services are designed not only to provide core AI functionalities but also to align with the dynamic, high-performance requirements of 6G networks, setting them apart from traditional AI services.

The AI orchestrator manages the deployment, execution, and lifecycle of AI services, ensuring tasks like real-time network performance optimization for use cases such as video streaming quality enhancement or latency reduction in autonomous vehicle communication, fault detection, predictive maintenance, and resource allocation are seamlessly orchestrated across the network. It dynamically selects AI models, deploys them to relevant nodes, and coordinates their execution in near real-time. By monitoring network conditions and application needs, the AI orchestrator adaptively allocates resources to optimize both the performance of the AI system in achieving its specific goals and the overall performance of the network and applications. It also delivers AI/ML services, including training, inference, and testing, via the AIaaSF, integrating them into network functions or applications and exposing them to the Application Layer through interfaces like Common

API Framework (CAPIF). AIaaS is not a standalone network function but an exposure framework integrated into existing network functions to standardize and streamline AI service access. The Orchestrator selects the most suitable models based on specific requests to ensure optimal performance. It works in conjunction with the M&O functional block, complementing its capabilities rather than replacing it, particularly when AI models are integrated into network functions.

The AI/ML catalogue serves as a repository of pre-trained AI services and models, algorithms, and associated metadata. It includes models tailored for different network functions and use cases, such as anomaly detection, QoS prediction, and energy efficiency optimization. These models can be developed in-house or sourced from 3P providers, offering flexibility and scalability. The catalogue hosts different types of “as-a-service” functions, ready to be deployed and consumed, as shown in Figure 6-7, including the AIaaS, the Data Function (DataF), and the MLOps Function (MLOpsF). The AIaaS block provides standardized interfaces for exposing and accessing AI/ML models as services, enabling seamless integration into network functions and applications. The DataF block manages data preprocessing, storage, and sharing, ensuring that training and inference processes are supported with high-quality data while maintaining privacy and security. The MLOpsF block oversees the lifecycle of AI models, including training, validation, deployment, monitoring and streamlining operations for continuous improvement and reliable performance. Moreover, the catalogue supports model versioning, enabling the network to leverage the latest advancements in AI technology. Additionally, it facilitates interoperability by providing standardized interfaces for integrating models into different network environments and ensures that AI solutions can be deployed across diverse network ecosystems.

The MLOps orchestrator is essential for managing the end-to-end lifecycle of AI/ML models. It handles critical tasks such as continuous monitoring, performance evaluation, retraining, and version control, ensuring that deployed models remain effective over time. While the AI orchestrator is responsible for model deployment to relevant network elements, the MLOps orchestrator focuses on ongoing lifecycle management, including model retraining and adaptation over time. One of the key challenges in deploying AI in network environments is ensuring that models remain accurate and relevant over time, especially as network conditions and user behaviours evolve. The MLOps orchestrator implements automated pipelines for retraining and updating models based on performance metrics, addressing challenges of model adaptation over time. Operating in a cloud-native or virtualized environment, the MLOps orchestrator interacts with AIaaS to support both network and application-related AI services, orchestrating essential MLOps workflows for effective model lifecycle management without directly handling model deployment or exposing capabilities via APIs.

Furthermore, the AI/ML integration extends beyond individual network functions to encompass cross-layer optimization. By leveraging data from multiple layers—such as the RAN, transport, and core networks—the AI framework can generate holistic insights that improve overall network performance. For example, AI models can analyse traffic patterns across different network segments to predict congestion and dynamically allocate resources to mitigate it. Similarly, predictive maintenance models can analyse equipment performance data to identify potential faults before they occur, reducing downtime and maintenance costs. These capabilities enable a proactive approach to network management.

The data management framework ensures effective collection, processing, and governance of data, which is essential for AI/ML operations. It handles data collection from various network sources, including UE, RAN, transport, core network functions, and applications, covering performance metrics, traffic, user behaviour, and environmental data. To protect sensitive information, the framework uses encryption, anonymization, and differential privacy techniques. It aggregates, normalizes, and stores data in centralized or distributed data lakes for AI model access. Additionally, it supports near real-time data streaming, enabling AI models to make context-aware decisions. The data management framework executes all DataF, managing data collection, distribution, and storage across network layers, ensuring that AIaaS and MLOpsF have the necessary data for tasks like inference, training, and performance monitoring.

A key aspect of the data management framework is its compliance with regulatory requirements. With increasing scrutiny on privacy and security, especially in the context of telecommunications, the framework ensures that all data handling processes adhere to relevant regulations such as the GDPR. This includes maintaining audit trails, implementing access controls, and ensuring that data is processed in accordance with user consent. By embedding these compliance mechanisms into the Data Management Framework, the

architecture ensures that AI/ML operations are not only effective but also trustworthy and ethically sound. The framework also facilitates data governance and ensures that data quality is maintained throughout its lifecycle.

Once the AI/ML processes have been executed and the necessary optimizations are made, the outcomes are fed back into the Network Functions Layer and then propagated up to the application layer. This feedback loop ensures that the service request is fulfilled with optimal performance, providing enhanced capabilities such as reduced latency, improved throughput, or dynamic resource allocation. The applications receive near real-time insights and enhanced network performance.

Use Case: Failure prediction in 5G/6G core.

Figure 6-8 Processes of failure prediction in 5G/6G core.

The use case we analysed is shown in Figure 6-8. Figure 6-8a on the left illustrates the process of failure prediction using ML applied to collected raw data, which is then organized into a dataset in CSV file format. Raw data is gathered through the DataF, processed, and stored using Data Operations (DataOps). These datasets can be subsequently transferred to the AI/ML Framework. AI/MLOps orchestrators streamline the process of developing, deploying, and monitoring ML models, as shown in Figure 6-8a.

Figure 6-8b on the right depicts the process of integrating the ML model with AIaaSF. In this workflow, trained models can be transferred via Service Exposure to AIaaSF, which integrates with the 5G or 6G Core. The ML model deployed through AIaaSF provides failure predictions to M&O, enabling proactive maintenance of the 5G/6G Core.

6.1.5.2 Architecture supporting security, privacy and resiliency functionalities

The general problem of addressing 6G system trustworthiness and incorporating it in E2E design was addressed by first identifying three fundamental dimensions of the problem: Security, privacy and resilience, and this is why we generically refer to issues regarding these dimensions by the SPR acronym. From this starting point, focus was put on the 6G delta in what relates to SPR as explained in Chapter 5, to address changes in the threat surface and the mitigation strategies. The research on threats and mitigations has been completed with an analysis of how the awareness on SPR requirements and applicable technologies can be incorporated into the 6G E2E system design. Furthermore, the essential pervasiveness implied by SPR issues led to the use of the concept of *control*, as a specific kind of enabler, deeply integrated with other functionalities associated with individual enablers, and providing support and being supported via different interface kinds to and by the combination of other enablers.

As a first pillar in this analysis, a classification of the SPR features has been produced, associating them with the three SPR dimensions. In addition, the analysis of the integration with the other enablers identified in the project, constitutes the second essential pillar of the SPR view of the 6G system blueprint. According to the feature classification and the connection with the enablers identified in the project, a mapping of the different feature classes has been analysed, including them as part of the pervasive functionalities in the E2E system blueprint. Figure 6-9 both illustrates the positioning of the SPR functionalities in the E2E system blueprint and the classification of the SPR features and their mapping to SPR dimensions (zoom on the Figure 6-9).

Figure 6-9 SPR features within the E2E system blueprint

6.1.5.2.1 A classification of features related to security, privacy and resilience

In parallel to the identification of threats and potential mitigations related to technology evolution associated to this 6G delta, the mapping onto a general E2E system blueprint requires the consideration of the different SPR features and how they relate with the general SPR dimensions. The analysis of these features and their application to next-generation mobile networks can be structured around six functional blocks, as depicted in the zoom part of Figure 6-9, mapped onto the different SPR dimensions.

There are three specific feature classes fundamentally associated to the Security dimension, and constituting the foundations of highly pervasive security controls:

- The CIA triad, essentially supported by cryptographic mechanisms and the integration of redundancy mechanisms. Both supporting technologies require specific considerations related to the evolution to quantum-safe crypto and the possibilities offered by cloud-native architectural choices.
- The AAA, connected with different aspects of identity. The challenge for the 6G system lies fundamentally on how to deal with non-human identities, and the implications of addressing the evolution of the CIA triad above.
- The use of closed-loop automation for defining and enforcing policies. Beyond the pervasiveness of AI, with these closed loops becoming a paradigm of other enablers supporting SPR features, aspects related to dynamic monitoring and accurate data applied for decisions become essential.

As shown in the diagram, there are two specific aspects in the CIA triad, confidentiality and availability, directly connected to the privacy and resilience dimensions, respectively. The obvious connection of closed-loop automation to the resilience dimension is also shown in Figure 6-9.

Three other aspects have been identified, namely:

- The application of data minimization mechanisms and the explicit support for consent and transparency in order to address requirements in the privacy dimensions. The extension of these concepts to address the combination of human and pervasive non-human identities becomes a relevant challenge here.
- The use of *what-if* scenarios to assess resilience in different scenarios, taking advantage of simulation mechanisms and their integration with different synthetic environments emulating network segments. A common interface to these environments, and their seamless integration on demand are the main goals to achieve the use of the NDT paradigm following the as-a-service pattern.

6.1.5.2.2 Mapping SPR features on the E2E system blueprint

As explained before, Figure 6-9 above also illustrates the mapping of the different SPR features, and the corresponding controls, on the E2E 6G system blueprint. The features associated to controls focused on direct security and privacy support become thus integrated within the pervasive functionalities, as specifically illustrated in Figure 6-9 by zooming in the corresponding element, highlighting how the CIA triad, AAA mechanisms, and the application of data protection and transparency have to be applied at all layers. Let us next describe how SPR controls, and the features are related with the different layers, as pervasive functionalities and/or specific enablers. The connection with the different layers enablers is discussed in section 8.2.

- *Infrastructure layer*

Cloud and computer service providers need to protect their own infrastructure from attacks and ensure the isolation of workloads by following techniques such as confidential computing to achieve CIA and AAA features. Device-level security addresses the resource-constrained and ultra-low-power environments, where the SPR controls should include energy-aware security protocols and integrated trust mechanisms. Trustworthy SoC architectures can be designed to prevent data leaks, ensure resilience against attacks, and provide robust foundations for tiny ML applications.

- *Network functions layer*

Security and privacy features should be carefully considered in this layer considering multi-level security solutions. For instance, when MNO relies on data networks deployed by other compute resource providers AAA features should be protected. The associated SPR controls in this layer collectively ensure the resilience, availability, confidentiality, and integrity of systems and data. They enhance data recovery mechanisms to maintain resilience against loss or corruption, ensure secure communication through ciphering and integrity protection, and provide robust mobility management to support seamless transitions and uninterrupted service. Physical layer security mechanisms aim to secure RAN protocols to strengthen the system's resilience and support CIA and AAA features by establishing secure communication channels.

- *Application enablement platform layer*

The paradigmatic scenario, when the UE acts as a CaaS consumer, considers the DN managed by a CCN, which is the CaaS provider. When the CCN manages compute resources at the DN and interfaces with the 6G system, it is important to establish a secure communication path between the UE application client and the DN that ensures CIA and AAA features as well as the data privacy properties such as data minimization and supporting consent and transparency.

- *Management and orchestration*

As a pervasive functionality in the 6G E2E system blueprint, M&O can contribute to advancing security management through closed-loop control and using AI for automating security actions. This approach enables efficient and secure multi-agent-based network management while incorporating dynamic security control loops in the 6G E2E system. By orchestrating security services seamlessly together with the closed loops, the system will allow the enforcement of remediation policies by automated actions and the application of SecDevOps mechanisms.

- *AI framework*

The integration of AI/ML framework in the 6G E2E system blueprint is pivotal for ensuring intelligent, adaptive, and efficient operations in all the layers. Robust and trustworthy AI mechanisms should be integrated, accompanied by privacy-enhanced data management and mechanisms to ensure CIA and AAA properties across network functions and connectivity options. Security automation in edge computing environments and accountability for shared data in federated domains are crucial to maintaining data integrity, reliability, and system trustworthiness.

- *Data Management framework*

The key functionalities performed by the data management framework such as data collection, distribution, and storage are required to be privacy compliant. This entails not only aligning with the privacy-compliant regulatory requirements but also fulfilling data minimization, supporting consent and transparency, and achieving confidentiality in data processing and storage.

- *Multistakeholder 6G ecosystem*

In a multi-stakeholder 6G ecosystem that allows resource federation among multiple administrative domains, there is a possibility of the transmission of security issues when there is no proper isolation is achieved between the domains. To ensure robust and secure service, it is essential to incorporate continuous monitoring and security assessment to ensure E2E security. This includes developing dynamic and adaptive security solutions for threat detection, mitigation, prediction, and response in a multi-stakeholder environment. To provide strong isolation between services over a multi-tenant/multi-operator infrastructure, potential solutions include incorporating cryptographically protected multi-level security enablers or using security policies together with identity and access management schemes. It is also important to ensure trust in such a multistakeholder environment where each entity is certain that another will perform the specific actions as expected. This can be addressed by the trust assurance with Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) mechanisms, and the application of specific enablers such as the Level of Trust Assessment Function (LoTAF), and the Transparent Notary Service (TNS) enablers, as described below.

- *Service exposure and new 6G services*

This allows to securely expose services and capabilities provided by 6G platform. Service exposure framework should support a strong authentication and authorization framework for secure identity and access management. With the zero-trust security models supported by 6G networks, it is important to maintain dynamic and continuous verification of service exposure. With the advancements in ciphering techniques from public key infrastructure towards a quantum-safe era, it will even necessitate encrypting API communication using quantum-safe cryptographic protocols.

In particular, a number of specific enablers are proposed as a specific class of beyond-communications functions labelled Trust & Evidence highlighted in Figure 6-9. These functions would include LoTAF, as exemplified in the figure, helping network users in assessing the trustworthiness of network services, the TNS as the common reference for identity (AAA) and crypto (CIA) features, and the possibility of exercising on-demand resilience evaluations.

6.1.6 Migration path from 5G to 6G

[HEX224-D21] discussed options for the evolution to 6G, i.e., the 5G to 6G migration path. It was concluded that 6G RAN should be standalone and connected to a CN that is based on an evolved 5G Core (aka “E-5GC” in Hexa-X-II) with Shared NFs and dedicated 6G NFs to support 6G UEs and specific 6G functionalities.

The main reason for base the 6G CN on an evolved 5GC, is to avoid delays in introducing key 6G services. To ensure smooth and timely migration to 6G, 6G CN can share selected network functions (NFs) with 5G, see Figure 6-10 which shows an example of how new 6G NFs and sharing (reusing) 5G NFs can look like. New or non-backward compatible changes can be introduced by adding new NFs or new services to existing NFs. In this example the UPF, Session Management Function (SMF) and Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) are new 6G NFs and the Unified Data Management (UDM), Network function Repository Function (NRF), Authentication Server Function (AUSF) and the NEF are shared.

Figure 6-10 Core design in 6G based on evolution of 5GC with 6G NFs and Shared NFs [HEX225-D35]

Co-existence on the same spectrum between 5G and 6G is done by MRSS [HEX223-D43] and inter-RAT handover is used for interworking, see Figure 6-11. The main reason to not use a dual connectivity solution as interworking between 5G and 6G is that this causes a “non-stand alone” 6G (as it happened for 5G), and this

will delay the introduction of new 6G services. Furthermore, the use of dual connectivity also caused numerous architecture options which that led to unnecessary complexity. Figure 6-11 also depicts that a LLS in the RAN will likely be used for 6G, instead of the HLS (the Centralized Unit (CU)/Distributed Unit (DU) split) used in 5G. The main reason for this is to simplify the RAN architecture, as well as to support distributed radio nodes for e.g., Distributed (D-MIMO).

Figure 6-11 Overview of components of 5G to 6G migration

The overhead by using MRSS should obviously be minimized. Unlike the 5G dynamic spectrum sharing feature, which had to account with the numerous always-on reference signals from 4G, MRSS will have to contend with far less incumbent signals, leading to a much more efficient use of the resources. The legacy 5G UEs should be able to avoid all 6G signals, i.e., the 6G signals are “hidden” by reusing 5G locations in the time frequency grid, i.e., the 5G UEs will not be affected by these 6G signals. For example, the 6G CSI reference signal locations should be a superset of 5G CSI reference signal time/frequency locations. In general, the 6G UL signals can be handled by scheduling 6G within the 5G carrier and thereby avoid overlap with 5G signals. However, the uplink control information (UCI) signal for 5G and 6G needs to be coordinated. The 5G UCI is essentially scheduled by 5G and any periodic physical UL control channel remains as in 5G. Similarly, the (possible) 6G UCI is scheduled by 6G. For RACH resources, it is possible to reuse the 5G RACH structure as long as the 6G RACH is similar enough to 5G RACH. All in all, MRSS in the UL should be possible with negligible overhead.

In DL, there are several signals that need to be considered. To estimate the signalling overhead incurred by MRSS, consider e.g., a scenario with no 6G traffic, a 20 MHz carrier, and 15 kHz subcarrier spacing. The fundamental 6G downlink signals which are always present are the SSB and the SIB1. Assuming a system with a carrier bandwidth of 20 MHz (100 Resource blocks). Further on, the 5G SSB typically occupies 20 Resource blocks and 4 out of 14 symbols which are transmitted every 20 ms [Sam21]. Assuming same SSB allocation for 6G, this means that the SSB signal gives roughly 0.3% overhead (see [HEX225-D35]). If the SSB periodicity in 6G will be even longer, the overhead will decrease even more. In the same manner, the SIB1 gives an overhead of 1.2%. Similarly, if the bandwidth is increased, the overhead will decrease even further. Note that there is no Cell-specific Reference Signal (CRS) in either 5G or 6G as there is in 4G, so the overhead from the CRS signals can be avoided between 5G and 6G. All in all, this means that the overhead from an empty 6G carrier on top of 5G is ~1.5%. However, for scenarios with even higher bandwidths, the overhead will be even lower. For example, for a 100 MHz carrier (mid-band Time Division Duplex -TDD),

the corresponding overhead for MRSS is 0.3%. This can be compared to the overhead from dynamic spectrum sharing between 4G and 5G, which incurs an overhead of at least 5% [Sam21].

6.2 Final selected enablers for the 6G E2E system in cobots use case

This section presents the results of the enabler selection process obtained by implementing the KG method steps as shown in Figure 2-2 (c.f. Section 2.3). It is important to state here that, the implementation of the KG method presented in this section is only carried out for the Industrial cobots use case [HEX223-D12],[HEX225-D14], which is expected to serve as an example for the rest of the community to carry the work forward and perform the same process with other use cases. Furthermore, the selected enablers here are only a reflection of the set of enablers that are well placed to serve the Industrial cobots use case. Hence, a given enabler if not selected here does not indicate in any way that it will not be present in the overall 6G blueprint and vision. Instead, it should be interpreted that the given enabler is not well suited to serve the Industrial cobots use case, as compared to other enablers.

Note that, to perform the enabler selection, in addition to the meta-data collection performed within the Hexa-X-II project, enabler information from other SNS-JU projects was also solicited. In Section 6.2.1, a brief description of the enablers from other SNS-JU projects, from whom the information was received, has been provided. Subsequently in Sections 6.2.2-6.2.7, the complete Knowledge graph-based enabler selection method, as detailed in Chapter 2 (Section 2.3), for the industrial cobots use case has been elaborated.

6.2.1 Integration of enablers from other SNS-JU projects

As part of the enabler selection process, and the broader mandate of the Hexa-X-II project as the EU flagship project, enablers from other projects have also been considered. Broadly, information was solicited from multiple SNS-JU projects, and inputs on multiple enablers being explored within them was collected. Note that, responses were solicited from multiple projects, however, completed data was received only from four of these, the description and short enabler descriptions of which are presented in sections 6.2.1.1 – 6.2.1.4.

6.2.1.1 PREDICT-6G enablers

The PREDICT-6G project [SNS-PRED6G] focuses on designing a deterministic network that is reliable, time-sensitive, and predictable, analysing relevant use cases to evaluate its potential business impact. It also aims to enhance the reliability and time sensitivity achievable in different technology domains, particularly in wireless domains, while enabling predictability of their behaviour. Additionally, PREDICT-6G seeks to provide an AI-based control-plane framework to enable determinism in multi-stakeholder, multi-technology 6G environments, facilitating frictionless multi-domain connectivity in heterogeneous 6G settings. Some of the enablers within PREDICT-6G, for whom the input was received, are briefly discussed below:

- *Multi-domain Data Plane (MDP)*
The multi-domain data plane is designed to enable seamless and efficient data transmission across heterogeneous network domains. This architecture ensures that data flows smoothly across multiple technologies and network segments, such as terrestrial, satellite, and wireless infrastructures. The MDP integrates deterministic communication and predictability into the data plane, ensuring that services are delivered with low latency, high reliability, and strict time sensitivity. By creating a unified data plane, it supports interoperability between different network layers, simplifying the complexity of multi-stakeholder environments and enhancing overall network performance in 6G ecosystems.
- *AI-enabled Control Plane (AICP)*
The AI-enabled control plane utilizes artificial intelligence to manage and optimize network operations across diverse and multi-domain environments. AICP automates decision-making processes related to resource allocation, traffic management, and service provisioning, ensuring that the network can dynamically adapt to real-time conditions, such as changing traffic loads or network failures. The AI-driven approach allows for predictive analysis, enabling proactive adjustments to maintain deterministic service levels, low latency, and high reliability. By coordinating across various network domains (e.g., terrestrial, satellite, and wireless), AICP enhances interoperability, streamlining operations in complex 6G networks and enabling seamless, efficient service delivery across multiple stakeholders and technologies.

6.2.1.2 6G-SHINE enablers

The 6G-SHINE project [SNS-6GSH] focuses on developing in-X wireless subnetworks—short-range, low-power radio cells designed to be embedded within various entities such as robots, vehicles, production modules, and classrooms. These subnetworks aim to meet extreme communication requirements, including ultra-low latency, high reliability, and multi-gigabit data rates. By leveraging the unique deployment characteristics of these short-range systems, 6G-SHINE seeks to achieve a highly efficient and cost-effective radio design, bringing wireless connectivity to an unprecedented level of pervasiveness. Some of the enablers within 6G-SHINE, for whom the input was received, are briefly discussed below:

- *Flexible subnetwork architecture with dynamic roles and integrating them with the 6G network of networks vision*
Flexible subnetwork architecture refers to dynamically adaptable, short-range in-X wireless subnetworks embedded in environments like vehicles, robots, and industrial modules. These subnetworks can assume dynamic roles, shifting between local control, edge processing, and high-speed data transmission based on real-time needs. By integrating with the broader 6G network of networks vision, these subnetworks interact seamlessly with larger-scale infrastructures, enabling efficient resource management, ultra-reliable low-latency communication, and adaptive connectivity. This approach enhances network scalability, resilience, and performance, making 6G communication more context-aware and energy-efficient.
- *Architecture enablers for advanced RRM mechanism and goal-oriented communications in subnetwork*
Architecture enablers are key components that support advanced RRM mechanisms and goal-oriented communications within in-X wireless subnetworks. These subnetworks dynamically adapt to local context, traffic demands, and performance requirements, optimizing spectrum use, latency, and energy efficiency. Advanced AI-driven RRM ensures efficient resource allocation, interference management, and seamless integration with the broader 6G network of networks. Goal-oriented communications shift the focus from raw data transmission to delivering only task-relevant information, improving efficiency, reliability, and real-time decision-making in environments like robotics, smart factories, and autonomous systems.

6.2.1.3 ETHER enablers

The ETHER project [SNS-ETHER] aims to develop a unified and sustainable RAN that seamlessly integrates terrestrial, aerial, and space-based components. By leveraging AI/ML, ETHER focuses on optimizing resource management across this multi-layered architecture, enabling the network to self-adapt to dynamic conditions without human intervention. The project also emphasizes energy efficiency and cost-effectiveness, striving to provide continuous broadband connectivity even in remote or underserved areas. Key objectives include demonstrating practical applications through experimentation and identifying benefits that will drive future investments in integrated networks. Some of the enablers within ETHER, for whom the input was received, are briefly discussed below:

- *Unified waveform design*
The unified waveform design refers to the development of a single, adaptable waveform that can efficiently support communication across multiple network layers, including terrestrial, aerial, and space-based components. By leveraging AI/ML-driven optimization, unified waveforms can dynamically adapt to varying channel conditions, reduce interference, and enhance spectral efficiency. This approach enables self-evolving networks, improving connectivity, reliability, and energy efficiency while supporting diverse 6G use cases, such as broadband access in remote areas and robust global communication links.
- *Horizontal/vertical handovers and AI-based handover control mechanisms for NTN*
Seamless connectivity across terrestrial, aerial, and space-based networks requires efficient handover mechanisms. Horizontal handovers occur between similar network types (e.g., between terrestrial BSs or NTN BSs), while vertical handovers manage transitions between different network layers (e.g., switching from a ground-based 5G/6G network to an NTN BS). Note that, while in the literature a horizontal HO is between 3GPP network types and a vertical HO is between a 3GPP and non-3GPP network type, in this case, a horizontal HO refers to a HO between terrestrial BSs, while a vertical HO is between a terrestrial and non-terrestrial network. To optimize these handovers, AI-based control mechanisms use real-time data, predictive analytics, and machine learning to enhance decision-making. These mechanisms anticipate link quality variations, minimize latency, and reduce service disruptions, ensuring a self-evolving, resilient, and energy-efficient hybrid network for future 6G applications.

- *Integrated TN-NTN architecture*
The Integrated Terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial Network (TN-NTN) architecture aims to create a unified communication system that seamlessly connects terrestrial infrastructures, such as 5G base stations, with non-terrestrial networks, including satellites, HAPS, and UAVs. This integration enables continuous global coverage, improved network resilience, and enhanced connectivity in remote or underserved areas. AI-driven resource management ensures dynamic adaptation to varying network conditions, optimizing spectrum usage, reducing latency, and maintaining service quality across diverse environments. This hybrid architecture is a key enabler for 6G networks, supporting ultra-reliable and high-capacity communication.
- *Flexible payload design for satellite communications*
Flexible payload design is a key innovation for enhancing the adaptability and efficiency of NTN in satellite communications. Unlike traditional rigid payloads, flexible payloads enable dynamic reconfiguration of frequency bands, beamforming, and power allocation based on real-time network demands. By leveraging software-defined radio (SDR) and AI-driven resource management, satellites can optimize coverage, reduce interference, and seamlessly integrate with TN. This adaptability is crucial for 6G networks, ensuring scalability, energy efficiency, and enhanced service continuity, particularly in remote and dynamic environments.
- *Zero-touch management and orchestration*
It refers to the use of AI/ML-driven automation to operate and optimize hybrid TN-NTN without human intervention. This approach enables self-configuring, self-optimizing, and self-healing network functions, ensuring seamless connectivity across satellites, aerial platforms, and ground-based infrastructures. By leveraging intelligent orchestration, the network can dynamically allocate resources, manage handovers, and adapt to changing traffic demands in real-time. This enhances efficiency, scalability, and reliability, making 6G networks more resilient, energy-efficient, and cost-effective while reducing operational complexity.

6.2.1.4 TERA6G enablers

The TERA6G project [SNS-TERA6G] is focused on developing advanced photonic wireless transceivers to achieve Terabit-per-second data rates and implement massive MIMO techniques. These transceivers operate in the millimetre-wave (30 GHz to 300 GHz) and Terahertz (300 GHz to 3 THz) frequency bands, facilitating the “Fiber-over-the-Air” concept. This approach enables independently steerable wireless pencil-beams with data capacities comparable to fibre optics, supporting applications such as dense urban mobile site connectivity, temporary ad-hoc networks, and connections to moving objects in various networks. Some of the enablers within TERA6G, for whom the input was received, are briefly discussed below:

- *Photonics-based broadband transceivers*
These transceivers aim to use the capabilities of a photonics-based system, to be able to create transceivers that deliver high bit rates with significantly lower power consumption and high fidelity. Furthermore, an additional capability being developed in TERA6G project is to operate them in the microwave/millimetre-wave/Terahertz range.
- *Photonic-based beam-formed and beam-steered two-dimensional antenna arrays*
By utilizing photonics, the system can dynamically form and steer multiple independent beams, enhancing spatial multiplexing, reducing interference, and improving network flexibility. Hence, photonic-based beam-formed and beam-steered two-dimensional (2D) antenna arrays leverage photonic technologies to generate and control high-frequency electromagnetic beams with precision.
- *Beam-steering control algorithms*
The main aim of these control algorithms is to minimize misalignment impacts and to exploit spatial discovery and network topology dynamic reconfigurability.

6.2.2 Meta-data collection

The enabler selection process, as presented in section 2.3 (c.f. Steps 1-3), requires the collection of enabler meta-data. The final set of collected enabler meta-data is provided in an open-source repository [HEX2-JOK+25]. For the collection of the qualitative impact on KPIs and KVIs, the set of KPIs and KVIs that were considered for this assessment are presented in Table 6-2 and Table 6-3, respectively.

Table 6-2 KPIs considered for enabler collection

KPIs	Justification/criticality/assumption
Device-to-device latency ≥ 0.8 ms	Exchange of coordination messages between cobots, etc.
Latency (cobot to campus) = 1-10 ms	Critical if timely response is expected. However, not critical if no real-time response is expected (e.g., AI/ML model exchange)
Minimum transfer interval ≥ 1.66 ms and < 10 ms	Critical for scenarios when determinism is necessary for cobots.
Message error rate $< 1e-5 - 1e-7$	Low message error rate is essential to ensure reliable communications
Bitrate control plane ≥ 2.5 Mbps	Data rates for control plane signalling
Bitrate data plane ≤ 250 Mbps	In general, the data rate requirement is around 10 Mbps. However, in scenarios where there might be requirement of high-definition videos, e.g., cameras, these requirements can go up to 250 Mbps.
Connection density ≤ 0.5 devices / m ²	The assumption here is that there would be at least 8 cobots in a 4 m x 4 m area
Positioning accuracy ≤ 0.1 m	This level of positioning accuracy is envisioned for cobots to function in space constrained scenarios
Localization accuracy < 1 m	This level of localization accuracy is envisioned for cobots to function
Setup time	Amount of time taken to setup services
Migration time	Time required to migrate services
Security and trust (data plane)	Critical to ensuring security of data plane operations, user data as well as privacy for each user
Security and trust (control plane)	Critical to ensuring security of network identity and operations
Energy consumption	In general, 6G should be designed with energy efficient communication principles
Material reuse	In general, 6G should be designed with minimal waste (maximum reuse) of materials

In more detail, Table 6-2 details the list of KPIs along with the justification/importance/assumptions related to choosing these KPIs for the Industrial cobots use case. For further information on specific KPIs, we refer the reader to [HEX223-D12, HEX225-D14] and [HEX224-D24]. Notably, certain specific KPIs related to trust, security, setup time and migration time have also been introduced, which will provide the required guidance towards designing a 6G system that is both reliable and trustworthy.

Next, in Table 6-3 KVI associated with industrial cobots have been outlined, which aim to provide a guiding principle for designing a 6G system that adheres to the economic, social and environmental sustainability pillars [HEX224-D13]. Specifically, based on these sustainability pillars and the corresponding sustainability handprints and sustainability footprints for the use case under investigation, the KVIs developed in [HEX225-D14] are utilized to analyse the level of impact the technological enablers have on the sustainability pillars. Further details on the use cases, sustainability pillars and KVI development process can be found in [HEX225-D14].

Table 6-3 KVIs considered for enabler collection

Main topic	KVIs	Sustainability Handprint	Sustainability Footprint
Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total energy usage (kWh) in communication dimensions for the cobots • Total energy usage (kWh) for data transfer (optimising packets and data vol.) 	Resource efficiency: Functionalities may be provided by machines with less materials, energy, and waste generated	Energy is consumed and materials are used to manufacture, deploy, and operate cobots and associated services
Materials /waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Life expectancy of robots: making better and longer-lasting hardware/software, easily upgradable, modular. Avoid having to replace the entire cobot because of failures in the 6G-related aspects • # of virtualised functionalities: Preventing/avoiding material usage for hardware, when these features/capabilities could be virtualised. 		The disposal of machines and devices results in increased electronic waste
Safety	# of injuries at work/level of severity of work-related injuries/perception of risk	Safer work environment leading to less injuries.	
Trustworthiness /privacy /security	# of data leaks/breaches/cyber-attacks, with personal information compromised	Increased autonomy by robots supporting people with disabilities	People's privacy may be breached by unauthorized use of robots' and cobots' sensors
Costs	# of industries or stakeholders that cannot access cobots for a given reason / # total industries or stakeholders, per domain/vertical and/or per geographical area: Ensuring that the communication and coverage aspects in the infrastructure deployment are not a bottleneck for the implementation of cobots. i.e., it's easy and not expensive to deploy the required communication environment for a proper application of cobots.	Benefits of robots and cobots might not be distributed evenly among society	New business opportunities for old and new businesses from the use of collaborative robots (new markets around robots beyond factory): Cf. "Accessibility" in "Social benefits"
Productivity /efficiency	<p>Ensure that 6G is reliable and resilient, and so, no downtimes in a given production scenario are due to failures in the communication-related aspects.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Downtimes • several production KPIs (distinctive per factory) 	Increased local and global productivity, cost efficiency and enhanced competitiveness from the use of the collaborative robots	

6.2.3 Meta-data transformation

To perform the graph pruning procedure, as discussed in Section 2.3, we first need to ensure that the given meta-data [HEX2-JOK+25] is transformed such that it can be utilized to create a knowledge graph. Specifically, we focus primarily on the following inputs to construct the knowledge graph: *Maturity*, *Importance towards Migration*, *KPIs*, *Design principles fulfilled*, *Enabler dependencies*, *KVIs*.

It is worth stating that the aim of the enabler selection process was to not penalize standardization of new technologies, development of newer and more efficient hardware and alongside it the necessary development of new interfaces for future uses and applications. Hence, those features have not been considered for the

analysis in the current scope of this work. However, as standardization, hardware and interfaces mature, these aspects can be considered for future iterations of the 6G E2E system, for example after 3GPP Release 21/22.

Next, each of the considered features is, if required, transformed to an objective scale. The maturity of an enabler, which is expressed as the technological readiness level on a scale of 1–9, readily translates to an objective quantity that can be utilized for graph development, comparison and graph pruning processes. The importance towards migration for an enabler is expressed objectively as either “yes” or “no”. To emphasize the criticality of enablers, which exist and will be important for migration from 5G to 6G, a weight of $1e6$ is provided to those enablers with a value yes and a weight of 1 to the others. This ensures that enablers are not negatively penalized but at the same time enablers with importance towards migrations are significantly prioritized, in line with the evolutionary nature of 6G vis-à-vis 5G.

Notably, the KPI and KVI related meta-data is collected as a subjective assessment. Specifically, for the KPI the meta-data collected indicates whether a technological enabler has a positive, negative or neutral impact on a given KPI. For the assessment with respect to the KVIs, it involves first distilling the stated KVI requirements into technical requirements, after which it is determined if a given enabler (or groups of enablers) satisfy those requirements. Based on the enabler to the technical requirement mapping, they can be then mapped as being able to satisfy the corresponding KVI requirement. A detailed description of the KVI to technical requirement mapping is provided later in this section. Next, the main reason for the aforementioned subjective analysis is because:

- The entire 6G system blueprint will consist of a large number of enablers, located in the different stacks of the E2E system (c.f. Figure 6-1 for the E2E system blueprint). Each of these enablers provisions a certain KPI and KVI value. Notably, these will be different at different stacks of the E2E system, given that the requirements at those stacks will be different to achieve a certain use case KPI and KVI target.
- Certain enablers are at significantly low TRL level, such as TRL 1. For such enablers, the KPI and KVI assessments do not exist at the moment as they are still under development.

Hence, to have a fair assessment of enablers jointly, while they reside on different parts of the 6G E2E system, a subjective evaluation is carried out first. Subsequently, the responses for the KPI meta-data are encoded by the triple [-1, 0, +1], wherein -1 is for a negative impact, 0 is for a neutral impact and +1 is for a positive impact. The sum of the impacts on all the KPIs for an enabler is used to compute an overall KPI score. This is subsequently used in the graph pruning process.

The fulfilment of design principles is captured via edge weights, wherein the existence of an edge between an enabler and a design principle is given a weight 1. On the other hand, there is no edge if an enabler does not fulfil a certain design principle. Further, the dependencies between enablers are also captured via edges. However, we specify an edge weight of 0 to distinguish these edges from those that are used for the establishing the relationship between enabler and design principles.

Next, association of the KVI requirements to the technical requirements is presented in Table 6.4. These technical requirements, and hence, the KVI requirements are then used to align the selected enablers, such that the final list of enablers satisfies both the KPI and KVI requirements for the use case under consideration. Note that, by aligning it is meant that either more enablers may be added, or some enablers may be removed.

Table 6.4 KVIs to technical requirements mapping

Main topic	KVIs	Requirements
Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total energy usage (kWh) in communication dimensions for the cobots • Total energy usage (kWh) for data transfer (optimising packets and data vol.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy efficient network operation • Energy efficient devices • Energy efficient AI/ML training and inference
Materials /Waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Life expectancy of robots: making better and longer-lasting hardware/software, easily upgradable, modular. Avoid having to replace the entire cobot because of failures in the 6G-related aspects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modularization • Virtualization • Softwarization • Compute offloading • Resilience

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of virtualised functionalities: Preventing/avoiding material usage for hardware, when these features/capabilities could be virtualised. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predictable low-latency
Safety	# of injuries at work/level of severity of work-related injuries/perception of risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ubiquitous connectivity • Resilience • Explainability
Trustworthiness /Privacy /Security	# of data leaks/breaches/cyber-attacks, with personal information compromised	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliability • Trust and security • Explainability
Costs	# of industries or stakeholders that cannot access cobots for a given reason / # total industries or stakeholders, per domain/vertical and/or per geographical area: Ensuring that the communication and coverage aspects in the infrastructure deployment are not a bottleneck for the implementation of cobots. i.e., it's easy and not expensive to deploy the required communication environment for a proper application of cobots.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low Capital Expenditure • Closed-loop control • Reliability • Monitoring and telemetry • Low energy/energy neutral • Zero-touch • Service exposure
Productivity /Efficiency	<p>Ensure that 6G is reliable and resilient, and so, no downtimes in a given production scenario are due to failures in the communication-related aspects.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Downtimes • Several production KPIs (distinctive per factory) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ubiquitous connectivity • Low latency • AI-native • Reliability • Resiliency • Service exposure • Ensuring SLAs

6.2.4 Noisy knowledge graph generation

Figure 6-12 Noisy knowledge graph (green bubbles = design principles, blue bubbles = enablers that satisfy at least one design principle and orange bubbles = enablers that do not satisfy any design principle)

Figure 6-12 presents the full knowledge graph (KG) which was obtained from the metadata table [HEX2-JOK+25]. Specifically, the features for the nodes and edges of the noisy KG are generated based on the meta-

data that has been collected and subsequently transformed, as discussed in Section 6.2.3. Note that, the full KG does not include the KVI information as shown in Figure 2-2. From Figure 6-12, it can be observed that the Noisy KG for the Industrial cobots use case presents quite a complex landscape for the enabler selection process. It is imperative to highlight here that the acronyms in the blue, orange and green bubbles in Figure 6-12 are created solely for the sake of brevity, and their full description can be found in [HEX2-JOK+25]. Next, the green bubbles in Figure 6-12 indicate the ten design principles as stated in section 2.2. Additionally, the blue bubbles represent all the enablers which satisfy at least one design principle. Lastly, the orange bubbles represent the enablers which do not satisfy any design principle.

Furthermore, each blue bubble (enabler) has a green edge, with a weight 1, towards a green bubble (design principle) if the said enabler satisfies the said design principle. On the other hand, the dependencies between the enablers are captured via the red coloured edges. Note that, we do not provision any weighting (weight = 0) for these edges as these are utilized to capture just the relationship between enablers and the fact that if an enabler is chosen then the other enablers on which it is dependent are also chosen during the selection process.

6.2.5 Graph pruning

Figure 6-13 Pruned knowledge graph, wherein all enablers (except the dependencies) have at least TRL 2 and all the enablers essential for migration have also been preserved

The graph pruning process involves selecting enablers that address the use case as well as the broader 6G system requirements. Given the noisy KG (Figure 6-12) and the requirements presented in Section 6.2.2, a first pruning step is carried out based on the maturity and importance towards migration. The pruning is performed by thresholding the maturity feature to at least TRL 2, i.e., all enablers with at least TRL 2 are retained, and preserving all enablers that are important towards migration. The pruned KG is shown in Figure 6-13.

Next, an analysis of the KPI scores for each of the selected enablers, excluding the dependencies, within the pruned KG is performed. Specifically, the KPI scores for each enabler are computed by summing up the [+1,0,-1] encoded triple of impact on KPIs, as discussed in section 6.2.3. Notably, from [HEX2-JOK+25] it can be seen that enablers either have a positive (+1) or neutral (0) impact only on the KPIs for the industrial cobots use case. Consequently, a higher sum value, i.e., KPI score, is representative of the number of KPIs on which the said enabler will have a positive impact. Figure 6-14 demonstrates a frequency analysis of the KPI scores of all the enablers within the pruned KG.

Figure 6-14 KPI impact analysis for each enabler from the pruned KG

From Figure 6-14, it can be observed that 12 enablers have a net zero KPI impact on the use case KPI requirements. This means that these enablers do not contribute anything to the overall fulfilment of the use case KPI requirements. Hence, as part of the graph pruning process a threshold on the KPI score of greater than or equal to 1 is set. This means that enablers which have a positive impact of at least 1 for satisfying use case KPI requirements are selected. Subsequently, the KG obtained in Figure 6-13 is pruned further, which we now term it as KPI-based-pruned KG (KKG), which is presented in Figure 6-15.

Figure 6-15 KPI-based pruned knowledge graph, wherein enablers that have at least a positive impact of 1, i.e., a KPI score of 1, are selected

Following the creation of KKG, a categorization of these enablers and KVI impact analysis is performed next.

6.2.6 Enabler categorization and KVI impact analysis

Firstly, the selected enablers from the KKG are combined with the already selected list of enablers in [HEX224-D23], which acts as a baseline for the enabler selection, and categorized into 23 enabler categories. Some examples of the categorized enablers are provided in Table 6-5, and a complete list of categorized enablers is provided in Table C-5 in Annex C.

Table 6-5 Examples of categorized enablers (c.f. Table C-5 for full list)

Category	Enabler name
Intelligent radio interface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ITx: Intelligent transmitter IRx: Intelligent receiver ITRx: Intelligent transmitter and receiver SpecShare: Spectrum sharing, coexistence
JCAS PHY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> JCSWave: JCAS waveforms and frame structures JCSRA: JCAS resource allocation
New Devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IGENE: Identification of 4 new 6G device classes (RHDRBL, HRLl, EmMTC, EN)
Flexible radio interface and protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FRRC: Flat RRC design SICMS: Separation of IDLE mode and CONNECTED mode signalling SDAPBCS: SDAP protocol for Beyond Communication Services (BCS) DRRM: Data recovery and reordering mechanisms MRRC: Modular RRC design RPUP: Radio Processing Units for user plane MCIP: MAC ciphering and integrity protection RRC: Radio protocols for beyond communication

Subsequently, the full list of enabler categories in Table C-5 are mapped to the new requirements derived from the KVI requirements, as presented in Section 6.2.3. An example list is provided in Table 6-6 and a full list of enablers mapped to the new requirements, and hence the KVIs is provided in Table C-6 in Annex C.

Table 6-6 Examples of mapping Enablers to Requirements and KVIs (c.f. Table C-6 for full list)

Category	Enabler name	Requirements addressed	KVIs addressed
Intelligent radio interface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ITx: Intelligent transmitter IRx: Intelligent receiver ITRx: Intelligent transmitter and receiver SpecShare: Spectrum sharing, coexistence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI-native Reliability to varying channel conditions Improved data rates and spectral resource efficiency Reduced costs due to spectrum sharing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lower downtimes (efficiency) Reduced costs due to improved coverage, throughput and latency Improved trustworthiness in network performance
JCAS PHY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> JCSWave: JCAS waveforms and frame structures JCSRA: JCAS resource allocation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reliability to do improved sensing and localization for indoor factory environments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lower downtimes (efficiency) Industry specific production KPIs (productivity)
New Devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IGENE: Identification of 4 new 6G device classes (RHDRBL, HRLl, eLPWA, EN) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy efficient and neutral devices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced total energy usage Reduced OPEX (costs) due to reduced energy requirements
Flexible radio interface and protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FRRC: Flat RRC design SICMS: Separation of IDLE mode and CONNECTED mode signalling SDAPBCS: SDAP protocol for beyond communication services DRRM: Data recovery and reordering mechanisms MRRC: Modular RRC design RPUP: Radio processing units for user plane MCIP: MAC ciphering and integrity protection RRC: Radio protocols for beyond communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Modularization Energy efficient network operation Reliability and Resiliency to adverse channel conditions and scenarios Low latency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced total energy usage Lower downtimes (Efficiency) Industry specific production KPIs (productivity)

6.2.7 Pragmatic considerations and final enabler list

Given the enabler mapping onto the KVI, a KVI score is computed wherein the number of enabler categories which in help in satisfying a specific KVI is determined. This is shown in Figure 6-16.

Figure 6-16 Number of enabler categories per KVI

Based on the histogram-based analysis in Figure 6-16, it can be observed that the enabler selection process has slightly under provisioned the 6G system for industrial cobots use case for reducing material usage and waste. Moreover, there are only three enabler categories that help in satisfying the safety KVI. Subsequently, pragmatic considerations motivated the introduction of one specific enabler, within the *flexible radio interface and protocol* category. Indeed, the enabler *Primary Cell (Pcell) Recovery*, which was not selected due to lack of KPI score fulfillment criteria, can be introduced to enhance *safety* characteristics. This will enable service continuity and connectivity to the cobots even if the primary serving cell becomes blocked by moving the connection to a secondary cell.

The Final list of categorized enablers, following the pragmatic considerations alongside the inputs from other SNS-JU projects, is presented in Table C-8 of Annex C. Notably, the enablers provided by the ETHER and TERA-6G project were not relevant to the industrial cobots use case and hence, have not been listed in the final list of the selected enablers. On the other hand, the enablers from PREDICT-6G and 6G-SHINE projects were relevant to the use case, but they have already been considered within the list of selected enablers from HEXA-X-II.

6.3 Conclusions

In this chapter, the 6G system architecture have been updated with specific views of the 6G E2E system and the results of the enabler selection based on KG method, meta-data. Regarding the design of a 6G system architecture which requires a holistic approach, the updated system blueprint describes the fundamental functionalities and key interfaces of the 6G system, both internally and externally. Specific system views of the system blueprint have been described. These specific views include radio protocols and flexible topologies, new 6G services and the related exposure framework, multistakeholder aspects in the realization of an E2E 6G system, pervasive functionalities including the AI/ML and data frameworks, pervasive security, privacy and resilience, and migration path from 5G to 6G. The implementation of the KG method presented in this chapter is only carried out for the Industrial cobots use case. The selection of enablers represents a suite of enablers based on pragmatic considerations and Industrial cobots use case. Those enablers that were not selected are those that do not correspond to Industrial cobots use cases, but it is possible that they could be selected for the other 6G use cases. In future perspectives, selection could be extended to other 6G use cases to obtain a holistic system blueprint with detailed views of specific aspects covering a large range of KPIs and KVIs. Concerning AI/ML specific view, it should support multi-stakeholder AI/ML cooperative decision making and MLOps pipelines for each type of data (infrastructure, virtual network, application enablement, etc).

7 Final E2E system-level validation phase

The validation process of the 6G system is driven by the design and implementation of PoCs. Within the scope of the E2E system-level validation, various 6G enablers are assessed, including aspects related to M&O over the 6G continuum, beyond communication enablers, network transformation, network control programmability and telemetry, 6G devices, radio protocols and sensing. The basic framework for the development of System PoCs and System-PoC A was first described in Hexa-X-II deliverables D2.1 [HEX223-D21] and then D2.2 [HEX223-D22]. D2.3 [HEX224-D23] provided an overview of the system-PoC A together with some complementary simulation results, accompanied with a description of the planned components of system-PoC B. D2.4 [HEX224-D24] was the deliverable that provided the description of the system-PoC B in detail, accompanied by various results.

The final E2E system-level validation phase represents the final stage of Hexa-X-II's efforts in designing, testing, and refining the 6G system blueprint. This phase takes a comprehensive approach, combining experimental and simulation-based evaluations to confirm that the proposed system design aligns with the project's key principles, such as social, economic and environmental sustainability, resilience, flexible and modular design. Building on the progress made in earlier deliverables, this stage focuses on consolidating PoC results, integrating new enablers, and refining the E2E architecture. By addressing critical aspects like security, privacy, scalability, efficiency and automation, this final phase provides practical insights to strengthen the 6G vision and ensure its readiness to meet societal and ecosystem needs.

7.1 Overview of the E2E system evaluation and validations

The E2E system evaluation and validation in Hexa-X-II serves as a key step in assessing how the developed components, methodologies, and enablers align with the envisioned 6G system blueprint. The validation activities focus on demonstrating critical aspects related to the evolution of pervasive system features, such as advanced Management & Orchestration, as well as aspects such as beyond communication services, such as CaaS/compute offload, JCAS, AIaaS, etc. and ensuring practical alignment with the design principles of the 6G system.

The three system-PoCs, namely A, B and C have been designed to be developed in an incremental manner, extending the E2E system aspects.

- System-PoC A focused on smart network management aspects (WP6-oriented) for demonstrating management mechanisms ensuring the progression of 6G path from incorporating strong inputs from Hexa-X and other 6G EU, national and international projects, to the first public PoC [HEX223-D22].
- System-PoC B mainly focused on network architecture elements, such as network of networks enabler and flexible topologies, beyond communication network aspects (WP3), as well as refinements of the management mechanisms, introduced in system-PoC A.
- System-PoC C, lastly, focuses on the evolution of the PoC A and B enablers, while also introducing novel radio and devices aspects (WP4 and WP5).

More specifically, system-PoC A established the foundation for E2E system evaluations within a single-domain configuration, utilizing a testbed with autonomous mobile robots and UAVs. The core focus was the development and optimization of an automated warehouse inventory management scenario, emphasizing:

- Intent-based orchestration: Intents are processed and orchestrated through an IF that enables seamless interaction between various domains, including application, AI, and service management resources.
- Energy-efficient Functionality Allocation (FA): A metaheuristic algorithm optimized workload placement across compute nodes, ensuring energy efficiency and system trustworthiness.
- Trust evaluation functions: Real-time trust evaluations informed workload placement decisions, enhancing reliability.
- Advanced resource allocation: Optimal assignment of tasks, such as object detection and quality inspection, was dynamically determined, considering energy availability, proximity, and hardware capabilities.

Building on the successes of system-PoC A, system- and component-PoC B introduced more advanced features and extended the scope to multi-domain configurations. This iteration incorporated:

- Flexible topologies: Dynamic exposure and exploitation of temporary communication and compute resources to enhance system adaptability.
- Beyond communication features: Integration of Compute-as-a-Service and AI-as-a-Service models, enabling real-time resource and capability exposure.
- Enhanced applications: Support for latency-sensitive services, such as video streaming and object detection, ensuring robust performance under dynamic conditions.
- Advanced orchestration and management: Intent-driven resource allocation, closed-loop controls, and multi-platform orchestration ensured seamless operation across domains.
- Security and privacy enhancements: Trust evaluation functions reinforced the system's resilience and reliability.

The infrastructure layer, supported by the IF, enabled the interaction between devices, compute resources, and management systems, while pervasive functionalities like closed-loop automation further enhanced system adaptability.

7.2 Components of the system PoC-C

7.2.1 System PoC-C

System PoC-C builds upon the advancements of system PoC-B and component PoC-B elements, further extending the capabilities of the 6G system by integrating new enablers from 6G radio technologies and 6G devices, developed under WP4 and WP5, respectively. These innovations are incorporated both within the system PoC itself and through complementary component PoC-Cs that run in parallel. Overall, the system PoC-C is extending its scope and features via the following directions:

- New APIs leveraging exposure of application enablement platform capabilities (Figure 7-1), such as Quality-on-Demand (QoD), device status/density, as well as integrating system PoC-B capabilities, such as advanced flexible topologies functionality and compute offloading features,
- Integration fabric adoption as a core enabler in multi-domain resource orchestration scenarios,
- Multi-agent reinforcement learning for multi-cluster orchestration,
- New devices with energy harvesting capabilities as part of the warehouse management scenario,
- Advancement from reactive to cognitive closed-loop automation with AI-driven predictive analytics for proactive resource planning,
- Intent-driven orchestration leveraging intent hierarchy, i.e., business intents, as well as intent-based DSM capabilities.

Two driving scenarios are leveraged to showcase system-level advancements, both under the collaborative robots use case, namely the cobot-powered warehouse inventory management, which is the driving system PoC scenario as an evolution from System PoC-A, and the cobot-powered video surveillance scenario, via the evolution of the Component PoC-B.1 system-level features.

System PoC-C introduces novel, energy harvesting-capable proximity-sensing devices in the warehouse inventory management scenario, designed to monitor shelf occupancy with high precision. These devices, equipped with energy harvesting capabilities using solar panels, represent a step forward in sustainable and autonomous operation: real-time digital twinning of the warehouse storage areas is updated via the energy harvesting devices for shelf occupancy; this information is then utilised by the evolution of the FA algorithm [HEX224-D24]. Additionally, these devices feature an intelligent wake-up/sleep cycle adjustment, powered by an integrated tinyML model, for further energy efficient enhancements.

As far as APIs exposed via the AEP are concerned, the warehouse inventory management platform has been extended with capabilities leveraging data exposed via the infrastructure and network domains comprising

localisation, CaaS, QoS, device status, etc. Some of the former, such as the device status/density and the QoS are Camara API-compliant [CAMARA].

As far as both the warehouse inventory management, as well as the cobot video surveillance scenarios are concerned, the intent-based DSM is used for configuring the network based on received business intent. The intent-based DSM is able to consume intent messages from the IF. Internal structure of the intent-based DSM has been described in Chapter 4 and [HEX2-ANG+24], including NLP capabilities and 3GPP intent data model. It interacts with TeraFlowSDN controller in order to dynamically establish the necessary connectivity services. The interface between IBN and SDN controller is based on IETF L3VPN YANG [IETF-L3VPN] using RESTconf protocol. The SDN controller is responsible for managing and controlling the network across the different domains. It is able to interact with multiple child SDN controllers, as well as interface directly with network equipment. For System PoC-C, an emulated transport network based on whiteboxes routers is considered. Using ContainerLab, [CNTLAB] Network Operating System is emulated from whiteboxes and the necessary L3VPN connectivity services are established.

7.2.1.1 System PoC C: cobot-powered warehouse inventory management in the context of multi-site synergetic monitoring and orchestration scenarios

One of the focus areas of the System PoC-C is to demonstrate, beyond network performance aspects, the enhanced operations and resilience leveraging novel functional capabilities, beyond communication, such as Flexible Topologies, Sensing, etc., and leveraging exposure of the network and infrastructure services via the respective APIs. Figure 7-1 illustrates a high-level representation of the conceptual architecture of the warehouse inventory management application components (client-server sides) leveraging the infrastructure and network functions layers' exposed capabilities.

Figure 7-1 Simplified view of the warehouse inventory management application components interfaces with E2E system's application enablement platform exposed capabilities

Furthermore, System PoC-C architecture (Figure 7-2) focuses on multi-domain, synergetic monitoring and orchestration scenario, assuming the following:

- Service A is a manufacturing-related latency-sensitive service comprising
 - a video streaming workflow (workflow A.1) and
 - an object detection workflow (workflow A.2)

- Service B is the warehouse inventory management service.
- End-to-end scenario
 - at time t_0 , an intent is received for starting workflow A.1 running at site B and workflow A.2 running at site A (synergetic monitoring scenario) with maximum latency requirement e.g., 10ms; SDN ensures the network requirement; metrics are monitored (frame per second, throughput, e2e latency, packet loss)
 - whenever latency or throughput is violated, SDN is triggered to dynamically regulate the bandwidth
 - at time t_1 , an intent is received for service B (inventory management) that needs to start at site A with high priority
 - Workflow A.2 needs to be interrupted due to insufficient resources
 - Site B is notified for the migration request of workflow A.2, which must respond according to resource availability
 - at t_2 , Workflow A.2 starts at site B; metrics are monitored and compared to initial set-up

Figure 7-2 Multi-domain/multi-site, synergetic monitoring and orchestration system PoC-C scenario

Targeted KPI measurements include: Migration downtime $t_2 - t_1$ for service A.2 (from the time the intent is received till the service is up and running in Site B); Throughput, E2E latency, packet loss in site A vs site B compared to the allocated compute and network resources; Power consumption related qualitative considerations for the execution of service A.2 in site A and Site B.

Figure 7-3 presents the main communicating components of the synergetic monitoring scenario with their interactions. The main contributing system components are:

- The UI, the interface orchestration manager component called API Server, the monitoring platform and the orchestrator of site A
- The API server, the monitoring platform and the orchestrator of site B
- The central monitoring and observability platform collecting metrics and KPIs from both sites/clusters (placed in site B)

- An intent-based DSM (detailed in Chapter 4) for configuring the network based on business intent
- The SDN controller for managing and controlling the network across the different domains
- The integration fabric for multi-tenancy support
- The message sequence chart in Figure 7-3 is divided into three sub-scenarios for better understanding. The first sub-scenario presents the beginning of the synergetic scenario with the network-related requirement. The intent arrives at the API Server of site B, which publishes it to the integration fabric. The intent is then consumed by the API server of site A and the intent-based DSM (referred as IBN in the figure). The IBN triggers the SDN controller to ensure the maximum latency requirement while workflow A.2 and workflow A.1 start running at site A and site B, respectively.
- The second sub-scenario relates to the dynamic regulation of bandwidth when a threshold violation is observed. The observability platform triggers the API Server of site B whenever it detects a latency or throughput violation. The API Server of site B publishes an event requesting bandwidth regulation. The IBN consumes the request and triggers the SDN controller to adjust the bandwidth accordingly.
- Finally, the last sub-scenario describes the case where migration of workflow A.2 needs to occur. Specifically, an intent is received by the API server of site A, requesting service B to be deployed with high priority. Due to insufficient resources, workflow A.2 needs to be deployed in site B. A message indicating this is published from the API server of site A to the integration fabric. The message is consumed by the API Server of site B and the IBN. The IBN triggers the SDN controller to deactivate previous intents while the migration of workflow A.2 from site A to site B occurs.

Figure 7-3 Message sequence chart of the main (initial) interactions between components for implementing the described end-to-end synergetic monitoring scenario.

The service deployment for multi-site synergetic monitoring and orchestration scenario includes three main components:

- Infrastructure: This includes two different sites, site A and site B as described above.
- Service components: Two main components are considered for this scenario, ‘Frame Sampler’ which is deployed in site B and ‘Object Detector’ which is moved across the two sites depending on the availability of site A’s resources.
- Observability: Heterogeneous data is gathered from both components using a distributed monitoring data collection mechanism of the monitoring and telemetry framework.

The scenario details are shown in Figure 7-4 that follows:

Figure 7-4 Synergetic scenario migration workflows

The intents coming from higher layers are translated into migration directives from site A to site B and vice versa. At the left figure, the migration process of the ‘Object Detector’ component from site B to site A is described, taking into consideration the timestamps used as measurement points. After evaluation of the two active intents on site A, the migration directive instructs the orchestrator of site A to start the service and the orchestrator of site B to drop the current deployment. The opposite process is described in the bottom workflow of Figure 7-4, where the resources are assigned to another application running on site A and thus, the directive to move the service from site A to site B is initiated.

7.2.1.2 System-level PoC aspects - Evolution of component-PoC #B.1: AI-assisted E2E lifecycle management of a 6G latency-sensitive service across the compute continuum – Evolution of closed-loop automation

In the multi-cluster setup, a single operator may hold the responsibility to manage service deployment across multiple clusters, but it can also be the case that individual cluster operators may deploy their own orchestration agents for consuming local resources. Such layered environments, depending on the agreement between operators can create various inter-agent dynamics. In this component PoC implementation a series of different

agents that collaboratively or independently try to optimally handle their given tasks based on their specific objectives is evaluated. During the component's next phase of implementation, a hierarchical mechanism was implemented using a multi agent reinforcement learning methodology where each agent tackles a different task: agent 1 migrates the service across clusters and agent 2 handles the scaling factor of the service. This study aims to evaluate scenarios where multiple stakeholders concurrently control different aspects of a deployment: such aspects may involve overlapping goals or deployment decision spaces large enough to either make inference impossible to learn or too heavy to execute.

The successful integration in the cobot-powered component PoC-B1 scenarios ([HEX224-D24]) of an instance of closed-loop demonstrated the effectiveness of i) CL-based automation and ii) the design and implementation of the CL as a cloud-native application customizable for the target system to be automated.

The plan for the next implementations towards PoC-C is to go beyond the reactive mechanism (i.e., the event-based actions, e.g., *battery level falls below a certain threshold*) evolve towards a cognitive one, based on AI analytics. The Analysis stage of the CL will be enhanced with AI/ML algorithms, capable of predicting in real-time the duration of the battery level of a given cobot. This implies also an enhancement of the collection capabilities of the monitoring stage: the number of parameters to be monitored will increase since the current battery level is not enough to provide an accurate prediction. In this sense, the cobot's resource consumption (CPU, memory, etc.), path to be covered, and task to be performed will be taken into account for both the training of the AI/ML model, as well as the inference. The results of the evolution towards an AI-driven closed-loop automation will be reported in [HEX225-D26].

From the standpoint of the IF (defined in the WP6 scope as management capabilities exposure), the system PoC-B did not serve as a testbed for the integration with other system components; rather, it offers a demonstrative presentation intended to guide the integration process and enhance existing interactions. This integration illustrated the effectiveness of the IF, demonstrating its capacity to enable seamless communication and orchestration between the diverse components of the 6G system within a multistakeholder architecture. In preparation for [HEX225-D26], the System PoC-C positions the IF as a central component for capability exposition within the 6G system architecture. The fabric aims to provide a unified interface for accessing and managing diverse system resources and services, at service level (Figure 7-5). Key aspects of the IF's positioning include:

1. *Capability abstraction*: The fabric abstracts complex underlying system capabilities, presenting them through simplified, standardized interfaces (e.g., REST interfaces) at service level.
2. *Multi-domain integration*: It facilitates seamless integration across multiple domains and sites, exploiting the event driven paradigm.
3. *Intent-based management*: The fabric supports the intent-based service management mechanisms, enabling efficient interaction between the producers and the consumers of the intent-based DSM-related high-level, goal-oriented control of system resources.

To support these capabilities, access to the developed platform was made available with the following main goals:

1. *Enabler integration*: Providing an in-house testbed for integrating various WP2 and WP6 enablers, allowing for real-world validation of their interoperability.
2. *API refinement*: Gathering feedback on the exposed APIs to refine and optimize the fabric's interface for future iterations.

The methodology for platform access involved a phased approach, starting with controlled access for key M&O components, followed by broader availability to the E2E architecture. Towards the [HEX225-D26], a detailed performance evaluation of the IF is planned, towards highlighting in a comprehensive way its role in managing complex and multi-domain scenarios.

Figure 7-5 System's components interaction with the integration fabric

The PoC domain, illustrated in Figure 7-6, exemplifies the seamless integration of automation, advanced connectivity, and human oversight, establishing a robust framework for use cases that combine autonomous system capabilities with human intervention. This PoC incorporates key 6G enablers into a 5G-connected cobot platform, exposing both software services and hardware resources to support intelligent, adaptive operations. The primary objective of the platform is to bridge the physical world with the evolving 6G architecture, specifically through the implementation of a ZSM-enabled cobot use case. The testbed will test the performance of the IBN functions and network KPIs such as latency and throughput of the services deployed in the platform.

Figure 7-6 Cobot surveillance use case architecture.

Within this platform, two critical 6G enablers, CL Platform and Intent-Based Network-Intent Management Entity (IBN-IME), are responsible for interpreting and fulfilling user-defined intents. This process follows a structured sequence of steps, as detailed in Section 4.2.3 (E2E Intent-based closed loop coordination). The

system is optimized for continuous operation, ensuring that the cobot can execute a surveillance mission with zero downtime. Beyond task execution, the platform actively monitors key performance metrics, allowing the IBN enabler to assess and ensure intent fulfillment throughout the entire mission lifecycle. In this deliverable, several advancements to the platform are introduced to enhance its surveillance and control capabilities, with respect to the deliverable D2.4 [HEX224-D24]. A significant update is the integration of a Virtual Reality (VR) module, which interfaces with a digital twin of the surveillance environment. This digital twin provides a real-time representation of the operational premises, displaying critical information such as cobot location, live video streams, and sensor data. Furthermore, the VR application enhances user interaction by allowing remote manual operation of cobots when required. This capability ensures that human operators can intervene dynamically, providing direct control when autonomous functions need adjustment or oversight.

The upper section of the diagram depicts the server platform, which is deployed across multiple edge equipment, including a server rack and a Dell Workstation (Dell WS). The lower section focuses on two cobots, or task-oriented robotic units, equipped with the necessary hardware and software. A new VR module has been integrated into the system architecture, extending the system's functionality to support advanced use cases beyond those described in previous deliverables.

Each rounded box in the diagram represents core platform modules, encompassing servers and cobots. These modules detail the hardware and software components that enable the system's operation. The software stack is visually categorized using symbols for clarity. For example, blue heptagons denote software components associated with Kubernetes clusters. Below the dashed line, Kubernetes components are responsible for orchestration, while the pods above execute services tailored to specific use cases. Additional software modules are deployed using containerization technologies such as Docker or Virtual Machines (VMs). IBN enablers are deployed within VMs hosted on the Dell Workstation.

The central section of the diagram outlines the edge private network, which combines Ethernet LAN, WLAN, and a 5G network to interconnect system components. The 5G Standalone (5GSA) network includes an Open5GS core and a Nokia AirScale indoor Radio RAN. Cobots connect via indoor picocells operating in the FR1 band 78 (TDD) using Telewell modems. For VR platform integration, Wi-Fi is employed, as current VR headsets lack 5G connectivity support.

The VR module enhances the system's capabilities by enabling advanced surveillance and facilitating human interaction with the intent-based DSM. While the PoC prioritizes automation and declarative intent instantiation, human intervention remains critical in the event of anomalies. For instance, cobots autonomously patrol the premises, but an operator may decide to assume control using the VR headset and joystick, navigating the environment as if physically present. Once the operator's task is complete, the IBN system seamlessly resumes system control. To ensure safe operations, the IBN gives precedence to human commands over automated processes, thereby avoiding conflicting instructions that could pose safety risks. The VR system further supports human operators by displaying critical monitoring data, such as environmental metrics and cobot platform status. For example, operators can view battery charge levels to determine whether another cobot with higher battery capacity should be deployed.

The platform has also been updated with additional features, including the IF client on edge servers. This software module publishes monitoring data, such as battery status, to the IF (Kafka broker), facilitating cross-domain monitoring and orchestration. Furthermore, the cobot platform has been enhanced with Nvidia Jetson Orin Nano processors, improving system performance compared to previous iterations. For example, this PoC incorporates a 3D Laser imaging Detection And Ranging (LiDAR) for navigation instead of a 2D LiDAR (in PoC-B), enabling the cobot platform to process richer data for obstacle avoidance.

As with prior implementations, the PoC-C system will include monitoring of network and application performance, with particular focus on the application migration use case. Network latency and application throughput will be assessed using Qosium Scope [QOS-001] software, which facilitates network measurements between defined endpoints. In this PoC, the endpoints are the cobot and the edge servers, as depicted in Figure 7-6. This methodology builds upon prior performance evaluations (in D2.4), ensuring that the integration of new components and features aligns with the overarching system objectives. The KPIs measured in this PoC include network QoS, specifically latency and throughput of deployed services—such as VR-to-cobot communication and video streaming—as well as intent fulfillment delay. These metrics

provide critical insights into system efficiency and responsiveness, supporting the optimization of autonomous operations within the platform.

7.2.2 6G Radio and 6G device components of PoC-C

7.2.2.1 *Component-PoC #C.1: 6G-based sensing algorithms and concepts with real-time performance*

The advent of 6G networks introduces advanced sensing capabilities that transcend traditional communication, offering transformative potential for industrial environments such as factories and warehouses where cobots operate alongside humans. Leveraging bistatic and multistatic sensing mechanisms, 6G networks enable real-time detection and localization of both connected agents, such as cobots, and non-connected entities, including human workers. This dual capability (i.e., detecting both connected and non-connected entities) enhances the safety of confined industrial spaces by integrating sensing with communication. For instance, while cobots benefit from precise positioning through 6G network connectivity, the challenge lies in accurately tracking non-connected agents like humans who move dynamically in the environment. Real-time sensing algorithms, as exemplified in WP4, D4.5 [HEX225-D45], address this by providing continuous updates on the location of non-connected agents, transmitting their live positions to the cobots. This ensures a cohesive, adaptive system where cobots can make informed navigational decisions, minimizing collision risks and fostering a safer interaction between humans and machinery. These sensing systems can support cobot-powered operations, such as the inventory management scenario, by enabling cobots to autonomously navigate and interact with objects while accounting for human presence, ultimately enhancing both operational efficiency and workplace safety. Results that will be included in [HEX225-D26] will focus on the detection performance.

7.2.2.2 *Component-PoC #C.2(a): AI-native air interface*

In this PoC, the target is to demonstrate the practical feasibility and performance gain of an end-to-end learned transmission link. The setup was described in detail in [HEX224-D43], and essentially it consists of an Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM)-transmitter utilizing a machine learned constellation, which is transmitting data to an ML-based receiver (DeepRx). The constellation and DeepRx are learned jointly with simulated data to communicate without any DMRS pilots, which results in increased spectral efficiency. The target of the PoC is to validate that this results in higher throughput also with real equipment and with real channels.

As described in [HEX224-D43], the PoC has been implemented with GPUs such that the Tx and Rx algorithms are executed on the GPU and the resulting digital baseband signal is fed to an SDR, which acts as the transmitter and receiver, using either physical antennas for the over-the-air measurements, or a channel emulator for the emulated lab experiments.

The PoC was tested in two different setups: through a channel emulator, and over-the-air inside the laboratory. The channel emulator experiments were repeated with three different mobility levels, corresponding to pedestrian, car, and train scenarios. Moreover, each measurement was also repeated with non-ML algorithms, which correspond to a 5G air interface. The highest throughput gain of 30% is achieved with the highest velocity scenario (train). With lower velocities, the throughput gain is in the order of 15-20%. The gain is mostly caused by the reduced overhead of the AI-based approach, as it has been trained to communicate without DMRS pilots. Since the proposed approach achieves similar bit error rate performance without the DMRS overhead as the conventional approach achieves with DMRS, a higher spectral efficiency is achieved.

In the over-the-air measurements, a throughput gain of 19.2% was achieved, which is similar to the low-velocity pedestrian scenario in the channel emulator experiments. This also demonstrates that the proposed approach performs with true physical radio channels.

7.2.2.3 *Component-PoC #C.2(b): ML-based channel state feedback compression in a multi-vendor scenario*

The target of this PoC is to demonstrate that cooperative AI-based techniques can improve the spectral efficiency and accuracy of channel state information feedback compared to legacy CSI schemes. This PoC focuses on sequential and separate AI-based techniques that do not require sharing proprietary AI models. The setup, detailed in [HEX224-D43], involves an AI/ML algorithm running on the device to encode/compress the CSI for transmission. At the gNB, a reciprocal AI-based technique decompresses the CSI. Together, those two

AI algorithms can improve CSI resolution for a given number of bits, or equivalently, reduce overhead for a fixed CSI resolution.

A testbed for this PoC has been implemented, and an evaluation of the downlink throughput gain was conducted in a lab testing environment to evaluate performance at varying Doppler frequencies. A gNB and a UE device were connected through an 8x4 channel emulator. The ML models were trained with lab collected samples. To evaluate performance at varying Doppler frequencies a channel emulator was used with a specified fading tapped delay line type A channel. The downlink throughput was measured with a full buffer data traffic.

Results show that ML-based CSI produces a more accurate beamforming as it can achieve, on average, a ~14% DL throughput gain over the baseline CSI feedback method.

In the context of cooperating autonomous robots, the benefit of ML-based channel state information feedback is to provide improved CSI, leading to higher beamforming gains, or, reciprocally, to reduce the CSI feedback overhead (i.e., reduced number of bits) compared to legacy schemes.

7.2.2.4 Component-PoC #C.3: Cellular-backscattered zero-energy devices

3GPP has recently introduced a study item on Ambient Internet of Things (AIoT) [38.769], exploring the feasibility of a novel IoT connectivity solution that significantly reduces complexity and power consumption compared to existing 3GPP LPWA technologies such as NB-IoT and LTE-MTC (machine type communication). Backscatter radio emerges as a promising candidate for enabling zero-energy AIoT devices. Unlike traditional radio-frequency identification (RFID) systems or AIoT approaches that rely on dedicated continuous carriers to illuminate the backscatter device, cellular backscattered zero-energy devices (ZEDs) harness existing cellular signals and receivers to interpret backscattered communications, integrating seamlessly with the cellular ecosystem.

In PoC C.3, a cellular-backscattered ZED was demonstrated using a 4G LTE system. In the downlink scenario, CRS were utilized by the UE for channel estimation. The ZED employed backscatter communication with Frequency Shift Keying, utilizing frequency shifts below the maximum Doppler shifts tolerated by the system. This caused the ZED to appear as an additional multipath component at the receiver, distinguishable from natural multipath components in the Doppler frequency domain. In the uplink scenario, the UE utilized Sounding Reference Signals, which enabled the base station to perform channel estimation. Similarly, the ZED was detectable in the Doppler frequency domain of the channel estimators. The feasibility of this concept has been demonstrated by PoCs using commercial LTE downlink signals [HEX2-LWK+24] and open-source implementation of UE channel estimator as the receiver [HEX2-LRJ+23]. Further details of the PoC can be found in Section 7.1 of [HEX225-D55].

Figure 7-7 ZED assisted cobot positioning.

The concept of a crowd-detectable zero-energy device involves the use of backscatter-based ZEDs to support applications such as indoor navigation and logistics [HEX2-PBR+22]. When a mobile phone comes within proximity to a ZED, it can detect the device's presence and demodulate its transmitted message. ZEDs can function as replacements for RFID tags, enabling mobile phones to perform asset tracking. Moreover, if the

location of a ZED is predefined, it can serve as an alternative to Bluetooth beacons, providing accurate indoor positioning and allowing mobile devices to localize themselves effectively, even in complex indoor environments [HEX2-YBP+24].

In 6G cobot applications, ZEDs can be utilized in a similar manner. They enable the radio modem at the cobot or base station to localize the cobot based on its proximity to ZEDs. In logistics applications, such as warehouse automation, ZEDs can serve as replacements for RFID tags, allowing cobots and the network to detect and identify parcels efficiently. If cobots are equipped with ZEDs, they can be detected and identified by other cobots even if they are powered off helping the system to improve overall energy efficiency. Figure 7-7 illustrates the ZED-assisted positioning concept. The cobot transmits data to the network, while the ZED embeds position references into the channel, enabling enhanced localization capabilities.

Cellular backscattered ZEDs can be integrated into the overall 6G architecture in two ways: by utilizing existing reference signals and data transmissions, as demonstrated in this PoC, or by designing new reference signals specifically for reading ZEDs. While the latter approach could enhance ZED performance in terms of range and data rate, it would introduce additional signalling overhead, which must be carefully considered in system design.

7.2.2.5 Component-PoC #C.4: End-to-end extended reality

In modern factory and warehouse environment, cooperating autonomous robots are increasingly used for various complex tasks. These battery-powered devices communicate with one another and other machines for safety and cooperation. They rely on sensors, such as cameras and LiDARs, to enable computer vision algorithms at regular intervals for navigation and positioning tasks. These sensors are also essential for cobots applications, such as object detection and object avoidance, as they operate alongside humans, other robots, and equipment.

One challenge for these devices is the processing of computer vision algorithms locally while maintaining a low power consumption. This is crucial to limit the battery size and provide compact form factor and ensure optimal operation time.

Additionally, VR-controlled (teleoperating) robots, where a human operator remotely controls the robot's movement to complete various tasks, have been proposed [PGB+21]. This approach requires the robot to transmit the sensor data to the operator and receive control commands in real time. Similarly to the cobots case, this requirement is crucial to limit the battery size and ensure optimal and timely operation for VR-controlled robots.

Scalable Compute offers a potential solution to address those challenges by offloading heavy processing tasks, such as vision-based processes, to a dedicated remote server. The cobot uploads sensors inputs and, in return, receives the corresponding positioning, object detection information (or other cobots required inputs). This approach reduces the power usage at the device while still providing the necessary computer vision results for the cobots operation.

In addition to power saving gain, Scalable Compute for cobots and VR-controlled robots, enhances capacity, service availability and coverage by optimally adjusting resource allocation based on the system capabilities. For cobots, it can switch to local computing on the device when remote server offloading is not available.

7.2.2.6 Component-PoC #C.5: Flexible modulation and transceiver design

The vision of 6G encompasses a vast array of demanding scenarios, requiring highly adaptable and efficient communication systems. Rather than designing radios with rigid hardware and signal processing capabilities tailored to extreme cases, a more pragmatic approach is essential. This approach involves developing a flexible and reconfigurable platform for holistic radio design evaluation, allowing dynamic adaptation to diverse requirements.

In this context, the goal of this PoC (Figure 7-8) is to develop a flexible transceiver system, as outlined in [HEX2-BCN+24]. Flexibility in this context refers to the ability of the system to adapt to different requirements dynamically without changing the default static system configuration. The choice of parameters is decided at runtime and remains adjustable in real time. There is a wide range of available waveforms, modulation and coding schemes, as well as signal processing algorithms to choose from. Figure 7-8 presents an overview of the flexible transceiver and its components, including:

- USRP devices: 4 USRP X310 are used for signal generation and reception.
- Controller: NI PXIw-1082 Chassis with NI PIXe-8133 embedded controller running LABVIEW software, being responsible for forwarding data streaming and control signals. During the runtime, the radio transmission parameters are adjusted dynamically.
- RF frontend: A variety of frontends can be utilized to radiate/receive radio signals that are generated/processed by the USRPs.
- Host: A computer running an API that generates control signals to manage the flexible transceiver. It supplies input data samples to the transceiver and receives output data samples from it.
- Reference (not represented in the schematic): A satellite receiver Meinberg 10 MP provides a 10 MHz reference signal to the USRPs and a 1-pulse-per-second signal for synchronization.

Figure 7-8 Flexible transceiver system schematic

7.2.2.7 Component-PoC #C.6: Radio propagation measurements to collect data for radio channel modelling

In factory settings where cobots operate, reliable and high-throughput wireless communication is essential for seamless operation and minimizing downtime. The industrial environment often features reflective surfaces and fast-moving obstructions, creating rich and dynamic multipath components and potential signal blockages. Conducting radio propagation measurements in these conditions is crucial for developing accurate site-specific channel models. These models allow for realistic link simulations that can predict performance metrics such as throughput and latency. Furthermore, channel models can also be used to simulate sensing, which is critical for cobot use cases where environmental awareness and adaptive operation are important. Section 2.3 of [HEX225-D45] analyses sub-THz channels in a factory hall and warehouse and provides path loss model parameters. Additionally, these measurements help create radio coverage maps that indicate signal strengths and identify dead zones. Such information is vital for network planning to optimize the placement of access points and other infrastructure to ensure robust and continuous connectivity.

7.3 PoC-driven components' mapping to the E2E system blueprint

Figure 7-9 illustrates the components of system PoC-C to the E2E 6G system blueprint, showcasing their alignment with the project's key design principles.

The Hexa-X-II architecture integrates a comprehensive set of system and component PoCs elements (represented by the purple rectangles), which work together to enable advanced functionalities across diverse applications such as cobots, intelligent automation, and real-time decision-making. At the application level, components like the trigger/UI provide intuitive user interaction, while video streaming, sensor data exposure, and device status modules ensure real-time access to critical information such as visual feeds, processed sensor data, and operational device conditions. Aggregated compute resources and pre-processed sensing data further optimize the availability and usability of computational and sensory inputs for demanding applications.

Within the network function layer, and the beyond communication services, the AIaaS framework delivers powerful AI-driven capabilities, supporting real-time decision-making and optimization. Advanced 6G functionalities are represented by components such as the 6G RAN and other NFs, which enable flexible topologies, AI-native air interfaces, and optimized transceiver design for efficient communication. These are

further enhanced by innovations like AI-based sensing algorithms, flexible modulation techniques, and precise radio propagation measurements, all developed under the System-PoC framework.

The integration fabric plays a critical role in seamlessly connecting devices, compute, and storage, enabling smooth communication and resource orchestration. M&O modules, along with AI-driven closed loops ensure the dynamic allocation of network and computational resources, while the trust evaluation function and synergetic monitoring safeguard the system by continuously evaluating trustworthiness and performance.

Figure 7-9 System PoC #C components mapped to earlier version of E2E 6G system blueprint [HEX224-D24]

7.4 Conclusions

The final E2E system-level validation phase design represented a critical milestone, focusing on experimental-based assessment design to validate the architecture’s robustness and readiness for future real-world deployment. This phase consolidated the system and component PoC design and implementation specifications, with system PoC-C aligning with advanced 6G radio and device technologies alongside advanced application features in the context of cobot-based manufacturing and logistics use cases, flexible network topologies, real-time orchestration, and trust evaluation mechanisms. Advanced application features such as intent-driven workflows, autonomous resource allocation, energy-aware dynamic AI offloading, as well as dynamic multi-stakeholder service coordination are incorporated and will be showcased in [HEX225-D26].

The primary outcomes highlighted the successful implementation of advanced application features, demonstrating the system’s capacity to support complex use cases like collaborative robotics and immersive environments. The design and implementation incorporate new devices with energy harvesting capabilities, key enablers such as advanced M&O enablers, the system’s integration fabric, the intent-based management framework, AI-powered closed-loop automation, as well as new APIs leveraging exposure of AEP layer capabilities, such as QoD and device status/density.

Future work will focus on leveraging the afore-presented PoCs towards a comprehensive assessment phase against the project’s established KPIs and KVIs, which will be reported in the WP2 final deliverable [HEX225-D26].

8 E2E system design qualitative assessment

This chapter presents a qualitative assessment of the 6G system design conducted within Hexa-X-II, focusing on achieving objectives 2 and 5 of the project. Objective 2, “Description of the blueprint and system validation of the environmentally, economically and socially sustainable 6G platform”, is addressed through the development of a comprehensive 6G platform blueprint, including architecture, interfaces, protocols, and an analysis of E2E system-level resilience, security, and privacy. This deliverable focuses on the design aspects of the system, with system validation to be reported later upon completion of the system PoCs [HEX225-D26]. Objective 5, “Efficient network realization, implementation, and management”, is addressed in the context of “Service orchestration aspects for the 6G platform”, specifically through the exploration of intent-based E2E service management automation. This approach, seen as a key component of the 6G system, also contributes to the achievement of objective 2 by enhancing the overall efficiency of the 6G platform.

The chapter delves into assessing the following aspects: the design of the 6G platform including the architecture, interfaces, and protocols, how these critical aspects of E2E system-level resilience, security, and privacy are covered in the 6G platform, the design of an intent-based E2E service management automation framework and conclude by the analysis of the technical aspects of the 6G platform that need to be considered in standardization activities.

8.1 Blueprint of 6G system design

The design of the 6G platform was guided by a comprehensive, continuous iterative system design methodology, employing both top-down and bottom-up approaches. The top-down approach involved multiple iterations of the system blueprint and completed with specific view that details specific aspects of the 6G system, outlining key functional blocks and key interfaces. Simultaneously, a bottom-up approach was employed, where enablers were developed from individual work packages, addressing various aspects of the 6G system. These enablers were then analysed for seamless integration into the 6G E2E system blueprint, utilizing a knowledge graph-based approach for enabler selection.

Recommendations generated during this process provided valuable feedback to the technical work packages, aiding in the refinement of enablers and contributing to the iterative enhancement of the overall E2E system blueprint. The technical aspects of the blueprint, in terms of functionalities, protocols, and interfaces, have been analysed to determine their alignment with the system requirements outlined in section 2.1. In Table 8-1, the system blueprint is then evaluated against the architectural design principles reminded in section 2.2, ensuring its adherence to these guiding principles. The assessment considers the blueprint’s impact on sustainability values, evaluating its contributions to economic, environmental and social sustainability. The analysis identifies relevant developed enablers that support these aspects of the blueprint.

Table 8-1 Alignment of the system blueprint design with the architectural design principles and the sustainability objective

System blueprint key aspects	Fulfilled main design principles	Economic sustainability	Environmental sustainability	Social sustainability (inclusion & trustworthiness)	Related enablers (examples)
Application enablement platform	1, 2, 7, 8	Reduces integration costs, simplifies communication, offers open-source platform	Aggregating capabilities from different NWs can lead to more efficient use of resources by reducing redundancy	Making 6G capabilities accessible to a wide range of developers and users can potentially promote digital inclusion	App-NW interaction, third-party services, application-layer BCS optimization, management capabilities exposure
New services (sensing, compute, AI, etc)	1, 2, 7, 8	Accelerates time-to-market, cost-effective and scalable AI access, optimizes resource utilization	Promotes energy efficiency, resource sharing, algorithm optimization	New services like JCAS can help in optimizing network deployment, potentially extending its coverage to underserved area, improving people safety and social well-being, and environmental monitoring; AIaaS supports more personalization and can improve digital inclusion. CaaS can enable the development of applications that promotes inclusion	JCAS protocols, signalling and procedures, compute protocols, signalling and procedures
Multi-stakeholder support	2, 4	Seamless integration of edge, core, and cloud resources, ensuring optimal resource utilization and service delivery	Reduces energy consumption and possibly lowers operating costs, benefiting both network operators and other resource/service providers	Encourages collaboration and reduces barriers to entry for various stakeholders	Multi-domain, multi-cloud federation, federation manager, third-party resource control separation,
Flexible access and topologies	3, 4, 5	NTN: Cost-effective deployment, flexible topologies, use of non-terrestrial nodes; Multi-connectivity reduces complexity by	NTN: reduces the need for terrestrial nodes and their connections, enabling ad-hoc deployment and potentially reducing power consumption;	Achieves a ubiquitous network, extending network access and service coverage to the entire globe, including remote and rural areas; UE-formed subnetworks can extend network coverage, particularly in areas	NTN integration, subnetwork management node, UAV assisted flexible topologies network of network, multi-

		simplifying architectural options, leading to faster time-to-market	Multi-connectivity allows reusing of existing infrastructure	where a direct connection to the base station is not available; Flexible topologies, such as subnetworks, enhance network resilience and security	connectivity, E2E context aware management
PHY layer and radio protocols	9, 5, 10	Spectrum sharing and coexistence: Reduces deployment costs, efficient spectrum use	Adaptable to future technologies and diverse use cases, with a flexible protocol stack operation, modular components, and the integration of new capabilities like JCAS, NTN, and AI-ML.	Resilient and reliable protocols, ensuring network availability and dependability, privacy and security in radio protocol design, ensuring user data protection and fostering trust in the 6G network	RRC design, modular user plane design, data recovery, ciphering and integrity protection, mobility procedure harmonization, low-latency random access, SoC architecture tailored to a microkernel-based OS, multi-source energy harvesting and power management, intelligent wake-up
Pervasive AI/ML frameworks	2, 4, 5, 6	MLOps reduces costs, accelerates time-to-market, improves decision-making, enables scalability, and mitigates risks; offers tools for efficient ML model lifecycle management	By leveraging AI/ML algorithms for network operations, the framework can help in reducing energy consumption in the network	Includes privacy-preserving data collection and training protocols, ensuring trusted distributed AI/ML applications development.	Machine learning operations, energy-aware tinyML applications
Pervasive data framework	2, 4, 5, 6	Reduces operational costs, optimizes data management processes, speeds up insights generation, and fosters collaboration and innovation	Promotes energy efficiency, resource optimization, cloud adoption, data reduction, and enables remote work and collaboration	Promotes responsible data usage by ensuring data quality, and accessibility and containing data privacy-preserving mechanisms	Monitoring and telemetry framework, DataOps, data fusion mechanisms based on telemetry data

Pervasive security, privacy and resilience	5, 6	<p>Reduces cost from security breaches and cyber-attack, minimizing downtime.</p> <p>Provides competitive advantage, attracting customers and partners</p>	Promote energy aware security protocols	<p>SPR framework facilitates transparency, accountability, and trustworthy AI/ML, fostering user trust and confidence in the 6G ecosystem;</p> <p>LoTAF, as a neutral service, helps users assess the trustworthiness of network services, thanks to informed decision-making power;</p> <p>Resilience is achieved through closed-loop automation for security management, including what-if scenarios, and NDT environment.</p>	Confidential network deployment, quantum-safe cryptography, level of trust assessment function, JCAS security and privacy, trustworthy AI, trust management, secure and scalable SoC architecture tailored for trustworthy AI/ML
Pervasive M&O	1, 2, 4, 6; 9, 10	Cost-efficient operation, multi-agent systems, decentralized orchestration, resource sharing, reduced operational expenses	Promotes use of edge and extreme-edge resources, reduces data interchange with core networks, minimizes data centre size, Reduces resource usage through AI/ML-based control algorithms	Orchestration over the cloud continuum increases network availability and reliability, decreases end-to-end latency, promotes digital inclusion, ensures optimal application deployment, balances latency, energy consumption, and resource availability while ensuring network security	Multi-X orchestration, multi-agent system for multi-cluster orchestration, Real-time Zero-touch control loops automation and coordination system, AI/ML-based control algorithms for sustainability, Network digital twin creation mechanisms, Intent based manager enablers

The 6G system interface and protocols build upon the existing 5G protocols and operations, to minimize the need for new standardization efforts, leveraging the current ecosystem of devices and infrastructure. Motivation and details of RAN and core interfaces are reported in [HEX223-D3.2], [HEX224-D33] and [HEX225-D35]. Key aspect is a Low Layer Split likely considered in the modularized RAN. The N2 interface for 6G is expected to evolve to handle the demands for a more cloud friendly environment. Interface and protocols between the UE and RAN are detailed in [HEX223-D22], [HEX224-D23] and in section 3 of this deliverable. 6G radio protocol is envisioned as an evolution of 5G, using what has worked well in 5G as baseline, while improving designs based on 5G learning, and supporting new capabilities. Proposed enhancements over 5G radio protocols (in section 3) relate to the user plane protocols, the mobility procedure, and interactions between applications and the network. The integration of additional 6G capabilities, such as Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS), Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN), and AI-ML, is analysed within the radio protocol design (in section 3). This integration necessitates the extension of current procedures, the updating of reference signals, and the addition of new functionalities for communication between the user equipment (UE) and the network.

JCAS integration requires protocols and procedures detailed in [HEX223-D32], [HEX224-D33] and [HEX225-D35] for transfer sensing measurement data to sensing processing entities in the 6G system responsible for processing and aggregation of the sensing measurement data. While the impact of sensing on the RAN-CN interface is still under investigation, it may involve a new interface for a data plane.

The proposed compute offloading architecture framework is designed to “loosely integrated” in the cellular network, thus making it less disruptive to existing cellular standards, allowing for faster time to market realization. This approach avoids significant changes to RAN and NAS protocols. Detailed procedures for offload node discovery, node registration and offload procedures are outlined in [HEX223-D3.2], [HEX224-D33] and [HEX225-D35]. Network signalling needs to support proposed procedures, requiring potentially novel or extension of existing interfaces to interact with the network, e.g., via AF and the NEF.

For AI/ML integration, new APIs, protocols, and standards are essential for seamless data collection and AI services lifecycle management and integration with existing architectures. It should address a current lack of standardization in this area.

The 6G system external interfaces are designed to provide abstracted interfaces and intent based interfaces. Exposed 6G capabilities and interfaces, such as CAMARA, are available on the NBI of the Application enablement platform layer for applications provider developers and vertical customers to easily access and utilize the 6G capabilities. Management capability exposure and programmability, via intent-based interfaces, enables the exposure of services allowing for greater control and customization of the network.

Different procedures, comprising protocols, functions and APIs, are being enhanced to address security, privacy and resilience (SPR) concerns. These enhancements, outlined in section 4 and in section 8.2, comprise the application of quantum-safe cryptographic procedures, especially in the service exposure APIs. Mechanisms related to physical layer security (like the secret key generation protocol) aim to secure RAN protocols. Procedures for improving JCAS security and data privacy are under development. Additionally, frameworks for trustworthy AI such as FASIL for the security & privacy in federated learning, are being explored.

8.2 Security considerations for 6G enablers

The integration of advanced enablers in the 6G ecosystem requires rigorous SPR measures to ensure the reliability and trustworthiness of the overall system. This implies a bidirectional relationship between enablers and the SPR controls discussed in this and previous deliverables, with these enablers playing a key role in support of SPR objectives and, conversely, acting as the main consumers of the features provided by SPR controls. This section highlights key enablers, beyond those specific ones considered in Chapter 5, analysing their roles in achieving SPR objectives and using SPR features: crypto primitives, AAA, data privacy, trustworthiness assessment, resilience evaluation, etc. The key enablers supporting SPR objectives are listed in Table 8-2, while the enablers that could be consider consumers of SPR controls are included in Table 8-3.

Privacy-enhanced solutions are critical for managing contextual information, mobility procedures, and sensing data. Enablers must ensure accountability, transparency, and security in processes like intent translation, provisioning, and multi-domain federations. Incorporating security automation and closed-loop coordination is essential to address vulnerabilities and maintain system resilience. Enhanced privacy controls, such as those for threat mitigation, safeguard against unauthorized access and reinforce trustworthiness.

Robust and trustworthy AI mechanisms should be integrated, accompanied by privacy-enhanced data management and mechanisms to ensure CIA and AAA properties across network functions and connectivity options. Security automation in edge computing environments and accountability for shared data in federated domains are crucial to maintaining data integrity, reliability, and system trust.

Security is a foundational requirement for system trustworthiness, particularly in sensing and positioning frameworks. Measures like jammer localization with high accuracy and availability mitigate vulnerabilities and bolster trust in sensing results and data ownership. Comprehensive security must also be addressed in Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS)-assisted transmissions and other advanced communication technologies.

In resource-constrained and ultra-low-power environments, enablers should include energy-aware security protocols and integrated trust mechanisms. RIS can be leveraged to enhance the security and privacy of radio links while aligning with context-aware security. Trustworthy SoC architectures must prevent data leaks, ensure resilience against attacks, and provide robust foundations for tiny ML applications.

These considerations establish a unified framework for enhancing privacy, security, and resilience, aligning with the advanced demands of next-generation network environments.

Table 8-2 Roles of enablers directly relevant to SPR objectives

WP CATEGORIES	ENABLERS	ROLE DESCRIPTION
WP2 ❖ 6G protocols and radio interface ❖ E2E Service management automation ❖ SPR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Data recovery mechanisms •Ciphering & integrity protection •Enhanced Special Cell (SpCell) change with UE initiation •Pcell recovery •Data-driven mobility <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Intent and TLA management •LoTAF •Notary service •Trustworthy AI 	<p>These enablers collectively ensure the resilience, availability, confidentiality, and integrity of systems and data. They enhance data recovery mechanisms to maintain resilience against loss or corruption, ensure secure communication through ciphering and integrity protection, and provide robust mobility management to support seamless transitions and uninterrupted service. Additionally, they strengthen system reliability by enabling primary and secondary cell recovery processes, ensuring continuity for critical use cases. Together, these functionalities contribute to achieving the CIA triad, AAA model, data privacy, and overall trustworthiness in network operations.</p>
WP3 ❖ AI enablers for data driven architecture ❖ Architectural enablers for new access and flexible topologies ❖ Network Beyond communications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •MLOps •DataOps •Intent-based management (Zero Touch) •Multi-connectivity •JCAS protocols, signalling, and procedures 	<p>These enablers focus on enhancing privacy, security, and system resilience in distributed and interconnected environments. They provide privacy-aware data collection and management through MLOps and DataOps, ensuring the protection of sensitive information during processing. Intent-based management introduces automated operations to reduce reliance on manual interventions. Multi-connectivity strengthens system resilience and availability by utilizing diverse network paths for uninterrupted service. Moreover, JCAS protocols, signalling, and procedures improve the privacy and security of sensing data management. Together, these enablers reinforce the CIA triad, AAA model, data privacy, and overall trustworthiness in advanced network systems.</p>
WP4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Trustworthy radio solutions 	<p>These enablers emphasize enhancing trustworthiness, security, and privacy in radio communications.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Radio design enablers for flexible, inclusive, sustainable and trustworthy radio ❖ Joint communications and sensing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security and privacy (jamming attack detection, key generation for encryption, etc.) 	<p>Trustworthy radio solutions leverage PLS techniques and key generation mechanisms to establish secure communication channels, ensuring trust in the system. Security and privacy measures, such as jamming attack detection and secure key generation, further support authentication, confidentiality, and protection against threats. Together, these enablers strengthen system resilience, support the CIA triad, and ensure robust SPR controls in radio communication environments.</p>
<p>WP5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Trustworthy specialized SoC design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secure and scalable SoC architecture tailored for trustworthy AI/ML 	<p>This enabler focuses on creating a secure and scalable SoC architecture designed for trustworthy AI/ML applications. It supports secure execution environments and safeguards sensitive data, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of AI/ML processes. By addressing both security and scalability, this enabler contributes to achieving robust SPR controls, enhancing trustworthiness, and supporting the CIA triad in advanced computational systems.</p>
<p>WP6</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Security framework ❖ AI/ML algorithms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Third-Party resource control separation system • User-centric service provisioning system • Trust management functionalities • Secure AI/ML-based control for intent-based management system. • Real-time zero-touch control loops governance and coordination to increase automation in the execution of actions for security incident recovery plans and orchestration of security services. • Privacy protection for data analytics system 	<p>These mechanisms focus on strengthening SPR controls by ensuring robust security, privacy, and trustworthiness in advanced network systems. They implement granular access controls to manage tenant permissions, enhance user-centric service delivery with data protection and SLA assurance, and establish trustworthy communication paths for sensitive data. Additionally, they safeguard AI/ML-based systems through privacy defence mechanisms and protections against model attacks, ensuring the integrity and reliability of automated network management. Collectively, these solutions address critical aspects of security, privacy, and resilience, supporting the CIA triad and AAA model in 6G environments.</p>

Table 8-3 Enablers consuming SPR control functionality following the interface modes described in section 6.1 of [HEX224-D23]

WP	ENABLERS
<p>WP2</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radio protocols for beyond communication • Sensing and positioning • Data fusion mechanisms based on telemetry data • Intent Conflict Administration • Human-machine intent interface design • Declarative Intent Reconciliation • Intent Reporting • Third-party services
<p>WP3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AIaaS • Architectural means and protocols • 6G Network modularization • E2E service design in modular 6G network of networks • Exposure and data management, and integration and orchestration of extreme edge resources in the computing continuum multi-domain/multi-cloud federation
<p>WP4</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RIS-assisted transmission

WP5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RIS system integration • Energy-aware protocols • RAN scope dedicated connectionless design • Energy-aware tinyML applications
WP6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-agent system for multi-cluster orchestration • Decentralised orchestration • All the overall functionalities in the smart management framework [HEX225-D65]. • Network programmability system

8.3 Intent-based E2E service management automation

Based on the work done in previous deliverables and in this deliverable, especially in chapter 4, the following conclusions identify how the objectives are reached from an IBM point of view.

Regarding the objective that focuses on “**Blueprint and system validation of the sustainable 6G platform**”:

- The presented work on IBM and multi-stakeholders’ scenarios outline an intent-based service management framework supporting single and multi-domain environments, emphasizing scalability, flexibility, and automation. The final architecture highlights how service intents are processed, negotiated, and executed across diverse administrative domains, ensuring seamless E2E service provisioning and fulfilment.
- To this end, two models (aggregation and federation) are proposed for managing services in multi-stakeholder scenarios, which ensure dynamic, inclusive, and cooperative resource management while maintaining trust and autonomy among stakeholders. Furthermore, the inclusion of intent-driven trust management mechanisms supports enhanced security and resilience, ensuring that services meet stringent requirements for trustworthiness and privacy in 6G networks.
- Regarding to the alignment with 6G requirements, the proposed intent-based service framework aligns with 6G goals of enabling sustainable networks, by supporting features such as closed-loop coordination (i.e., the system takes care of managing the used resources and solve possible issues, being time efficient by not waiting the human decision), adaptive resource allocation (i.e., the system is able to decide the right amount of resources), and robust conflict management in intent negotiation (i.e., the system guides the requester towards possible solution based on its resources knowledge, leading to a faster resolution than if the requester has to check the whole situation).

The work done on IBM allowed to clearly evolve the blueprint presented in D2.2 [HEX223-D22] by integrating new technological enablers and innovations.

Regarding the objective that focuses on “**Efficient network realization, implementation, and management**”, the key conclusions are:

- The introduction of automation in intent-based management reduces the dependency on human operators, enabling efficient resource management and service deployment tailored to 6G service requirements. In addition, features such as intent fulfilment management and evaluation workflows ensure that resources are allocated dynamically based on real-time demands and KPIs, enhancing network efficiency.
- The use of closed-loop coordination and monitoring mechanisms ensure continuous optimization of services, addressing evolving network conditions. Moreover, the designed architecture considers integration with existing and evolving standards (e.g., TM Forum, 3GPP, ETSI ZSM), facilitating interoperability and practical implementation.
- In terms of sustainability, specific enablers and workflows focus on minimizing environmental impact, such as leveraging energy-efficient management strategies. This allows to emphasize on adaptability, which ensures that the proposed systems can integrate emerging 6G services, such as sensing and AI/ML capabilities, alongside legacy system support.

These conclusions demonstrate how the IBN-related work done addresses the foundational aspects of developing a comprehensive, efficient, and trustworthy 6G platform while ensuring its practical realization and alignment with future network demands.

8.4 Assessment on standard-related impact

The 6G platform necessitates standardization efforts to address key technical aspects, including service exposure, security, privacy, and resilience, as well as intent-based E2E service management automation and radio protocols. The platform must effectively expose its capabilities and services to a wide range of applications and devices, encompassing both traditional communication services and “beyond communication” services. Standardization contributions are being made to 3GPP SA5 for network as a service and management services exposure, and to 3GPP SA2 for evolving the NEF and potentially the CAPIF to support the exposure of beyond communication services.

Addressing the new security threats (delta 6G threats) posed by the increased complexity, reliance on AI, and integration of novel cloud in 6G networks, necessitates a robust security, privacy, and resilience framework. Standardization efforts include contributions to 3GPP SA3 for SPR enablers (distributed and trustworthy AI, quantum-safe cryptography, distributed ledgers, remote attestation, context-awareness), 3GPP SA5 for trustworthy AI-based control to enhance the management plane, ETSI-MEC and ETSI-NFV for addressing security and privacy threats, mitigation techniques, and the use of network data telemetry for threat evaluation, ETSI SAI for understanding risks associated with widespread AI use in networks and developing relevant proofs of concept, and the IETF security area for attestation techniques, quantum-safe technologies, and automated certificate and key management procedures.

6G networks require highly automated and intelligent management to handle the complexity of managing diverse services and resources, and intent-based management automation framework is a promising approach. The architecture functionalities of the intent DSM defined by Hexa-X-II, their enablers, and the usability of standardized intent APIs on NBI and east/west are actual and potential contributions to the main standards addressing intent-based management and autonomous networks. Standardization efforts include contributions to 3GPP SA5 for intent-based management, including intent generic models and solutions in TS 28.312 [28.312], ETSI ZSM ([ZSM011] and [ZSM016]) for intent-based management, including intent life-cycle specifications and the use of smart contracts for supporting the governance of intent-driven closed loops, and TM Forum for the usability of Intent standardized API, from abstraction definition to implementation possibilities on how to use to translate intent into SLA requirements [TMFIO24].

Development of 6G radio interface and protocol design heavily relies on 3GPP specifications. These specifications detail how devices and RAN nodes communicate and operate the radio interface (the Uu interface). To support the solutions explored in this project, as described in chapter 3 and in previous deliverables [HEX224-D23] and [HEX223-D22], 3GPP 6G specifications impacts will spread across the specifications defining the radio protocol layers such as SDAP, PDCP, RRC, RLC, MAC and overall RAN aspects. Examples of changes in different aspects of the 3GPP specification are:

- The protocol design, e.g., how to encode the protocol, how to design the configuration messages, etc.
- The services the protocol layers support. For example, where AN security resides and how it is provisioned, services provided to upper layer or expected from lower layers, etc.
- The specific protocol procedures or behaviour the protocol has. For example, introducing new information elements to be exchanged, reusing or introducing events/behaviours for additional purposes while procedures are running, etc.

As far as open-source related activities are concerned, the Hexa-X-II PoC activities have extensively leveraged open-source tools for network orchestration, security, AI-driven management, and real-time monitoring in 6G validation. OpenAirInterface [OAI24] has been a key tool for evaluating RAN performance and architecture optimizations. Kubernetes has played a central role in orchestrating distributed workloads and AI applications, while Prometheus has been used for performance monitoring and observability. Apache Kafka has supported secure network exposure through mutual TLS authentication and REST API integration, and Qujata [QUJATA] with the Secure Post Quantum eRa cluster has been used for post-quantum cryptographic evaluations. TeraFlowSDN, CockroachDB [CKRDB], and OpenConfig have facilitated network slicing and automation, with gNMI telemetry enhancing real-time observability. Hexa-X-II has also initiated contributions to open-source tools such as TeraFlowSDN and Qujata. However, as activities on PoCs are still a work in progress, further details and final conclusions on open-source contributions will be included in [HEX225-D26].

9 Conclusion

This deliverable D2.5 concluded most of the work performed during the Hexa-II project by the WP2, especially on the design of an end-to-end 6G system architecture. The upcoming [HEX225-D26] will be the final WP2 document to conclude the evaluation and proof-of-concept activities.

This deliverable D2.5 has therefore explored the design of a 6G platform allowing for the realization of E2E services and relying on key design principles and requirements prioritizing economic, environmental and social sustainability (including trustworthiness), as well as the seamless integration of advanced functionalities among multiple actors of the 6G ecosystem. A main result in this deliverable is the description of the final Hexa-X-II 6G E2E system blueprint from a high-level and overarching view point, but also the details of specific system views, highlighting key differentiators of a 6G system on radio interfaces and protocols, new 6G services such as sensing, compute and AI as a service and their exposure, the multistakeholder dimension of such E2E 6G services, and pervasive functionalities in order to embed AI/ML mechanisms and security, privacy and resilience functionalities (Chapter 6). This resulting E2E 6G system blueprint and the detailed specific views also demonstrate the strong collaborative work beyond the WP2 partners to synthesize the technical outcomes from other Hexa-X-II WPs in an integrated and homogeneous way.

More specifically, D2.5 has extended intermediate results from previous WP2 deliverables, on several aspects:

- **Prioritization of sustainability:** The design of the 6G system emphasizes sustainability across environmental, economic, and social dimensions. This includes energy-efficient communication principles, minimal material wastage, and considerations for societal impact. In close collaboration with the Hexa-X-II WP1, Chapter 2 outlines the design principles, emphasizing the importance of sustainability in the 6G system and explains how Key Values and Key Value Indicators have been integrated in our enabler selection methodology to cover this new dimension.
- **Evolution of radio interfaces and protocols:** Extending results described in previous deliverables, Chapter 3 has proposed several innovations on radio user plane protocols, mobility procedures and application-network interactions. Key enablers including 6G MAC retransmission techniques, asymmetric radio link control, and modular user plane design are described to contribute to the overall efficiency and flexibility of the 6G system. It also provides an analysis for ensuring E2E support of new 6G capabilities like JCAS and the evolution of existing 5G capabilities like NTN and AI-ML for 6G. While trying to extend existing 5G radio protocols (e.g., innovating on top of current 5G protocol functionalities, optimizing 5G protocol operation) to limit the impact on standards and UEs, proposed innovations help at solving issues identified in 5G and leveraging on new opportunities resulting from new 6G capabilities.
- **Intent-based service management:** Chapter 4 has explored the design of an intent-based E2E service management automation framework, which enables efficient and intelligent orchestration of services and resources. A particular focus has been made on describing the architecture components, management models, and E2E services required to meet the demands of 6G multi-stakeholder scenarios where intent-based technologies are expected to be applied, comparing a more conservative approach (“aggregation” where each tenant is autonomous on the intent selection) with a more collaborative one (“federation” where automation is increased to globally optimize the intent management across domains). Details on enablers are also provided and grouped according to four main areas: a) intent provisioning and fulfilment, b) continuous evaluation to ensure the intent delivers as expected, c) managing intent-based closed loops, and d) incorporating trust parameters for secure and reliable network services. This framework is crucial for the scalability and automation of the 6G system.
- **Focus on Security, privacy and resilience:** The 6G system blueprint incorporates robust SPR measures to ensure the trustworthiness of the system. This includes integrating trustworthy AI mechanisms, privacy-enhanced data management, and secure communication protocols. Chapter 5 delves into the SPR aspects of the 6G system, highlighting the importance of trustworthy AI and transparent notary services. After identifying and addressing the *6G security delta* (the identification of specific threats and enhanced opportunities for detection and mitigation) in previous deliverables, this deliverable concludes the

consideration of this security delta and fulfils the objectives related to trustworthy networking, involving technologies with diverse TRLs.

- **Refinement of the enabler selection methodology:** While Chapter 6 primarily provides the 6G E2E system blueprint as explained earlier, it also describes how the enabler selection methodology has been continuously refined and improved, incorporating feedback from PoCs and incorporating new enablers as they mature. More importantly for a flagship project like Hexa-X-II, Chapter 6 has also identified and analysed complementary enablers from other SNS-JU projects, further enriching the 6G system blueprint and contributing to a more comprehensive and robust design. These complementary enablers are thus discussed, highlighting their potential contribution to the 6G system.
- **Update on the Proof of Concepts (PoC):** while [HEX225-D26] will conclude the validation and implementation activities for the WP2 and the whole Hexa-X-II project, this deliverable provides a detailed overview of the three iterations of the system PoCs (PoC-A, PoC-B, and PoC-C), and the demonstration of key functionalities, such as intent-based management, AI-driven sensing, and energy-efficient communication, giving practical insights on the feasibility of the proposed solutions. Chapter 7 also maps the implemented enablers of the system PoCs on the overall 6G E2E system blueprint to concretely instantiate the overall concepts.

Finally, as final deliverable on the Hexa-X-II E2E system blueprint, the document explores in the chapter 8 the assessment of the WP2 work, in particular with respect to the two related project objectives:

- **Objective 2: Description of the blueprint and system validation of the environmentally, economically and socially sustainable 6G platform**
 - **Blueprint of 6G system design:** The chapter highlights the comprehensive, iterative system design methodology employed, using both top-down and bottom-up approaches. As a result, key technical aspects of the proposed blueprint are analysed with respect to their compliance with the main design principles and with the economic, environmental and social sustainability objectives.
 - **Security considerations for 6G enablers:** It also discusses the security aspects of the 6G platform, emphasizing the importance of E2E trustworthiness across all domains and layers. This includes considerations for management and orchestration, AI/data frameworks, and control diagrams. It also considers enablers from all WPs and how these enablers participate (as provider or consumer) to the overall SPR functionalities of the 6G System.
- **Objective 5: Efficient network realization, implementation, and management**
 - **Intent-based E2E service management automation:** The chapter emphasizes how the intent-based service management framework contributes to efficient network realization, implementation, and management. It highlights features like closed-loop coordination, adaptive resource allocation, and robust conflict management in intent negotiation, all aligning with 6G goals of enabling sustainable networks, by proposing a system automatically tracking the usage of resources and self-correcting possible issues when possible or augmenting service requesters with relevant information for faster problem and/or conflict resolution. This framework emphasizes scalability, flexibility, and automation, ensuring seamless E2E service provisioning and fulfilment.
 - **Assessment on standard-related impact:** To allow highly flexible and dynamic services, involving multiple stakeholders and guaranteeing the E2E security, privacy and resilience, the 6G platform requires standardization efforts. The chapter analyses contributions made or being made at various standardization bodies and covering the exposure functionalities (3GPP SA2 and SA5), SPR functionalities (3GPP SA3 and SA5, ETSI-MEC, ETSI-NFV and ETSI SAI, IETF), intent and automation functionalities (3GPP SA5, ETSI ZSM, TM Forum) and 6G radio interface and protocols at the 3GPP.

The development of a sustainable 6G ecosystem is a complex and multifaceted endeavour. This deliverable has provided a comprehensive blueprint for the 6G system, outlining its architecture, interfaces, protocols, and key enablers. By prioritizing sustainability and intent-based management, the proposed 6G system has the potential to revolutionize communication and sensing capabilities, enabling a wide range of innovative applications and services. In each of the above technical dimensions, research and standardization efforts must be pursued to ensure the successful realization of this vision. For example:

- Future work is needed to achieve all the radio design principles and link these innovations to the 6G KVIs.
- Security vulnerabilities for the continuous intent generation and maintenance are still to be assessed and the development of specific policies for intent conflict resolution is still in its early stages.
- Controls and enablers to address the *6G security delta* need to be consolidated, in particular those remaining at an early TRL as discussed in Chapter 5.
- The proposed enabler selection methodology, introduced in the Hexa-X-II project could be extended and widely used by future SNS-JU projects and various stakeholders, including industry players, research institutions, and standardization bodies, to facilitate collaboration and ensure that the 6G system meets the needs of the wider ecosystem.

This deliverable thus provided a valuable foundation for future research and development activities, paving the way for a sustainable and trustworthy 6G future.

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Annex A Additional details on radio protocols

A.1 APP-NW interactions

A.1.1 Ad-hoc radio bearer and inline signalling

To give more details on the new mechanism, via inline MAC control element (CE) signalling in [HEX224-D23], Figure A-1 gives a visualization of the DRB setup proposal. This proposal would result in reducing the signalling overhead, and hence enhanced cell capacity and reduced latency, as well as enabling greater application-awareness and more UE intelligence.

Figure A-1 DRB setup example via ad-hoc radio bearer and inline signalling.

Now taking the proposed MAC CEs from Figure 3-11 in Section 3.1, further MSCs for DRB delta configuration and DRB release are introduced. Figure A-2 (a) and (b) gives an example for DRB delta reconfiguration, where the UE indicates “MAC CE for parameter reconfiguration” for LCID = 3 with the bitmap set to C0=1, C1...C6=0 and E=0. In this example it can be assumed that C0 refers to PDCP reordering timer, which is reconfigured to 40 ms in Figure A-2 (b). A last example is for DRB release in Figure A-3 (a) and (b), where the UE sends “Release MAC CE” for LCID = 3.

Figure A-2 DRB delta reconfiguration example: (a) message sequence chart, (b) MAC CE.

Figure A-3 DRB release example: (a) message sequence chart, (b) MAC CE.

For the proposed realization of ad-hoc bearer setup/release/reconfiguration via inline signalling using the SDAP layer and header, Figure A-4 shows the data flow with SDAP layer functionality split compared to the current NR status [38.323].

Figure A-4 Data flow for the proposed SDAP layer functionality split.

With the proposed SDAP functionality split and flow update in Figure A-4, updates for the SDAP header are needed to enable the inline signalling. Figure A-5 shows an example realization of SDAP header similar to that of 5G [38.323] with the addition of the Context ID octet of the preconfigured DRB setting to be used.

Figure A-5 Proposed UL SDAP data PDU.

A.1.2 UE quality level-aware scheduling

For our proposed two stage approach to overcome the shortcomings of the current QoS framework in Section 3.2, in Stage#1 - UE indicated quality-levels the UE agrees with the NW on multiple different quality levels that can then be used as a reference. Each quality level is defined by a set of parameters mapping to a certain QoS (e.g., packet size, packet rate, burst size, delay budgets, etc.). Note that the NW may reject the proposed levels and suggest different levels.

The different quality levels agreed upon between the UE and the NW in Stage#1 are then used as a reference for Stage#2 - level-aware scheduling. Figure A-6 gives an example MSC for a possible realization of Stage#2, where the NW is aware of the UEs quality level profiles and hence informs the UE on a regular basis about the quality level the NW is able to serve to this UE currently and/or in the future. This can be done along with the UL grant in the DCI or via DL MAC CEs, where additionally a validity time or window may be indicated. This information would then get propagated by the UE to the transport layer or running applications which can in turn use this information to generate the data based on the indicated quality level.

Figure A-6 Possible realization of stage#2 - level-aware scheduling.

A.2 Mobility procedures

A.2.1 Mobility procedure harmonization

The unified mobility procedure consists of three steps as can be seen in Figure A-7.

- **Pre-configurations:** network decides what candidate cells to prepare, e.g., based on UE measurement reports. For each candidate, network can configure triggering events (i.e., as in CHO). Network can configure target beams for pre-synchronization (e.g., TCI state configuration as in ICBM/LTM). All these configurations are provided in an RRC message. The configuration is updated (e.g., added or released) based on UE movement.
- **Pre-synchronization:** this step is mostly inspired by LTM, in which while the UE keeps the connection with the source cell, the network triggers the UE to synchronize to the candidate cell. For example, downlink pre-synchronization is triggered by the network to activate a TCI state associated with a target cell. Uplink pre-synchronization (e.g., UL TA acquiring) is triggered so that the UE transmits a random access preamble in the candidate cell. The command/trigger should also be in a RRC message. This DL pre-sync and UL pre-sync can also be autonomously triggered by UE (similar to LTM), e.g.,

UE keeps the DL pre-sync for measured SSBs (with good quality), and UE-based UL sync based on DL timing differences (assuming good synchronization between two DL signals).

- Execution: the mobility execution (i.e., mobility command) can be triggered by UE measurement events like A3 (CHO style), a special purpose RRC message to apply candidate configuration (LTM style), a special purpose RRC message that contains a limited set of configurations with a stricter processing time requirement, or the legacy RRC reconfiguration (e.g., L3 handover for candidates containing only pre-sync info or to override stored candidate configuration or only a small RRC configuration message). In this step, if the UL TA is acquired, the UE does not need to perform random access (i.e., RACH-less HO).
 - The legacy L3 HO is supported as “safety measure/fallback procedure”, e.g., for when things do not go as planned or the source and the target is from different vendors. It is also flexible and usable in all mobility cases.

Figure A-7 Harmonized mobility procedure

For a concrete example of a mobility scenario supported by this unified procedure and can represent how D-MIMO is deployed in practice. There is one baseband connecting to two radio units using lower LLS as shown in Figure A-8. Each radio unit is in a physical site. The coverage range of this baseband is, in this example, equivalent to legacy coverage of two base stations. Since there is only a single termination point (containing all protocol stacks (e.g., MAC, RLC, PDCP, RRC), it is possible and indeed preferable to not to reset the L2 user plane and not to perform security key update so as to reduce interruption time. The mobility command is also transmitted in a RRC message, but only a limited part of the reconfiguration is needed (e.g., RNTI, PDCCH common search space (CSS)). Thus, for this special purpose RRC message, a tighter processing delay requirement can be envisioned, compared to the relaxed RRC reconfiguration processing delay requirement (i.e., 10 ms – 16 ms) that has considered the worst-case scenario. Thus, there will be a much shorter interruption time.

Figure A-8 Mobility scenario between two radio units

A.2.2 Methods for cellular data transfer within connected measurements radio gaps

Figure A-9 below shows the potential realization of this approach in details. After UE is connected to serving cell, it receives the connected mode measurement configurations from NW at step 1, where frequencies F1/F2/F3 were configured to be measured. UE1 starts performing measurements according to the received configurations. At step 2, UE1 reports to the NW one of the detected cells, Cell A, on the neighbour frequency F1. The NW decides that data transfer can be exchanged with UE1 via Cell A, acting as DTMRG hosting cell, during the radio gaps assigned for F1 neighbour frequency measurements. NW decision could be based on various parameters, such as the amount of data pending transfer for UE1, the Cell A cell measurements. At step 3, NW RAN-BS1, serving UE1, requests from RAN-BS of Cell A (RAN-BS2) to exchange data with UE1 via Cell A, within a certain period that corresponds to the radio gaps that will be assigned for F1 measurements. Provided information may include the following:

- Cell A physical ID
- UE1 measurements for Cell A, based on data received from UE1 in the measurement report.
- UE1 measurement pattern for Cell A's frequency

At step 4, RAN-BS2 prepares the configurations required for exchanging data between UE1 and Cell A during the requested period that corresponds to radio gaps assigned for F1 measurement by UE1. Configurations could include:

- UE1 identity that shall be used while operating on Cell A, e.g., a new MG-RNTI to be used during data transfer via DTMRG hosting cell.
- Cell A physical layer configuration required to be able to perform data transfer.
 - May include information like cell A BeamID that shall be used (e.g., in case there are multi-beams reported, then hosting cell may choose the one to serve the UE, example based on beams load).

At step 5, the RAN-BS1 provides back the UE1 the configuration required to exchange data via Cell A during measurement gaps assigned for F1. At step 6, before the measurement gaps instances that shall be used by UE1 for measuring F1, RAN-BS1 may indicate to RAN-BS2 that in the next measurement gap instance, data transfer with UE1 via Cell A should take place. RAN-BS1 may provide to RAN-BS2 information like:

- Amount of UL/DL data required to be transferred.
- Latest UE1's Cell A measurements.
- Measurement radio gap start time and duration, if not previously provided.

At step 7, RAN-BS2 confirms back to RAN-BS1 and may provide information back to RAN-BS1 including:

- Amount of UL/DL bytes that could be exchanged with UE1.
 - For example, this could be based on Cell A radio resources availability within the next DTMRG instance.
- Optionally, the UL/DL grant information. This is applicable if:
 - This information was not already pre-configured as part of step#4
 - or if the UE is not required to listen for grants on Cell A (e.g., in 4G/5G, UE1 is not required to listen to PDCCH on Cell A)

At step 8, RAN-BS1 may provide UE1 information about the assignment of data exchange with Cell A in the next measurement gap instance, could be via one or more messages (e.g., 4G/5G L1 DCI messages). This message may contain:

- Indicating that next measurement radio gap instance shall be assigned for frequency F1 measurements, in case the measurement pattern for F1 was not pre-configured.
- The radio sources information via which the UE can transmit/receive data via Cell A.

At step 9, RAN-BS1 provides RAN-BS2 the DL data to be transferred to UE1, if DL data was planned for this DTMRG gap instance. At step 10, UL/DL data exchanged between UE1 and Cell A. At step 11, RAN-BS2 may provide RAN-BS1 the received UE1's UL data, if UL data was planned for this DTMRG gap instance.

Figure A-9: Detailed signalling aspects of DTMRG

A.2.3 Data driven mobility

Table A-1 contains the simulation assumptions for system level simulations. The UE initial location is set to $(x, y, z) = (-100, 800, 1.5)$ and the UE moves with 120 km/h into the tunnel. The tunnel length is set to 100 m such that the UE spends 3 seconds in the tunnel. The radio channel in tunnel is degraded such that it leads to radio link failures. The realistic data is used to model channel degradation in tunnel.

Table A-1 Simulation assumptions for throughput evaluation of contextual and baseline mobility events

Parameter	FR1
Deployment Scenario	Rural Macro single cell with distance-dependent LoS probability function defined in Table 7.4.2-1 in TR 38.901 [38.901]
Frequency Range and SCS	4 GHz; SCS: 30 kHz
System bandwidth	20 MHz
BS Tx Power	44 dBm
BS antenna height	35 m
Antenna setup at gNB	$(M, N, P, M_g, N_g; M_p, N_p) = (8, 4, 2, 1, 1, 2, 4)$, $(d_H, d_V) = (0.5, 0.8) \lambda$ 16 TX
Antenna setup at UE	$(M, N, P, M_g, N_g; M_p, N_p) = (1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 1)$, $(d_H, d_V) = (0.5, 0.8) \lambda$ 2 Rx
Spatial Consistency	Procedure A in 38.901 [38.901]
Measurement Periodicity	20 ms
Traffic	Full buffer
CSI Feedback periodicity	10 ms
UE Initial position	$(x, y, z) = (-100, 800, 1.5)$ m
UE trajectory	Linear trajectory with constant velocity UE is in car.
UE Speed	120 km/h
Tunnel center and length	Center: $(x, y) = (0, 800)$ m Length: 100 m Width: 80 m
Radio Link Monitoring (Reference from 36.839)	Qin: 2% Qout: 10% T310: 1s N310: 1 N311: 1

The channel degradation could be seen in Figure A-10. The serving cell RSRP drops by around 60 dB when the UE enters a tunnel, which leads to RLF in baseline mobility.

Figure A-10 Serving cell RSRP along with UE trajectory

The performance of contextual mobility is compared with the baseline approach, where the UE performs the reestablishment procedure. Different values i.e., 1000 ms and 1500 ms, are used to model the interruption time caused by the reestablishment procedure. In contextual mobility, the UE does not initiate the reestablishment procedure as the event e.g., Z2 is triggered and hence the T310 timer duration is increased. Table A-2 shows the interruption time and DL throughput with baseline reestablishment procedure with different interruption time and contextual mobility.

Table A-2 Service interruption time and average downlink throughput of contextual mobility and baseline approaches.

Procedure	Interruption time after the tunnel (ms)	Total Service Interruption time (ms)	DL Avg Throughput (Mbps)
Baseline 1000 ms interruption after tunnel	1000	4000	38.416
Baseline 1500 ms interruption after tunnel	1500	4500	32.000
Contextual mobility	0	3000	51.230

As seen from the table, in contextual mobility, the interruption time after the tunnel can be avoided by leveraging historical UE data and trajectory prediction. Therefore, the average DL throughput is also much higher than the baseline approaches. In addition, average DL throughput across different channel realizations is aggregated to compare the CDF of the different procedures, as seen in Figure 3-6.

A.2.4 Computation aware mobility

Figure A-11 shows the potential realization of this approach within conditional handover procedure with its impact on the RRC signalling and handover preparation and execution. At step 1, UE may inform the network that it needs to offload some operations to the network where xNodeBs can have different computation capabilities. At step 2, NW configures UE to report computation requirements to the NW (periodic or event-driven). The network configuration indicates also how can UE share computation requirements e.g., as a part of measurement report (option 1) or in a separate event (option 2). In option 1, UE may send the computation requirements forecast in RRC measurement report. This could be triggered by the movement of the UE to the cell edge. In Option 2, network may configure a separate event for computation update events based on its capability. The configured event may be event triggered or periodically sent by UE to the network and UE shares the computation requirement forecast with the Source xNB. After the step 3 (Option 1) or step 4 (option 2) in the figure, source xNB has information about the computation requirement forecast of the UE. In addition,

UE may decide the priority of computation offloading over communication link quality and share with the source xNB in step 3 or 4. The exchange of forecasted information can help network to perform proactive decisions and allocate computation resources for the expected UEs. Upon reception of the messages at steps 5&6, the target xNB(s) perform admission control using the information provided on the computation requirements of the UE. If the target xNB does not satisfy UE's required/anticipated computation requirements, it may reject the handover and inform the source xNB. The target xNB may still accept the handover of the UE, with the computations still being done at the source xNB compute resources, ensuring that the latency requirements with the extra hop(s) can still be maintained. At steps 7 and 8, the target xNB(s) sends a handover request acknowledgment including, configuration of computation events and available computation capacity. At step 9, the source xNB sends an RRC reconfiguration message to UE including the configuration of computation events of that prepared target xNB(s) and available computational resources of the prepared xNB(s). During handover execution, the UE may trigger xNB change condition based on either:

- A measurement event e.g., A3 event for handover execution is satisfied. (Legacy behaviour).
- A computation event indicating that the source xNB does not satisfy the computation requirements of the UE.
- On both measurement and computation events.

At step 11, once the conditional handover is triggered, the UE detaches from the source xNB and initiates connection establishment with the target xNB. At step 12, after the completion of handover, the target xNB may send the configuration of computation events to the UE. In this case, the messages on computation event configurations at steps 6 and 7 might not be needed. Steps 13 and 14, follow the legacy conditional xNB change procedure. At step 15, the source xNB may send the computation status to the target SpCell. This message contains intermediate computation results e.g., a partially processed image, etc.

Figure A-11 Potential realization of computation aware conditional handover

Annex B Complementary enablers

B.1 Complementary enablers from other WPs in Hexa-X-II

This section describes the enablers from other WPs not already described in previous chapters. These enablers may also be part of the enabler selection in Chapter 6 and the E2E service blueprint as well as specific system views.

Table B-3 Enablers from other work packages

Involved WP	Enabler name	Description
WP3	DataOps	The DataOps enabler [HEX223-D32, HEX224-D33 and HEX225-D35] contributes to providing procedures for ensuring data collection in a privacy preserving manner. This is achieved by introducing multiple architectural components (i.e., clients, aggregators, collectors and consumers) [HEX223-D32] that can be deployed flexibly in the cellular network. As an example, one of the possible deployment options consider the case where the different UEs are the clients, the NodeB acts as both an aggregator (i.e., leader) and a collector, while an independent ASP acts as the second aggregator (i.e., helper). Therefore, preserving privacy by separating shares in two different trust domains (i.e., NW and ASP). In this specific deployment it's evident from the proposed MSC in [HEX225-D35] that such deployment impacts the RAN with requirement on messaging exchange between the clients and the NodeB. Note that there are other deployment options that would impact the RAN in which the different functional entities are deployed at the different RAN nodes
	MLOps	MLOps offers a set of tools and methods for efficient management of distributed AI functions in 6G networks. These tools target to optimize the communication, computation, storage, and energy utilization across the distributed AI nodes
	AIaaS	An AI-native platform, integrated within the 6G network architecture, provides AI capabilities as services to support various applications, acting as a superset of MLOps features by incorporating all MLOps APIs along with additional APIs—such as data exposure and QoS—that enhance network capabilities and reinforce the vision of the mobile network as a platform.
	Interactions between modules	This enabler focus how different modules should interact. the modules are not limited to CN but also RAN and compute nodes. Assuming cobots will be connected to a network and using some service from an edge (i.e., connected to network), this enabler determines how the network internal interaction and data flow should occur.
	Design of a module	This enabler focus on how a module (or a 6G NF) should be designed, what would be the composition of an NF, what are the design principles, the granularity or different methods to create them. it directly impacts the network support to cobots as well as the relevant CP latency/signalling, energy etc.
	Modularization examples	In this enabler we have two major parts, focusing on the modularisation in the UP and in the RAN. Although this does not necessarily impact the cobot devices (UEs), it impacts how the network interacts and the latency and signalling. Note that this enabler also has impact in terms of the EE, so in a scenario where cobots are presented as an E2E service, this enabler will be a major energy efficiency part.
	Network of networks	The network of networks enabler [HEX223-D32, HEX224-D33 and HEX225-D35] contributes to creating a seamless and ubiquitous communication system with the use of terrestrial subnetworks and NTN. In the context of the <i>subnetworks</i> , the new UE role of a Management Node (MgtN) is introduced, which is associated with new functionalities that will

	<p>impact the radio protocols. A subnetwork is formed among mutually trusted UEs and is associated with the global 6G NW. The MgtN would be responsible for the coordination with the overlay NW on behalf of the UEs in the subnetwork. It would also be able to take over some responsibilities from the BS, as well as to support the UEs in the subnetwork with their RAN procedures (i.e., CP or UP). In, [HEX225-D35], further options for CP handling in subnetwork is presented to further detail additional architectural options to the initial proposals in [HEX223-D32, HEX224-D33]. One proposal is of MgtN aggregating the CP of the UEs, meaning that the UEs offload their CP or part of it towards the MgtN. At the same time, the SubNW uses the subnetwork CP between the UE and the MgtN, which is transparent to the NW and includes both the configuration and procedures within the subnetwork along with the offloaded UE CP information. Additionally, a further architectural option is proposed, where the UE offloads its CP to another UE without the BS's awareness. From all the above it's evident how the introduction of subnetworks can have a significant impact on the RAN interfaces and procedures</p>
Multi-Connectivity (MC)	<p>MC enables multiple frequency ranges by different physically separated nodes, the aggregation of different radio access technologies, carriers, and access networks. The aim is to increase the robustness and reliability, increased throughput. For 6G we propose only one option in the standard, taking the best from both DC and CA. This solution should however be based CA due to the inherent disadvantages of DC. A possible deployment for 6G MC is to use radio units connected to the same gNB using LLS, where the Radio units are not co-located. Further on, new procedures are proposed to support more robustness for CA by PCell recovery via Secondary Cell solution. Coverage extension or increased reliability via WLAN-based UE relay for remote UEs</p>
Context-aware management	<p>Mechanisms to allow each network component to dynamically adapt to the context to ensure the expected E2E QoS. Mission-critical operations, to reduce the network overhead and to allocate edge resources flexibly, ultimately improving the system performance by allowing multiple edge allocations and RAN slices</p>
Compute Offloading	<p>The emergence of new applications as well as new devices with varying capabilities, entails the need for the next generation networks to support <i>compute offloading</i> among other things, all the while maintaining and enhancing upon the legacy communication [HEX223-D32, HEX224-D33]. The compute offloading service enables moving computation from a mobile device to a network node with more suitable compute and storage capabilities. The proposed compute offloading architecture framework is loosely integrated in cellular network with no significant changes to RAN and NAS protocols, thus making it less disruptive to existing cellular standards, allowing for faster time to market realization. In addition, several procedures are detailed, for example on how to handle the offload node discovery, node registration and offload procedures.</p> <p>In [HEX223-D32], new functional nodes were introduced to enable the compute offloading procedure, namely offloading node (ON), computing node (CompN) and compute offload controlling node (CCN). Those nodes were introduced as functional entities that could be flexibly deployed anywhere in the wireless network. In [HEX224-D33], MSCs highlighting the interactions needed between the different functional entities for node discovery were introduced. Then the interactions between the different functional entities in the initial registration and computation offload procedure stages and the proposed interactions between the different functional entities were introduced in [HEX225-D35].</p>
JCAS architecture	<p>Enabling precise detection, monitoring, and analysis of the environment, sensing technologies may help enhance network performance and support a wide range of applications across various sectors. This enabler explores the fundamental concepts and technologies that drive the convergence of sensing</p>

		and communication, highlighting the optimization of resource utilization, the implementation of robust protocols, and the adoption of innovative approaches for autonomous environment mapping and navigation.
	Application-layer BCS optimisation	The enabler deals with the optimisation of the placement of the application functions (e.g., cobot-related autonomous navigation application function), consuming exposed resources via the AEP, towards minimising latency, maximising privacy and trust.
	Multi-domain/multi-cloud federation	This enabler deals with the architecture for cloud-native federation. Cobots may run in resources which belong to different providers and are federated
	Orchestration of the cloud continuum	Cobot functionality may be run in multiple hosting platforms across the cloud continuum, including edge and extreme edge (i.e., UEs). Orchestration of the functions and their placement is of paramount importance in this context.
WP4	Channel modelling at new radio frequencies	<p>The characterization of the radio channel is a crucial task when investigating use cases in new frequency bands, such as sub-THz and frequency range 3 (FR3). These efforts involve addressing several technical challenges to ensure accurate modelling and performance assessment. The key findings are summarized below, with additional details available in [HEX224-D43] and [HEX225-D45].</p> <p>For frequencies above 100 GHz, phenomena like coating and scattering effects significantly alter reflection coefficients, making classical Fresnel equations inadequate. To address this, ray-tracing methods should include a correction factor for reflection gain, tailored to distinguish between indoor and outdoor scenarios. Additionally, simplified models are being developed to account for molecular absorption loss, a crucial factor at these high frequencies.</p> <p>In the industrial domain, sub-THz dual-band characterization is essential for IIoT applications. Extensive efforts have been devoted to channel measurement campaigns and model fitting to capture the propagation characteristics at different frequencies in selected industrial environments.</p> <p>Based on measurement data, several studies have focused on updating the 3GPP TR 38.901 model, introducing a new modelling approach and redefining channel parameters [38.901]. Furthermore, a ray-launcher tool has been accordingly calibrated, enabling realistic simulations for link budget evaluation and coverage analysis.</p> <p>FR3 is emerging as a promising mid-spectrum band, offering a balance between bandwidth and propagation characteristics. However, it remains largely untested for wide-area mobile communication, especially under non-line-of-sight (NLOS) conditions, where propagation losses are influenced by foliage and urban obstacles. To address this, wideband channel sounders have been deployed for extensive measurement campaigns, providing insights into propagation behaviours in this band.</p> <p>A further consideration is the sub-THz link budget's implication for electric and magnetic field compliance. Future 6G radio equipment will need to comply with the electric and magnetic field regulatory requirements, necessitating a balance between performance and compliance.</p>
	Waveforms modulation and enhancement	<p>Enhancements in waveform design and modulation techniques have been thoroughly addressed and documented in [HEX224-D43] and [HEX225-D45]. The main conclusions are outlined below.</p> <p>The investigation of existing 5G NR waveforms and numerology for new frequency ranges, including sub-THz, has focused on the impact of non-linearities under different parameterizations. This analysis enables the</p>

		<p>assessment of phase noise and cyclic prefix effects, providing critical insights into the optimal parameterization of waveforms for sub-THz communications.</p> <p>To address challenges such as phase noise and Doppler effects, alternative constellations like polar formats have been explored, with their efficacy validated through simulations. Additionally, over-the-air sub-THz transmissions have been conducted to evaluate the feasibility and performance of hardware-friendly waveforms, focusing on metrics such as peak-to-average power ratio and error vector magnitude.</p> <p>Simulation results highlight the resilience of zero-crossing modulation combined with 1-bit analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) to hardware impairments, demonstrating their potential to enable energy-efficient, non-linear components for sub-THz frequencies.</p> <p>Moreover, waveform and modulation enhancements have been proposed, including adaptive multicarrier modulation with a new parameter for managing power spectral density. Finally, new 3GPP-compliant 5G LDPC matrices have been designed to optimize the power consumption</p>
	MIMO transmissions	<p>The investigation on MIMO transmissions has addressed various aspects related to distributed MIMO (D-MIMO), massive MIMO, multi-user, and system complexity. A detailed description can be found in [HEX224-D43] and [HEX225-D45], with a summary provided below.</p> <p>For D-MIMO systems, different beamforming strategies, including coherent and non-coherent transmissions, have been studied. These approaches demonstrate effectiveness in addressing challenges such as blockages, varying levels of CSI availability, and signalling constraints. Additionally, the performance of D-MIMO systems has been enhanced through various architectural innovations, including the use of movable and rotatable antennas to improve coverage and efficiency. The integration of analogue fronthaul has also been explored, providing accurate synchronization and improving signal quality. Furthermore, the optimization of JCAS beamforming within D-MIMO systems has been identified as a key area for future research.</p> <p>In the context of massive MIMO, hybrid beamforming architectures and deployment strategies have been proposed to enhance energy efficiency. A link-level signal model has been developed to optimize hybrid beamforming for these systems.</p> <p>Data-driven channel estimation techniques have also been explored, enabling robust performance in scenarios where pilot-based CSI is unavailable, or channel conditions are highly dynamic. This facilitates the design of precoders to optimize performance in multi-user MIMO systems.</p> <p>Finally, low-complexity architectures utilizing 1-bit ADCs and digital-to-analog converters have demonstrated significant potential in enhancing energy-efficiency in massive MIMO systems.</p>
	RIS-assisted transmission	<p>The investigation of reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS) has primarily focus on topics detailed in [HEX224-D43] and [HEX225-D45], which are summarized below.</p> <p>Signal-level analyses demonstrate that RIS can significantly enhance coverage, particularly when direct propagation paths are highly attenuated. Passive RIS improves coverage effectively, and active RIS provides even greater gains. Integration into distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) systems highlights the potential of RIS to enhance coverage probability and energy efficiency.</p> <p>Reflection modulation techniques via RIS show promising performance improvements for single and multi-user multiple-input single-output downlink compared to beamforming approaches without RIS. Investigations of RIS-assisted integrated access and backhaul networks indicate enhanced resilience in backhaul links supported by RIS. While RIS can improve service coverage,</p>

		<p>network-controlled repeaters (NCRs) often outperform RIS in this regard. However, NCRs come with higher costs and lower energy efficiency than RIS, emphasizing a trade-off between performance and financial viability.</p> <p>In terms of standardization, NCRs are specified in 3GPP Rel-18. This might provide a framework to leverage existing signalling specifications for integrating RIS into 6G systems. Overall, further studies on control mechanisms, feasibility, and pre-standardisation activities are still required.</p>
WP5	6G radio transceiver design	<p>This enabler encompasses critical components for the design and manufacturing of novel 6G radio transceivers for FR1, FR2, FR3, and sub-THz frequency bands. The enabler studies the challenges of efficiently operating at those frequencies, such as addressing nonlinearities in amplifiers, optimizing power efficiency, and supporting diverse communication ranges. Moreover, RIS design for FR1 and FR2 is considered, addressing the standardization of control interfaces and hardware prototyping. Specifically for sub-THz transceivers, their ability to unlock new spectrum bands for ultra-high data rate communication is studied. The power consumption of the components comprising high-frequency wideband transceivers is characterized and optimized. Hardware non-idealities are studied and modelled, with special focus on power amplifiers and phase noise at sub-THz frequencies. Solutions to make integration of sub-THz transceivers practically feasible are proposed, including phase noise reduction based on delayed carrier frequency delivery, irregular antenna arrays to simplify chip-to-antenna routing, and designs based on cost-effective resonant tunnelling diodes. Detailed results and conclusions can be found in [HEX225-D55].</p>
	AI- and signal processing accelerators	<p>The enabler explores the SoC components enabling 6G signal and AI processing. First, a reference design for an AI accelerator is proposed, specifically a Neural Processing Unit (NPU) optimized for on-chip inference tasks. This design integrates a lightweight RISC processor core based on the Rocket Chip RISC-V implementation, along with a tightly coupled memory subsystem, direct memory access units, and a 2D processing element (PE) array for parallel computation. To study the performance and energy needs of signal processing, scalable hardware processing elements are developed. These processing elements are optimized for key operations such as multiplication, addition, and accumulation. Mapping signal processing tasks to these operations helps to analyse the processing needs and energy use of transmitter and receiver signal processing chains. Detailed results and conclusions can be found in [HEX225-D55].</p>
	Energy harvesting & power management circuits	<p>This enabler addresses challenges in energy harvesting for 6G devices, proposing a novel energy combiner circuit. Unlike traditional power management units, this approach allows developers to choose power management units suited to their specific needs while efficiently combining energy from multiple harvesters. The energy combiner utilizes temporary energy buffers and a custom switching regulator to transfer harvested energy to a supercapacitor, ensuring reliable energy storage and utilization. Detailed results and conclusions can be found in [HEX225-D55].</p>
	Low-power protocols for energy neutral devices	<p>This enabler considers low-power protocols for low-power and energy neutral devices. It considers optimized channel access methods, based on the fast uplink grant principle, focusing on scalability and energy consumption. A scheduler for goal-oriented sensor reporting, can reconstruct sensing events at the edge nodes based on a more limited set of sensor reports, resulting in substantial energy savings. Finally, user plane protocol enhancements are proposed to enable energy neutral device communication over legacy network infrastructure. The introduction of an N3 tunnel between the RAN and UPF avoids the need for PDU session establishment, saving significant resources. Detailed results and conclusions can be found in [HEX225-D55].</p>

WP6	User-centric service provisioning system	Specific purpose system for the specific stakeholder's scope. It enables personalised service provisioning for tenants based on specific SLAs, ensuring optimal Quality of Experience and secure service access. It also provides customised service policies and closed-loop automation to monitor SLAs for tenant-specific service management and SLA enforcement [HEX225-D65].
	Secure AI/ML-based control for Intent-based Management System.	Specific purpose system for the specific stakeholder's scope. It ensures that decisions inferred by AI/ML models deployed on agents are resistant to adversarial attacks and are not manipulated or compromised. This enabler provides network service assurance and security functionalities and is considered to contribute to the effectiveness and resilience of next-generation networks by facilitating real-time and automated network management with enhanced security [HEX225-D65].
	Privacy protection for data analytics System	Specific purpose system for the specific stakeholder's scope. It is intended to ensure that sensitive data is protected while still enabling effective analysis and decision-making. The enabler proposes a privacy management function and a privacy operation function. The privacy operation function would be responsible for making data privacy-preserving using policies created by the privacy management function, which is responsible for selecting the privacy operation to be used by the privacy operation function and the generation and distribution of key pairs for privacy operations, which take place at local and central analytic functions in a federated learning setting [HEX225-D65].
	ML-based configuration recommender for energy savings algorithm.	Specific purpose algorithm for the specific stakeholder's scope. It aims at providing a solution for the energy reduction of the future 6G networks with the aid of AI/ML and without degrading the network performance. It provides a generic structure where different types of algorithms (e.g., AI-based or rule-based algorithms) targeting this objective can be deployed and implemented. It contributes to energy savings by targeting both network services and network resources configuration [HEX225-D65].
	Multi-domain federated learning algorithm	Specific purpose algorithm for the specific stakeholder's scope. It provides a way for operators to leverage rich data sources to provision resources for secure decentralised AI training network services for verticals. It also facilitates network service provisioning and compute resource assurance and configuration by directing the orchestration of resources to deliver on AI model training services, providing a structured process to enable the network deliver novel AI model training services using network edge compute and storage resources [HEX225-D65].
	Multi-agent RL for adaptive scaling algorithm.	Specific purpose algorithm for the specific stakeholder's scope. It provides a multi-agent system approach for service autoscaling and migration across the computing continuum. It is intended to improve automation in scaling actions while respecting SLAs. This specific algorithm follows the approach of the multi-agent system for multi-cluster orchestration Overall M&O Solution by assigning agents to interconnected services. Decisions are taken based on analysing service performance in terms of latency and resource consumption values supporting variable workloads and focusing on service assurance for seamless operation [HEX225-D65].
	Explainability for RL-based control algorithm.	Specific purpose algorithm for the specific stakeholder's scope. It provides human-interpretable explanations for decisions made by reinforcement learning AI models to enhance their trustworthiness. Provided explanations can be validated through automated procedures and/or human inspection to help detect anomalies, such as adversarial attacks, and contribute to network services assurance. The solution relies on eXplainable AI algorithms to analyse the reinforcement learning models and produce explanations [HEX225-D65].

B.2 Complementary enabler from other SNS projects

B.2.1 6G radio design

From radio interface and protocols perspective, CENTRIC studies complement the work done in Hexa-X-II [HEX224-D43] for the support of AI/ML capabilities in the radio operation. Examples of CENTRIC technical innovations are the studies on novel waveforms for sub-THz band and short packet transmission, methods for user-tailored modulation learning, AI-empowered MIMO communications, AI methods for emerging multiple-access protocols for specialized services, methods for transmission-mode selection in dense deployments, RRM techniques for cell-free massive MIMO targeting electric and magnetic field exposure reduction, or multi-objective AI methods for RRM performance-energy trade-offs, among others [CEN24-D34].

For TN-NTN integration from radio design perspective, SNS JU project ETHER aims to provide a holistic approach for integrated terrestrial-non-terrestrial networks. Within the use case-specific requirements ETHER considers, there are many related to TN-NTN mobility management and handovers, key areas to consider for radio design. A couple of the challenges under study in ETHER are related to current 3GPP system deficiencies when considering NTN and the lack of efficient handover control mechanisms for integrated TN-NTN. To address the identified challenges for TN-NTN integration, ETHER introduces eight main technical innovations in their research in [ETH24-D24]. From radio perspective, three of those complement the research done in Hexa-X-II for TN-NTN integration. Those three technical innovations in ETHER are: i) direct handheld device access at the Ka band from LEO satellites distributed LEO swarms, ii) unified waveform design, and iii) horizontal/vertical handovers including AI-based handover control mechanisms.

The first innovation, direct handheld device access at the Ka band from LEO satellites distributed LEO swarms, aims to achieve 100% coverage KPI, even in cases where the communication with a terrestrial small cell is unfeasible, by using swarm formations of LEO satellites. This innovation complements the work done in Hexa-X-II for network of networks with NTN and could benefit from new notion of "coverage fairness" as metric discussed in [HEX224-D33].

The second innovation, unified waveform design, identifies scenarios incorporating communication with fast-moving flying nodes (e.g., LEO satellites) where Orthogonal Time-Frequency Space modulation, being resilient to Doppler frequency shifts, is much more beneficial than OFDM. This innovation goes much more in detail for NTN, not being considered in this project.

The third innovation, horizontal/vertical handovers including AI-based handover control mechanisms, has two main considerations: i) further advances common handover implementations to consider additional parameters such as time availability and network sustainability, and ii) more elaborated criteria for performing horizontal and vertical handovers in hybrid TN-NTN platforms by leveraging AI-based algorithms to make the process autonomous. This AI-based control mechanism targets handover management optimization. To perform the optimization, the relevant data should be provided to the decision engine. The data sources for AI-based handover control are going to be discussed in future ETHER work. Regarding the location of the decision engine, ETHER framework will support two optional scenarios: i) local handover decision at the source gNB, or ii) handover decision engine externalised outside gNB or consulted "on the fly" with an external functional instance. This research complements Hexa-X-II TN-NTN mobility enablers in [HEX224-D43] and A1aaS in [HEX224-D33].

B.2.2 Network of networks

The concept of Network of Networks stands for the integration of multiple networks or network segments to provide connectivity services. This includes examples such as Body Area Networks, Car Area Networks, Non-Terrestrial Networks, multi-connectivity proposals or subnetworks.

B.2.2.1 NTN

One of the main challenges of satellite communication networks includes managing the dynamic links between the Ground Station (GS) and satellites (SAT), which are crucial for transmitting application images and managing tasks but are limited by satellite mobility and intermittent connectivity. Additionally, resource management within satellites is a complex task due to fixed, pre-defined hardware capabilities and the inability for satellites to dynamically compile or adjust applications, constraining operational flexibility. Coordination

via the GS-SAT link allows for some remote management of satellite configurations; however, issues such as failure reporting and self-healing capabilities are limited until the next GS contact. To address these challenges, ETHER project proposes the satellite communications architecture to integrate into the NFVI with the ETSI framework [ETH24-D24]. This integration enhances the efficiency and reliability by employing a distributed, multi-node cluster approach managed by a GS, where SATs function as cluster nodes with distributed master systems to enhance availability and resilience, using ISLs for improved connectivity and latency management. The project uses Kubernetes to perform complex container management tasks, such as automatic deployment, scaling, and management of containerised applications, which makes it ideally suited for the dynamic and distributed nature of integrated TN-NTN systems. In addition to that, ETHER project provides flexible payload design with the adoption of SDR platforms to flexibly adapt satellite payloads to operators' services.

The ADROIT6G project studies how different satellite topologies enhance coverage and facilitate low-latency applications. Here they consider three main topologies such as Bent-pipe topology, Regenerative topology, and Inter Satellite Link (ISL) topology [ADR24-D22]. ADROIT6G expects to assess whether the edge computing on the satellites can support the applications by splitting the impact of satellite communications E2E path, and how such benefits will depend on the satellite topology or the capabilities of the satellite links.

B.2.2.2 Subnetworks

The 6G-SHINE project [6GS24-D4.2] focuses on realizing a flexible subnetwork architecture with the introduction of dynamic roles of UEs and the integration of the UEs forming a subnetwork with the overlay 6G network, realizing part of the overall envisioned 6G network of networks [HX225-D35]. In particular the project proposes flexible subnetwork architecture, a set of light-weight procedures and interfaces and exposure functions for subnetwork and local communications enablement. To achieve that a new UE role is introduced, namely management node (MgtN). The MgtN has high capabilities and is able to overtake the control of subnetwork operations enabling the formation of a subnetwork as well as supporting low-capability (LC) as well as other high-capability (HC) devices within the subnetwork. Additionally, a lighter subnetwork communications architecture is proposed, to save power and reduce the required complexity of the UEs that are part of the subnetwork. Moreover, architecture enablers for advanced RRM mechanisms and goal-oriented communication within the subnetwork and in cooperation with the 6G parent network is presented. Finally, interfaces and exposure functions to extend the communication and computing continuum from the subnetwork level to the cloud is introduced.

B.2.3 Deterministic networks

The project PREDICT-6G focuses on the development of deterministic networks, considering reliability, time sensitiveness and predictability as its main pillars [PRE23-D12]. PREDICT-6G focuses specifically in 3GPP and WiFi technologies [PRE23-D21], considering a multi-technology, multi-domain solution, providing E2E deterministic services even spanning non-deterministic networks. It's main building blocks are the Multi-domain Data plane [PRE23-D21] and AI-enabled Control Plane [PRE23-D31]. The MDP is based on a Detnet layer-3 approach which interacts with technology specific enhancements. Among those, PREDICT-6G proposes and demonstrates [PRE23-D22] new TSN capabilities for IEEE 802.11, and AI-based TSN enhancements for 3GPP. In the control plane, main innovations cover the predictability of the network, where an approach based on digital twinning has been followed [PRE23-D22].

B.2.4 Device/hardware design for 6G networks

To introduce novel end-to-end hardware co-design solutions for energy-efficient AI-native transceivers, the CENTRIC project designs a novel AI computing hardware and real-time optimization [CEN24-D34]. This includes multiple innovations such as digital CMOS in-memory computing architecture, mixed analog-digital memristor-based in-memory computing architecture, computing platform designs based on neuromorphic computing paradigms and the methods for GPU acceleration of deep learning algorithms.

From the project TERA6G [SNS-TERA6G], two enablers are identified as the complementary enablers related to device and hardware design for 6G networks. The first is about unlocking 2D antenna arrays. To increase the emitter power (beam forming) and also to control the radiation emission directions (beam steering), TERA6G develops antenna arrays operating in the millimetre and THz frequency ranges using integrated RF photonics techniques. In addition, the revolutionary use of an array of dielectric rod waveguide antennas allows

to radiate directly from the photonic integrated circuits, minimizing the losses to the antenna. The second is about Photonics-enabled control of the RF beam directions through network orchestration commands. TERA6G introduces a photonic approach to generate the RF signals in the millimetre and Terahertz frequency ranges that can perform the optical beamforming and beam steering functions in the optical domain, through an optical beam forming network. This is the most efficient approach when aiming at a multi-beam system, where a Blass matrix converts the optical signals of each beam into the delayed version required for each antenna element.

6GTandem project [6GT24] aims to provide uniform ultra-high throughput coverage, off-load lower frequency bands and provide new services such as high-resolution sensing and positioning in high traffic, densely populated areas by using a thin and light dielectric waveguide (i.e., a plastic fibre) to distribute a sub-THz RF signal through a daisy chain connection of low-power antenna units (AUs), following the radio stripe concept. By combining lower frequency bands with the sub-THz bands in a dual frequency distributed MIMO 6G mobile network, 6GTandem will develop technologies that benefit from the attractive capacity that sub-THz communications offer. One key innovation from 6GTandem is the novel design of low-cost easy-deployable sub-THz infrastructure for distributed MIMO systems to support joint communication, high resolution sensing and cater to high resilience and reliability.

B.2.5 Data-driven architecture (DataOps, MLOps and AIaaS)

The project ADROIT6G presents CrowdSourcing AI or Machine Learning as a Service (MLaaS) approach in distributed systems [ADR24-D32]. The concept entails collaborative training of ML models and the execution of inference tasks through those models, using distributed techniques and enabling a continuous cycle for learning creation, validation, refinement, and transfer of ML models across domains. Crowdsourcing also saves computational power and memory associated with ML training where a domain requiring an ML model can retrieve a pre-trained model and further refine it using its own data. Moreover, the concept uses meta-learning techniques to support the discovery and selection of the best available ML model for the execution of a given task and for the training of a model to establish the best solution for the amount of energy consumed by ML model training/updating/inference and the quality of the decisions made. To orchestrate the training of ML models and to obtain inference, the concept uses multiple computing entities (devices, network nodes) or different (computing/networking) resources and techniques including cooperative and collaborative training of models, transfer and federated learning, intelligent model selection, and intelligent placement and management of AI/ML services in distributed execution environments.

B.2.6 Compute offloading techniques

The ADROIT6G project uses the concept of user equipment as virtual base station for computing to advance cellular network for 6G [ADR24-D32]. This concept represents a transformative approach where individual mobile devices are not only consumers of network resources, but also contributors to the network. The so-called BDI (Beliefs – Desires - Intention (BDI)) agents proposed by the ADROIT6G project are focused on intelligent network optimization including resource scheduling and offloading. This includes a novel dynamic energy-efficient edge resource management strategy based on stochastic optimization that uses a goal-oriented compression mechanism where UEs can opportunistically make decisions on whether to process inference tasks locally or offload them to the edge server. The ADROIT6G enhancements advance the state-of-the-art in context-aware prediction for offloading by implementing models capable of learning joint representations from multi-input data sources. These enhancements are crucial in supporting other learning algorithms by providing larger, more robust datasets, especially in environments where multi-modal sensor data collection may be unreliable.

B.2.7 Management and orchestration

ADROIT6G project proposes distributed closed-loop automation for AI-driven management and orchestration [ADR24-D41]. The AI-driven management and orchestration framework proposed by ADROIT6G implements the logic and AI-based algorithms for the end-to-end, automated management of vertical services over an inter-computing and inter-domain network infrastructure. Here, the network and compute resources are allocated and dynamically managed across domains using AI-based methods, and services are continuously and intelligently monitored and optimized using AI-driven closed-loops and zero-touch principles.

The SNS JU project PREDICT-6G proposes the integration of an AI/ML framework in the M&O domain control loops of 6G architecture to enable the management of the complete lifecycle of AI/ML models, from design and training to deployment and serving in production environments at different domains [PRE23-D31] [PRE23-D32]. The AICP [PRE23-D12] includes mechanisms to introduce AI-based control loops and digital twins, to infer the KPIs a flow will achieve and reconfigure the network accordingly. Since the focus of the project is on providing deterministic support to multi-domain, multi-technology networks, the AICP is in charge of orchestrating and configuring the deterministic service in an end-to-end fashion, requesting from each domain the specific treatment of each flow.

Intent-based orchestration and service management where network services are offered as slices. This entails the cloud-native deployment of network services and component conforming to the serverless or Functions as a Service concept; Secure multi-agent-based network management and control that can address the complexity and scalability issues of centralized control and optimization.

B.2.8 Security and privacy

The CONFIDENTIAL6G project studies the requirements for confidential computing [CON23-D31] and confidential networking [CON23-D41] by gathering information from different stakeholders to bring long-term security and privacy solutions for 6G systems. Identifying the requirements, they propose a confidential networking architecture, to guarantee secure and confidential edge-cloud communication, control, and orchestration infrastructure in 6G networks. The architecture itself is formed as a collection of a multitude of technologies in the calibre of confidential orchestration, secure and decentralized data sharing, Federated AI/ML, and post-quantum TLS. As the first innovation, the CONFIDENTIAL6G project proposes an architectural design and implementation of a secure decentralized data-sharing framework applicable to decentralized 6G communication networks [CON24-D42]. Their proposed framework encompasses DLT to ensure data integrity and immutability by incorporating many other technologies such as multi-party computation, fully homomorphic encryption, and Trusted Execution Environments for privacy preservation.

Annex C Selected enablers and categorization

Table C-4 Meta-data used in D2.3 for enabler selection

Parameter Name	Explanation
Recommendation based on prioritization	Enablers are considered as high, medium, or low on prioritization scale towards inclusion into the 6G E2E system blueprint depending on their current state of development and experimentation.
High-level functionality	The main functional behaviour offered by the enabler. Needed functionalities are identified from the system requirements in Section 2.1.
Enabler TRL level	The TRL of the enabler, with TRL-1 being just a concept and TRL-9 being deployable in product.
Standards requirement	Enablers could be requiring standardization efforts, or they may not be needing any standardization.
Importance towards Migration	Certain enablers may be present in 5G, and it will be important to maintain/evolve them to ensure a smooth migration to 6G. Interoperability with 5G is one important requirement for the 6G system in Section 2.1.
Hardware requirements	The enabler may or may not require new hardware components when implemented.
Dependency on other Enablers	An enabler might have a dependency on other enablers which are being explored across the Hexa-X-II project or other SNS-JU projects.
Existence of standard Interfaces	The enablers, which have dependency on each other, may or may not have readily available standardized interfaces.
Use case applicability	The use cases (established in the Hexa-X-II deliverable D1.2 [HEX23-D12]) to which the enabler is applicable.
Fulfilment of design principles	The design principles that a given enabler fulfils.

Table C-5 Categorized enablers: Prior to KVI considerations

Category	Enabler Name
Intelligent radio interface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ITx: Intelligent transmitter • IRx: Intelligent receiver • ITRx: Intelligent transmitter and receiver • SpecShare: Spectrum sharing, coexistence
JCAS PHY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JCSWave: JCAS waveforms and frame structures • JCSRA: JCAS resource allocation
New Devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IGENE: Identification of 4 new 6G device classes (RHDRBL, HRLI, EmMTC, EN)
Flexible radio interface and protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FRRC: Flat RRC design • SICMS: Separation of IDLE mode and CONNECTED mode signalling • SDAPBCS: SDAP protocol for beyond communication services • DRRM: Data Recovery and reordering mechanisms • MRRC: Modular RRC design • RPUP: Radio Processing Units for user plane • MCIP: MAC ciphering and integrity protection • RRC: Radio protocols for beyond communication
Mobility procedure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mproc: mobility procedure harmonization • LSM: lean system and mobility • MRE: mobility related enablers
Interaction with Application layer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ANIWQM: Application-NW interaction for service differentiation and QoS/QoE management • TPS: Third-party services • ALBCS: Application-layer BCS optimization

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DQIS: Dynamic adaptation of QoS resources for interactive services • TRCS: Third-Party Resource Control Separation Enabler
Smooth Path from 5G	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mfro: Migration from 5G to 6G • LDPC: LDPC channel coding • Wwaveforms: Waveforms • MModulations: Modulations
6G network functions modularization & E2E design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E2ESM: E2E service design in modular 6G • Inter: Interactions between entities • DoM: Design of a module • Mexmp: Modularisation examples
New access and flexible topologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NoN: Network of networks • Mconn: Multi-connectivity
Cloud-continuum integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MCMM: Multi-cloud management mechanisms • IIC: Integration and orchestration of extreme edge resources in the computing continuum • MMMF: Multi-domain/Multi-cloud federation • OMCC: Orchestration mechanisms for the computing continuum
Beyond communication services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JCSSP: JCAS protocols, signalling and procedures • CPSP: Compute protocols, signalling and procedures • AAIaaS: AI-as-a-Service
AI framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MMLOps: Machine Learning Operations • AMP: Architectural means and protocols
Data framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MTF: Monitoring and telemetry framework • PNMT: Programmable network monitoring and telemetry • DDataOps: Data Operations • DDD: Data fusion mechanisms based on telemetry data
Service Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mca: Management capabilities exposure
Intent-based management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ITP: Intent Translation and Provisioning • HHD: Human-machine intent interface design • DIR: Declarative Intent Reconciliation • ICA: Intent Conflict Administration • INR: Intent Reporting
Synergetic orchestration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fedor: Federated orchestration system • MXO: Multi-X orchestration • SnO: 6G Slicing and orchestration • MMO: Multi-agent system for multi-cluster orchestration • DEOS: Decentralized orchestration system
Closed loop control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RTZS: Real-time Zero-touch control loops automation and coordination system • CLC: Closed Loop Coordination • AIMLCAS: AI/ML-based control algorithms for sustainability
Network digital twin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NDTCM: Network digital twin creation mechanisms
Programmable and autonomous networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NAM: Network autonomy • NPM: Network programmability • PFNC: Programmable and flexible network configuration
Security & privacy controls (pervasive functionalities)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CND: Confidential network deployment • QSC: Quantum-safe cryptography • LoTAF: LoTAF • JCSSec: JCAS security and privacy • TrustAI: Trustworthy AI • Trust: Trust management
Energy efficient operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MMM: Multi-source energy harvesting and power management • III: Intelligent wake-up • EATML: Energy-aware tinyML applications • EEA: Efficient network and service function allocation
Low latency wireless medium access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LLAA: Low-latency random access • ARBIS: Ad-Hoc radio bearer and inline signalling

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LLUS: Low latency UL scheduling
RF & SoC design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WLOLOR: Wideband array phase noise analysis and role of LO routing • SSOSO: Secure and scalable SoC architecture tailored to a microkernel-based OS

Table C-6 Enabler category mapping to KVI requirements

Category	Enabler Name	Requirements Addressed	KVIs Addressed
Intelligent radio interface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ITx: Intelligent transmitter • IRx: Intelligent receiver • ITRx: Intelligent transmitter and receiver • SpecShare: Spectrum sharing, coexistence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-native • Reliability to varying channel conditions • Improved data rates and spectral resource efficiency • Reduced costs due to spectrum sharing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower downtimes (Efficiency) • Reduced costs due to improved coverage, throughput and latency • Improved Trustworthiness in network performance
JCAS PHY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JCSWave: JCAS waveforms and frame structures • JCSRA: JCAS resource allocation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliability to do improved sensing and localization for indoor factory environments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower downtimes (Efficiency) • Industry specific production KPIs (Productivity)
New Devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IGENE: Identification of 4 new 6G device classes (RHDRBL, HRL, EmMTC, EN) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy efficient and neutral devices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced Total energy usage • Reduced OPEX (costs) due to reduced energy requirements
Flexible radio interface and protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FRRc: Flat RRC design • SICMS: Separation of IDLE mode and CONNECTED mode signalling • SDAPBCS: SDAP protocol for beyond communication services • DRRM: Data Recovery and reordering mechanisms • MRRC: Modular RRC design • RPUP: Radio Processing Units for user plane • MCIP: MAC ciphering and integrity protection • RRC: Radio protocols for beyond communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modularization • Energy efficient network operation • Reliability and Resiliency to adverse channel conditions and scenarios • Low latency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced Total energy usage • Lower downtimes (Efficiency) • Industry specific production KPIs (Productivity)
Mobility procedure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mproc: mobility procedure harmonization • LSM: lean system and mobility • MRE: mobility related enablers (compute aware mobility, data driven mobility) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ubiquitous connectivity • Low latency operations • Reliability due to service continuity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing number of injuries at work due to continuous connectivity, monitoring and control (Safety) • Trustworthiness in the network due to continued service continuity • Lower downtimes and Improved industry specific KPIs (Efficiency)
Interaction with Application layer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ANIWQM: Application-NW interaction for service differentiation and QoS/QoE management • TPS: Third-party services • ALBCS: Application-layer BCS optimization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service Exposures for different applications and services • Ensuring SLAs are defined well and met • Trustworthiness due to concrete SLAs and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved industry specific KPIs (Efficiency) due to service exposure and SLA determination • Trustworthiness in the network due to secured exposure framework and adherence to SLAs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DQIS: Dynamic adaptation of QoS resources for interactive services • TRCS: Third-Party Resource Control Separation Enabler 	authentication during service exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved revenues and hence, reduced overall costs due to the capability of monetizing the exposure framework
Smooth Path from 5G	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mfiro: Migration from 5G to 6G • LDPC: LDPC channel coding • Wwaveforms: Waveforms • MModulations: Modulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliability due to usage of proven enablers • Low Capital Expenditure for multiple technology enablers in 6G 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing the costs by re-utilizing the enablers in use in 5G • Provisioning Trustworthiness by using enablers that have been tested and in-use in previous generations
6G network functions modularization & E2E design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E2ESM: E2E service design in modular 6G • Inter: Interactions between entities • DoM: Design of a module • Mexmp: Modularisation examples 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modularization of network functions • Virtualization of network functions • Softwarization of network functions • Compute offloading through end-to-end service design, which accounts for compute components in the network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing the costs by virtualizing and modularizing multiple components • Reducing the costs by offloading compute tasks to the network and hence helping reduce the size and maintenance of the cobots
New access and flexible topologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NoN: Network of networks • Mconn: Multi-connectivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ubiquitous Connectivity through satellite communications and other non-3GPP networks • Reliability (same reason as above) • Resilience (same reason as above) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trustworthiness due to provisioning of ubiquitous connectivity via Satellite comm. and multi-connectivity • Lower downtimes (Efficiency) due to natural disasters or other black swan events as well as technical challenges (such as need for load balancing)
Intent-based management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ITP: Intent Translation and Provisioning • HHD: Human-machine intent interface design • DIR: Declarative Intent Reconciliation • ICA: Intent Conflict Administration • INR: Intent Reporting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zero-touch control and automation for the end user via intent-based management • Virtualization of network functions to enable intent-based orchestration • Modularization of network functions to enable intent-based orchestration • Softwarization of network functions to enable intent-based orchestration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved productivity (Efficiency) in certain industrial functions • Reduced (costs) in OPEX due to intuitive inputs and feedback for IT/OT teams in Industries • Reduce material usage/waste through virtualization and modularization of network functions/components
Synergetic orchestration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fedor: Federated orchestration system • MXO: Multi-X orchestration • SnO: 6G Slicing and orchestration • MMO: Multi-agent system for multi-cluster orchestration • DEOS: Decentralized orchestration system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtualization of network functions to enable intent-based orchestration • Modularization of network functions to enable intent-based orchestration • Softwarization of network functions to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved productivity (Efficiency) in certain industrial functions • Reduced (costs) in OPEX due to intuitive inputs and feedback for IT/OT teams in Industries • Lower downtimes (Efficiency)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enable intent-based orchestration Reliability and Resiliency due to decentralization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce material usage/waste through virtualization and modularization of network functions/components
Closed loop control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RTZS: Real-time Zero-touch control loops automation and coordination system CLC: Closed Loop Coordination AIMLCAS: AI/ML-based control algorithms for sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zero-touch control and automation for the end user via intent-based management Enhanced network energy efficiency due to AI/ML based insights and decisions Improved Reliability and resiliency towards network anomalies via closed-loop control and AI/ML 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved productivity (Efficiency) in certain industrial functions Reduced (costs) in OPEX due to intuitive inputs and feedback for IT/OT teams in Industries Lower downtimes (Efficiency) Reduced Total energy usage Improved Trustworthiness and Safety Reduce material usage/waste through virtualization and modularization of network functions/components
Network digital twin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NDTCM: Network digital twin creation mechanisms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved Reliability and resiliency towards network anomalies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved productivity (Efficiency) in certain industrial functions Improved Trustworthiness due to reliable network operations and pre-emptive decision making Reduced costs in OPEX
Programmable and autonomous networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NAM: Network autonomy NPM: Network programmability PFNC: Programmable and flexible network configuration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Virtualization, Modularization and Softwarization of network functions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved productivity (Efficiency) in certain industrial functions Reduced (costs) in OPEX due to intuitive inputs and feedback for IT/OT teams in Industries Reduce material usage/waste through virtualization and modularization of network functions/components
Security & privacy controls (pervasive functionalities)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CND: Confidential network deployment QSC: Quantum-safe cryptography LoTAF: LoTAF JCSSec: JCAS security and privacy TrustAI: Trustworthy AI Trust: Trust management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trust and Security Reliability due to multiple levels of trust mechanisms including Quantum-safe cryptography Explainability due to Trustworthy AI and Security and Privacy mechanisms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trustworthiness due to multiple levels of security and trust mechanisms, including quantum-safe cryptography as well as Explainable AI
Energy efficient operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MMM: Multi-source energy harvesting and power management III: Intelligent wake-up EATML: Energy-aware tinyML applications EEA: Efficient network and service function allocation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy efficient Network operation Energy neutral devices Energy efficient AI/ML training and inference 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced Total energy usage Reduced OPEX (costs) due to energy efficient devices, network operations as well as energy harvesting mechanisms

Low latency wireless medium access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LLAA: Low-latency random access • ARBIS: Ad-Hoc radio bearer and inline signalling • LLUS: Low latency UL scheduling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predictable low latency • Energy efficient Network operation due to reduced latency (and hence signalling) in the Random access and UL scheduling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved productivity (efficiency) due to improved network operation characteristics • Reduced OPEX (costs) due to low energy consumption in random access and UL scheduling • Improved Trustworthiness due to improved reliability owing to faster access to the network • Reduced Total energy usage
RF & SoC design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WOLOR: Wideband array phase noise analysis and role of LO routing • SSOSO: Secure and scalable SoC architecture tailored to a microkernel-based OS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy efficient operation • Security in the hardware 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced Total energy usage • Reduced OPEX (costs) due to reduced energy requirements • Trustworthiness due to secure hardware

Table C-7 Final list of categorized enablers

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